

> DESIRE6G <

**D4.3: Final report on the unified
programmable data plane layer of
DESIRE6G**

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Abstract

This deliverable describes the final, integrated version of the unified programmable data plane layer developed in WP4 of the DESIRE6G project. The report describes the different components, describing their novelty compared to the state of art solutions, their evaluation results, current limitations, and plans for improvement. The report also describes and evaluates the interoperability of this layer with services developed in WP3, and how it can help to achieve the relevant DESIRE6G requirements and fulfil the KPIs.

Keywords

Programmable data plane, NFVO, VIM, cloud-native, network function, programmable traffic management, multi-tenancy, in-band telemetry, hardware acceleration

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List of Acronyms

AAN	Access Aggregation Network
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
AQM	Active Queue Management
BFRT	Barefoot Runtime
CE	Congestion Experienced/Encountered
CNF	Containerized Network Function
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CU	Central Unit
CU-UP	Central Unit User Plane
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DU	Distributed Unit
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification
FAR	Forward Action Rule
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FQ	Fair Queueing
GPP	Generic-Purpose Processor
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling protocol

HH	Heavy Hitter
HLIR	High-Level Intermediate Representation
HQoS	Hierarchical Quality of Service
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
IP	Internet Protocol
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
LNSD	Local Network Service Descriptor
LO	Load Optimizer
LO-CP	Load Optimizer Control Plane
LO-DP	Load Optimizer Data Plane
LPM	Longest Prefix Match
MAS	Multi Agent System
ML	Machine Learning
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MPLS-TE	MPLS-Traffic Engineering
MPPS	Million Packet Per Second
NIC	Network Interface Card
NDR	Non-Drop Rate
NF	Network Function
NF-CP	Network Function Control Plane
NF-DP	Network Function Data Plane
NFR	NF Routing
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
P4RT	P4Runtime
P4S	P4 Switch
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDR	Packet Detection Rule

PDU	Packet Data Unit
PFA	Per-Flow Aggregation
PPV	Per Packet Value
PREOF	Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions
PV	Packet Value
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RT	Real Time
RU	Radio Unit
SDAP	Service Data Adaptation Protocol
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDNC	SDN Controller
SECaaS	Security as a Service
SF	Service Function
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SM	State Migration
T4P4S	Transpiler for P4 Switches
TNA	Tofino Native Architecture
UPF	User Plane Function
VES	VNF Event Streaming
VF	Virtual Function
VIM	Virtualized Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
QoS	Quality of Service
XDP	eXpress Data Path

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final report detailing the implementation and development of the unified data plane layer within the DESIRE6G architecture as a result of the work done in WP4. Building upon the requirements and architecture defined in WP2, the report describes the different components, their evaluation results, current limitations, and plans for improvement. It covers enhancements to network service deployment, data plane techniques, traffic management, monitoring solutions, and hardware accelerators. These components collectively address performance, latency, and resource-sharing challenges, enabling a cloud-native approach to packet processing.

The document assumes familiarity with DESIRE6G terminology and architecture and complements earlier deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [4]. To ease understanding, some important component descriptions and architectural aspects are repeated. However, many technical details from earlier work are referenced, detailing the effort made after D4.2 (during months 24 to 32) of the project.

Key contributions

We highlight the following key contributions:

- We outline the service requirements, and we show how those relevant for the unified programmable data plane and pervasive monitoring map into the DESIRE6G architecture (section 2.1).
- We provide explanation and proof on how the list of KPIs derived in WP2 may be fulfilled by the unified programmable data plane (section 2.2).
- We provide an analysis on the potential impacts of the WP4-specific DESIRE6G architecture on the 3GPP architecture (section 2.3).
- We present updates on the WP4-related components reported in D4.1 and D4.2, and description of new components developed after month 24, providing their implementation details, usage interfaces, evaluation and limitations analysis in the following macro-areas:
 - Deployment and configuration of network service subgraphs (section 3).
 - Infrastructure network functions for network service execution (section 4).
 - Cloud-native data plane components (section 5).

- Performance isolation for deep slicing support (section 6).
- Pervasive monitoring framework (section 7)
- Application and network function acceleration and offloading (section 8).

1 Introduction

This document serves as a final report and an extension of D4.2 [4], and focuses on the unified data plane layer of the DESIRE6G architecture. We describe in this document the work conducted in WP4 across the whole DESIRE6G project, providing a short summary of the work already documented in D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [4], while detailing the results of the activities performed between month 24 and month 32.

In this deliverable we present updates and improvements of the components presented in D4.2, and we also describe new components that were not previously included.

In Section 2, we present an overview of the programmable unified programmable data plane components and how they fit into DESIRE6G architecture. We outline the set of service requirements, defined in D2.1 [5], and we highlight how the WP4 components satisfy the programmable data plane and the pervasive monitoring requirements. We also provide a complete report on the KPIs to measure the DESIRE6G project objective, specified in the DoA, that are targeted by WP4. We describe how we fulfilled them and justify why we could not fulfil the very few exceptions. Section 2 also includes an analysis of the impact of the DESIRE6G architecture on 3GPP architectural vision.

In Section 3, we describe the components for deployment and configuration of network service subgraphs, such as the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) and the Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (Local NFVO) of the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML). Since the IML-LNFVO's main role is the deployment and configuration of the Infrastructure NFs, these NFs are also described in this section. However, we kept Section 4 to add an explicit reference to the description of the Infrastructure NFs and to keep the document structure that is similar of that of D4.2.

In Section 5, we present updates on the cloud-native data plane components, which are the IML control plane proxy layer and the Run-Time load optimizer, and the P4 data plane aggregator.

In Section 6, we expand the set of solutions for performance isolation for supporting deep slicing by adding the RAN inter-slice scheduler and the network-wide hierarchical resource sharing with DSCP marking.

In Section 7, we provide updates on the pervasive monitoring framework components, such as the MAS telemetry agent, telemetry collector, P4 in-band network telemetry, RAN telemetry exposure, self-

contained monitoring. We also present two new components for heavy-hitter detection and cloud monitoring manager.

In Section 8, we present updates on the components for accelerating or offloading the applications and network functions to enhance throughput and latency performance. Updates to the modules for accelerated CU-UP for SmartNIC, offloading of security functions to Bluefield NIC, accelerated Neural Network execution, remote hardware acceleration with vAccel and Tofino implementation of PREOF are presented, as well as new components such as offloading the UPF functionality to Bluefield NIC, in-network computing with P4RROT and Teraflow SDN controller for PREOF.

We conclude the document with Section 9.

2 Architecture and components of the unified programmable data plane

The final form of the DESIRE6G system architecture is described in D2.2 [2]. The high-level view of architecture is defined in Section 2.1 of [2] and is shown in Figure 1. The main scope of WP4 are the End-to-End (E2E) Programmable Data Plane (PDP) and the Physical Infrastructure Layer, depicted respectively as the pink and grey layers in Figure 1 and the pervasive monitoring framework depicted in Figure 2.

The components of the PDP layer defined and developed in the DESIRE6G project are the following:

- Infrastructure Management Layer (IML). It is responsible for transparent data plane optimization, hardware acceleration, and network and application function deployment, i.e., it is the bridge between the logical and the physical network function. The IML hides the implementation and deployment details of the Network Function (NF) – Data Plane (DP) from the NF-Control Plane (CP) by providing a simple unified view of the data plane. IML provides APIs towards the various upper layer entities. Besides, IML also includes components for data plane program deployment (see Section 3), which is generally referred to as “Enhanced Virtual Infrastructure Manager” and Local “Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (Local NFVO)” which are further described in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively. Further, IML includes CP proxies for the configuration of the different Business NFs and Infrastructure NF-Data Planes (NF-DPs) (see Section 5.1).
- The Infrastructure NF-DPs defined in the DESIRE6G project are the following:
 - NF Routing: Implements the forwarding graph between NF-DPs in network services (denoted RR in the figure, see Section 4.2 of D4.2 [4] and also the description in section 3.3).
 - Run-time Load Optimizer: Consists of a Load Balancer (LB) and a Heavy-hitter Offloader (HH) (see Section 5.2).
 - Some in-band telemetry (INT) modules that may be handled as Infra-NFs, i.e., deployed and instantiated together with the NF DPs (or UE, Section 7.3, 7.4) by the IML based on the service (monitoring) requirements received from SMO.
 - UE2ServiceMapper: Assigns packets generated by UEs to the appropriate network service (see Section 4.1 of D4.2 [4] as well as section 3.3).

- TransportAdapter : Ensures transport over various tunnelling protocols between DESIRE6G sites (see Section 5.4 of D.2.2 [2]). TransportAdapter functions have been merged with NF Routing (see section 3.3).
- Various accelerated RAN/Core Network Functions as well as Application Functions (AFs) enabling in-network computation (see Section 8).
- Per-slice isolation and dynamic multi-tenant traffic management (see Section 6).
- A PREOF component, which is a possible high-reliability realization to the Transport network, (see Section 8.7).

FIGURE 1: DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE AND LAYERS (SEE SECTION 2.1 OF [2])

The Pervasive monitoring (and intelligent data aggregation) framework in DESIRE6G enables:

1. **Service Monitoring** that focuses on assessing the performance and availability of specific services or applications critical for business operations. This involves collecting data with high granularity to facilitate closed-loop operations that uphold Service Level Agreements.
2. **Infrastructure Monitoring** that involves tracking the health and performance of the underlying hardware, software, and network components supporting these services.

The following figure is depicting a simplified reference scenario including a multi-site DESIRE6G environment. Section 7 describes complementary aspects to D.4.1 [1] and D.4.2 [4] with regards to the

pervasive monitoring framework, such as the telemetry agents, data collectors with advanced functions (i.e., heavy-hitter detection) and in-network control, P4-based INT on NF-DPs or UEs, RAN telemetry exposure, software monitoring and a cloud monitoring manager, together enabling fine-grained, scalable, and slice-aware and infrastructure-level visibility across the DESIRE6G architecture.

FIGURE 2: PERVERSIVE MONITORING ARCHITECTURE (SEE SECTION 4.2 OF [2])

2.1 Mapping of design specifications to the architecture

The service requirements to be met by the DESIRE6G system architecture were formulated in D2.1 [5]. These requirements were structured according to several categories:

- **E2E Service Orchestration requirements** to enable the orchestration of services spanning different segments (including the RAN, Transport and Core domains, and in some cases even the UE domain) and physical sites.
- **Autonomous Networking requirements** to account for short response times that can only be achieved using autonomous networking techniques.
- **Programmable Data Plane requirements** enabling customised packet treatment features and the selection of the most efficient platform for a given network or application function.
- **AI integration requirements** as means to achieve the optimization of the performance or the operation of the DESIRE6G system supporting demanding 6G use cases.

- **Pervasive monitoring requirements** to enable a fine-grained visibility of the status of the network infrastructure and the services deployed on top to comply with the reaction time of the 6G use cases requirements.

This categorization of the DESIRE6G system requirements have shaped the layers of the DESIRE6G architecture as documented in [2]:

- An **Intent-based Orchestration layer** in charge of fulfilling the **E2E Service Orchestration requirements**.
- An **Optimization and network control layer** capable of meeting the **Autonomous Networking requirements**.
- An **E2E PDP layer** that addresses both the **Programmable Data Plane requirements** and the **Pervasive Monitoring requirements**.

AI integration requirements have a **vertical impact** on the 3 main aforementioned layers of the architecture due to the potential role of AI in all 3 layers of the DESIRE6G architecture.

The mappings of the different requirements are summarized in Table 1 Each of the requirements is mapped to one or more primary (P) and secondary (S) architectural blocks. WP4’s focus is on the DESIRE6G Programmable Data Plane layer, and as such targets the definition and implementation of that layer, along with its pervasive monitoring capabilities and the integration of AI capabilities in the PDP layer. Therefore, WP4 components oversee fulfilling the E2E Programmable Data Plane, Pervasive Monitoring and AI integration requirements. This has been addressed by the WP4 components in the DESIRE6G system architecture as described in the following sections that list the requirements formulated in [5] along with the mapping of those requirements to the DESIRE6G functional modules supporting them.

TABLE 1: REQUIREMENTS MAPPING TO THE DIFFERENT ARCHITECTURAL LAYERS/BLOCKS

			Intent-based Orchestration Layer					Optimization and Network Control Layer					Programmable Data Plane Layer			
			Federation	IBN	Opt. Engine	MLFO	SO	MAS: Agent	SECaaS / D-MUTRA	NF-CP	Pervasive Monitoring	SDNC	IML	InfraNF-DPs	Custom NF-DPs and Afs	VIM
E2E Service Orchestration Requirements	E2E-SO-REQ-1	Network slicing					P									
	E2E-SO-REQ-2	Intent Based Management		P			P									
	E2E-SO-REQ-3	Cloud Native approach					P									
	E2E-SO-REQ-4	Federation of administrative domains	P				P									

Autonomous Networking Requirements	AN-REQ-1	Distributed decision-making			S			P					S				
	AN-REQ-2	Orchestration of AI/ML pipelines					P										
	AN-REQ-3	Security of MAS Agents						S	P								
	AN-REQ-4	Trust between agents						S	P								
	AN-REQ-5	Securing AI/ML pipelines and MAS inter-agent communications						S	P								
Programmable Data Plane Requirements	PDP-REQ-1	Unified Programmable Data Plane layer								S			P	S			
	PDP-REQ-2	Cloud Native approach								S			P				
	PDP-REQ-3	Slicing, Multitenancy and QoS enforcement								S			P				
	PDP-REQ-4	Offloading of network/service/AI functions										S	P	S			
	PDP-REQ-5	Integration of customised telemetry									S		P	S			
AI Integration Requirements	AI-REQ-1	AI models Integration in different architectural levels			P		P						P				
	AI-REQ-2	AI models to optimize the performance			P												
	AI-REQ-3	AI models data privacy			P												
	AI-REQ-4	AI models Sustainability			P												
	AI-REQ-5	AI Algorithm robustness			P						S						
Pervasive Monitoring Requirements	PM-REQ-1	Conducting both service monitoring and infrastructure monitoring			S		S					P		P			
	PM-REQ-2	Pervasive monitoring system must extend all the infrastructure domains					S					P		P			
	PM-REQ-3	Pervasive monitoring system must										P				P	

	extend to the UE														
PM-REQ-4	Monitoring data to AI/ML data consumers in the architecture			S	S					P					
PM-REQ-5	Pervasive monitoring system must be scalable									P					
PM-REQ-6	Pervasive monitoring system must be customizable						S			P					

2.1.1 Programmable Data Plane requirements

The PDP requirements shown in *italic* text below are listed in section 11.2.3 of D2.1 [5], accompanied with a description of how we meet each of them with the DESIRE6G architecture components.

- *DESIRE6G system must include a unified Programmable Data Plane layer, from the RAN to the Core network segments, spanning different heterogeneous HW targets.*

The DESIRE6G architecture allows for a unified view of the programmable data plane, seamlessly managing scaling operations, hardware acceleration, and function deployment, while abstracting the complexity of handling the physical resources. This is achieved via the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML), which hides the implementation and deployment details of the data plane functions (NF-DPs) from the control plane functions (NF-CPs). For example, even if an NF-DP is vertically or horizontally disaggregated into multiple data plane programs running on different HW/SW targets, IML ensures that its NF-CP only sees a single NF-DP instance and handles the complexity of managing the disaggregated packet processing components.

- *DESIRE6G system PDP design must follow a Cloud Native approach to abstract the implementation of the functions from the different heterogeneous HW targets.*

In DESIRE6G, we developed components making the management of data plane resources like the cloud-native approach in traditional computation. IML consists of a **control plane proxy** (see Section 5.2) that separates the control planes from the data plane implementations by hiding the deployment and implementation details of the data plane and providing a simple single-

instance view to the control plane. The proxy enables seamless optimization in the data plane including vertical/horizontal disaggregation, data plane program aggregation, etc. We also developed a **compiler-based approach to support the multi-tenant usage of hardware P4 programmable devices** (see Section 5.3). The method emulates the virtualization of hardware P4 targets and supports their better resource utilization by enabling the execution of multiple P4 program simultaneously. The control plane access to the different P4 programs is isolated by the control plane proxy component.

- *DESIRE6G system PDP must support slicing, multitenancy and QoS enforcement.*

As described in D2.2, enforcing QoS requires support from both control/management layer (WP3) and the data plane layer. Data plane layer and PDP can react to changes in network conditions at packet-level timescale, aiming to satisfy the requirements in case of, e.g., congestion. In DESIRE6G, we developed non-conventional **traffic management (TM) approaches** (see Section 6) that require the flexibility of PDPs. The method consists of two data plane components, 1) a packet marker that applies the resource sharing/performance isolation policy by tagging packets with a packet value and 2) an active queue management method that drops or ECN-marks packets with the minimum value in case of congestion. The marker can encode QoS policies between a large number of users. In D4.2 we have shown how the packet marker method can scale up to handle 1 million users with a single Tofino switch. We integrated the control of the policy encoding packet marker into IML. The TM components can independently handle QoS requirements on throughput demand, latency requirements and reliability. We proposed a fine-grained policy description and definition that is then mapped to configuration of the applied traffic management and policy enforcement method. In Section 6.3 of this deliverable, we also present an alternative approach where QoS policy hierarchies are used to determine the desired throughput allocation between services, slices, sub-slices and users, and the packet marker assigns different DSCP drop precedence levels according to the precomputed allocation. The DSCP drop precedencies are then used by simple WRED AQM methods with different RED profiles. The throughput allocation is periodically recomputed based on the throughput measurements done by the data plane. The evaluation of this method shows that deep HQoS policies can be enforced at the network level and only the packet marking node requires programmable data plane element. To support multitenant usage of hardware PDPs, we created a P4 data plane aggregator component and a control plane proxy components that

enable the sharing of PDP resources among tenants and isolates per tenant access to the data plane resources.

- *DESIRE6G system must support the offloading of network/service/AI functions to the appropriate acceleration platform.*

The vAccel framework in DESIRE6G enables efficient offloading of network, service, and AI functions to the most suitable acceleration platforms, optimizing performance across diverse environments. By abstracting hardware specifics, vAccel provides a unified interface that can dynamically map high-level operations, such as image inference, classification, and other AI tasks, onto various accelerator types (e.g., GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs) available in edge or cloud environments. This flexible, plugin-based architecture supports seamless switching between accelerators without altering application code, allowing network and service functions to leverage hardware acceleration based on real-time demands. The integration within DESIRE6G allows operators to fully utilize edge resources and orchestrate workloads to appropriate resources as needed, ensuring optimal execution and low latency.

- *DESIRE6G system PDP must enable the integration of customised telemetry features in the architecture.*

The adoption of PDP in DESIRE6G fosters the integration of flexible and efficient solutions to collect relevant metadata from the traffic flowing in the network. This solution is an example of passive monitoring, exploiting the INT model, with no need of probing traffic (ad-hoc traffic injected in the network to measure specific metrics). With the adoption of local registers, the INT header can be enhanced with additional “custom” metrics, collected at the PDP nodes, to be conveyed to the telemetry collector.

2.1.2 Pervasive Monitoring Requirements

The pervasive monitoring requirements shown in *italic* text below are listed in section 11.2.5 of D2.1 [5].

- *DESIRE6G system must support a pervasive monitoring system capable of conducting both service monitoring and infrastructure monitoring.*

In DESIRE6G, a comprehensive monitoring system has been conceived. In particular, different solutions have been combined to collect heterogeneous data from all the considered

technology domains. Two main types of collection strategies have been considered: **service monitoring** and **infrastructure monitoring**. For service monitoring, an In-band Network Telemetry (INT)-based approach is used. This method enables data collection at line rate, as packets traverse the network. To achieve this, specific headers are added to each packet, allowing metadata to be collected at every transit node along the path.

For infrastructure monitoring, relevant metrics can be collected from the infrastructure entities, for example the network devices (nodes and link) and the cloud resources. For this purpose, specific frameworks/probes are adopted (see Section 7.7) and pushed to the data consumers (i.e., AI/ML-based routines) via publish-subscribe system.

- *DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring system must extend all the infrastructure domains present in the architecture, including the SW level in terms of securing its correct execution.*

As explained, in DESIRE6G specific frameworks/probes are adopted in the different domains (i.e., network, cloud, radio) to periodically collect the status of the resources (i.e., total and available resources) and the status of instantiated entities (i.e., the consumption of the resources of a specific VM, Pod or container). In addition, the infrastructure monitoring allows to monitor the correct “software execution” by performing a periodical assessment of its execution. This is done through the insertion of probes into the control flow graph of the workload, recording timestamps in a buffer when they are traversed. A post processing of these timestamps enable to construct time series characterizing the software execution. This helps in detecting anomalies, or unexpected behavior in the execution of the software.

- *DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring system must extend to the UE.*

One of the specific focus of DESIRE6G is the extension of the INT domain up to the UE. This design opens the possibility to exploit INT to convey relevant metric collected at the UE. The relevant metrics can include the radio link information, GPS positioning and application specific metadata to trigger service adaptation. In particular, this information can be exploited at service/application monitoring by the Telemetry Collector, being able to automatically detect relevant changes in the system and potentially re-adapting the service.

- *DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring system must be capable of making available the monitoring data to AI/ML data consumers in the architecture.*

The data collected in the INT service monitoring and one related to infrastructure monitoring are available to the AI/ML data consumers through different channels. For the service monitoring, the data are collected by the telemetry collected and made available to service agents through a dedicated API. For the infrastructure monitoring, the data is exposed to a publish-subscribe framework where data consumers can attach to exploit the collected data.

- *DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring system must be scalable in terms of computing and communication resources.*

All the monitoring solutions (INT for the service and publish-subscribe for the infrastructure) have been selected to guarantee scalability. In the INT-based system, the adoption of a telemetry collector, that supports multiple levels of aggregation enables the possibility to reduce the rate of INT samples, by exposing statistical metrics with different levels of aggregation.

For the infrastructure monitoring, the selection of a proper publish-subscribe system, is natively reliable and scalable, supporting a huge number of consumers. Moreover, the publish-subscribe architecture embeds reliability techniques to automatically recover the full operation even in case of failure of one of the data processing units.

- *DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring system must be customisable.*

Heterogeneous metrics can be collected by the pervasive monitoring system. Then, the system offers the possibility to filter desired metadata among the ones collected by the system.

Considering service monitoring, besides standard INT metrics, other custom metrics can be added to the INT header (GPS position, CPU status, battery levels, ...)

For the infrastructure monitoring, all the data are made available for being consumed in the push-subscribe system. The metrics are provided with service/infrastructure labels/tags to help consumer to filtering the data.

2.2 KPIs

In this section we present the KPIs defined for the DESIRE6G project Objectives that are relevant for the unified programmable data plane. We present a total of 19 KPIs, distributed among DESIRE6G Objectives 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, described in the DoA. We fully fulfilled 14 of them, partially fulfilled four and not fulfilled just one.

We describe how we fulfilled them and justify where we could not in the following 6 tables, one for each target objective. In each table, we mention the relevant objective and each of the KPIs associated. For each KPI, we present a status, which can be either **Fulfilled**, **Partially Fulfilled** or **Not Fulfilled**, and a comment describing the consortium efforts towards its fulfilment.

TABLE 2: OBJECTIVE 1 KPIS

Objective 1 (O1)	Design a functional architecture for 6G mobile networks to support the next generation of URLLC use cases
KPI 1: Meeting the evolving KPIs and forming the KVis for the DESIRE6G use cases that fall under extreme URLLC category	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>We developed a traffic management solution based on packet tagging that can implement different resource sharing policies between traffic aggregates (e.g., slices, users, etc.). We described the solution in D4.2 and in this deliverable. The method applies a coupled AQM that can handle the latency and throughput requirements separately. This way ensuring low latency (L4S) for throughput demanding traffic can also be satisfied. For L4S traffic, the method ensures less than 1ms average queuing delay and the maximum delay is 2ms – limited by the L4S queue size. The implementation is available in P4 for Intel Tofino (TNA Arch.), in eBPF/XDP and as a DPDK program. This traffic management method was demonstrated in the Y1.5 Digital Twin demo, the EUCNC 2025 demo and will also be presented in the final Digital Twin demo.</p> <p>We designed and developed a load optimization component as part of IML described in D4.2 and in this deliverable that can offload latency sensitive and/or throughput hungry (heavy hitter) flows to hardware-based network function implementation (e.g., running on an Intel Tofino or a smartNIC) while keeping traffic with less strict requirements on software-based network function instances. The proposed method can apply hardware offloading on demand, solving both static and dynamic state migration between software and hardware instances and reconfiguration of forwarding. The</p>

method has already been implemented in P4 and tested in a high-speed testbed. The evaluation measurements presented in this deliverable shows that both static and dynamic state migration can be done without extra packet losses. Hardware-based network functions like an UPF running Tofino results 1-10 usec packet processing delay, independently of the traffic mix. The state migration from the software instance to the hardware one can be done less than 50ms.

vAccel enables the transparent offloading of network, service, and AI functions to heterogeneous accelerators (e.g., GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs) available in edge and cloud. This capability ensures that compute-intensive tasks such as real-time inference can be executed with low-latency and high throughput, while preserving application portability. Evaluation results in Section 8.5 show that vAccel reduces inference time when mapped to appropriate accelerators, demonstrating low response times in edge scenarios and supporting the predictability required for URLLC use cases. The plugin-based architecture allows dynamic selection of the optimal hardware backend at runtime, ensuring service continuity even under changing workload and resource conditions. By abstracting hardware-specific details and enabling automatic workload placement on the most suitable accelerator, vAccel contributes directly to the latency and reliability requirements of xURLLC applications, complementing the packet-level optimizations and load offloading mechanisms developed in WP4.

We have designed and implemented PREOF-DetNet on P4 switches with TNA architecture and DPDK servers. This enables us to enhance reliability in the deterministic transport network by duplicating packets, sending them to the same destination through multiple paths, discarding duplicates at the destination, and reordering packets in case any disorder occurs during transmission.

	Tests have been conducted on this implementation by sending traffic at a rate of 1 Gbps with varying packet sizes: 64B (small), 512B (medium), and 1024B (large). In the worst-case scenario, a packet loss rate of 2.29061×10^{-6} was observed, which remains within the limits tolerated by URLLC.
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TABLE 3: OBJECTIVE 3 KPIS

Objective 3 (O3)	Design a “AI-native architecture” for 6G systems. While 5G solutions aimed at providing machine learning solutions over-the-top, DESIRE6G seeks to update the network architecture so that it natively supports AI operations.
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KPI 3.3: <1s (depending on the involved elements) automatic resource selection and network programmability to validate the required workflows entailing the orchestration and control functions, and the defined interfaces.

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The local NFVO (LNFVO) subcomponent of IML presented in D4.2 and this deliverable solves the deployment of a subgraph of the network service on heterogeneous resources available in a DESIRE6G site. IML is responsible to deploy network function including both data and control plane components and application functions. In addition, data plane components could be deployed on a Kubernetes cluster, running as packet processing software instances (containerized network functions), or hardware data plane like Intel Tofino and Netronome Agilio. IML implements a resource selection process and applies the in-built functions of Kubernetes and custom plugins for deployment on programmable data plane hardware with minimal overhead. The concept of this component was described in D4.1, the implementation details and use case scenarios were presented in D4.2, and the evaluation measurements are described in this deliverable. According to the investigated scenarios shown in this deliverable, the latency introduced by LNFVO for resource selection, preparation of

	configurations and filling tables of infrastructure network functions during the deployment process is less than 1 second.
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KPI3.4: 10^6 inferences per second and sub-0.1 ms latency per-inference for in network ML.

Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	<p>The results of throughput and latency of SOL optimized neural networks, shown in Section 8.4.4, highlight a consistent improvement over the baseline. The figure of 10^6 inferences per second can be theoretically achieved by leveraging parallel computation.</p> <p>The latency per-inference for in-network ML, using stochastic learning automata as an example of lightweight in-network RL [73] [74], has been estimated in the sub-0.5 millisecond range at the 99th percentile. Since the performance evaluation of this approach was conducted using Mininet/BMv2, considerably lower inference latencies are theoretically achievable on hardware targets (e.g., DPUs or ASICs), potentially reaching the order of tens of microseconds (sub-0.1 ms).</p>

KPI3.5: 10x less model training compute latency, 10x higher energy compute efficiency at training time, higher scalability, and resiliency than single point-of-failure cloud-based solutions.

Status	Comment
Partially fulfilled	We consider this KPI only partially fulfilled in the context of WP4 as we showed in Section 8.4.4.3 that a 2x improvement during the training phase is possible but not a 10x improvement.

KPI3.7: >70% performance improvement in AI training using RDMA in the edge computing platform.

Status	Comment
N/A	The DESIRE6G project has not focused on improving the AI training performance using RDMA, hence this requirement is not applicable

TABLE 4: OBJECTIVE 4 KPIS

Objective 4 (O4)	Unified management and control of heterogenous programable data planes and hardware accelerators, while enabling increased controllability for the tenant and service.
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KPI4.1: Integration of at least three P4 programmable targets and a non-P4 programmable accelerator (e.g., FPGA) into the unified data plane layer through IML.

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>Three different Infrastructure NFs have been functionally integrated (i.e., NF router, UE2service mapper, INT) considering bmv2 software switch and Tofino switch backends and abstract models.</p> <p>The LNFVO subcomponent of the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML) presented in D4.1, D4.2 and this deliverable currently supports the deployment of P4-based network functions on Intel Tofino, Netronome Agilio and Software targets (as CNFs running in Kubernetes pods with BMv2 or T4P4S) through a plugin system with a common API specified in this deliverable. For the deployment of hardware targets, it introduces a plugin system with a simple REST API. A plugin for a non-P4 programmable target, the nVidia BlueField2 with DOCA SDK has also been created to demonstrate the flexibility of the plugin system and show how it can support the deployment of non-P4 network functions. The deployment components of IML are described in Section 3.3.</p>

KPI4.2: Enabling the deployment of virtual P4 pipelines on at least two P4 targets

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>We developed a P4 program aggregation component called P4-MTAGG and a P4Runtime-based Control Plane proxy to support multitenancy on P4 programmable hardware data planes where virtualization and shared usage are not possible by default. The final release includes the toolset for Netronome Agilio, SW targets (using v1model) and Intel Tofino (using the TNA architecture model), enabling the generation of an aggregated P4 program from multiple P4 programs. The proxy ensures the isolated access to data plane objects from the corresponding control plane components via P4Runtime API, enabling the integration of any</p>

data planes (including non-P4 programmable ones) using P4Runtime as control plane API. The performance evaluation of the aggregation method is presented in this deliverable. The implementation was detailed in D4.2.

KPI4.3: In-network computing as a service enables the offloading of traditional computations to at least one ASIC and one DPU targets.

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	We continued the work on a P4-code generation library called P4RROT developed for offloading application layer computations to programmable data planes. The library is based on Python and it aims at lowering the burden of developing data plane programs implementing simple request-reply communication and payload processing. We extended the P4RROT library with a partial support of Intel Tofino ASIC and added new primitive objects to it to cover a wider range of application scenarios. Note that in addition to Tofino, P4RROT can also generate P4 code for BMv2 and Netronome Agilio smartNIC/DPU targets. We presented a simple measurement in this deliverable that show the response times of P4RROT applications offloaded to smartNIC and Tofino compared to a software-based counterpart running on an x86 server.

KPI4.4: Enable the use of at least three (3) execution devices (cloud GPU accelerators, edge CPUs, edge GPU accelerators) by a single application binary.

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The vAccel framework enables seamless execution of a single application binary across diverse hardware targets by abstracting hardware-specific functionality through a plugin-based architecture. Using the same vAccel API and binary, we have demonstrated successful execution on: 1) cloud-based GPU backends (via vAccel-SOL with CUDA), 2) edge CPUs (e.g., Raspberry Pi), and 3) edge GPU devices (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson). The application dispatches high-level inference calls, such as <code>classify_image</code> or <code>depth_estimate</code> , which are resolved at runtime by vAccel's plugin

system without modifying the application itself. This multi-target deployment is demonstrated in Demo 2 (monocular depth estimation), where the same Python script runs unmodified across cloud and edge targets with hardware-specific acceleration provided transparently via vAccel.

KPI4.5: Offloaded in-network computations result in less than 100 usec response time

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>We extended the P4RROT library with a partial support of Intel Tofino and added new primitive objects to it to cover a wider range of application scenarios. On Tofino ASIC, it can result in a response time less than 10usec while for Netronome Agilio smartNIC it is still below 100usec. The P4RROT code generator’s response time performance is show in Section 8.6 for both hardware targets in an application offloading scenario</p> <p>The evaluation of the DPU-based 6GUPF with VIAVI and TRex traffic generators confirmed that hardware offloading enables stringent latency requirements to be met. Specifically, the transfer of GTP-U encap/decap (entirely in hardware) and flow-handling functions from the host CPU to the DPU reduced processing overheads and minimized software-induced queuing delays. As a result, offloaded in-network computations (i.e., match and encap) consistently achieved sub-100 μs response times, significantly improving upon NIC- and CPU-based implementations, which exhibited latencies in the order of hundreds of microseconds to 1 ms under comparable load conditions. The overall packet latency remains around 300us since queuing and flow handling, while fully offloaded at the DPU, are not totally hardware accelerated yet.</p>

TABLE 5: OBJECTIVE 5 KPIS

Objective 5 (O5)	Develop and validate a performant, measurable, predictable, and customizable data plane that supports multi-tenancy.
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KPI5.1: Iteration between DU control loops for managing resources between services

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	In Section 6.2 we have investigated the support of iterative control loops at the DU level for managing resource allocation between services. Specifically, the proposed inter-slice scheduling approach was executed in an online manner, continuously updating PRB allocations based on real-time telemetry. By leveraging a Real-Time Intelligent Controller (EdgeRIC), these iterations are performed at TTI (Transmission Time Interval) granularity, ensuring that service-level requirements were met under dynamic traffic conditions.

KPI5.2: In-network feature extraction in less than 200 μ s, compared to current >10s time required by external SW features extraction. FSM pre-enforced for traffic engineering adaptations to be performed at wire speed, also within novel programmable DPUs

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	Feature extraction demonstrated in the security functions offloaded in the Bluefield-2 DPU related to UPF telemetry (less than 100us, see Section 8.2). FSM enforced at the P4 DPAC collector to detect excessive accumulated latency and immediate adaptations fully at the data plane with sub-ms recovery time (see Section 7.2).

KPI5.3: Application-aware failure/congestion detection performed in-network, reducing 5x the detection time compared to application layer detection (e.g., generate explicit congestion notification)

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	In-network DPAC intervention achieves more than 10x detection and enforcement time reduction with respect to higher layers closed loops involving the SDN controller and the application layers (See Section 7.2)

KPI5.4: End-to-end measurement through in-band network telemetry with sub-ms granularity

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The INT implementations at L4 and L2.5 including the UE-RAN segment can report per-packet segment-based and end-to end latency measurements at the microsecond granularity (see Section 7.3)

KPI5.5: Transparent acceleration of AI algorithms without SW adaptation for widely used AI frameworks

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	As shown in Section 8.4.4, we achieve transparent acceleration for 60 models from the popular computer vision Python library Torchvision

KPI5.6: Support automatic deployment on the target infrastructure, including CPU-based and HW accelerators

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	The Local NFVO subcomponent of IML takes care of the deployment of network function instances on either software or hardware targets or both (e.g., in heavy hitter offloading use cases). In Section 3.3, we show the helm-based approach of containerized software data plane deployment process and introduce the LNFVO's plugin system for the deployment on P4 and non-P4 programmable hardware data plane targets.

KPI5.7: >50% inference latency reduction for AI algorithm optimizations and 5-10x overall throughput increase

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	In Section 8.4.4 we achieve a latency reduction well beyond 50%, with a 6 times shorter latency in the GPU in average. Same for the throughput, were in average we achieve a 9 times higher throughput in the GPU.

KPI5.8: In-network solution enforcing Hierarchical QoS (HQoS) among and withing slices across multiple (>2) hierarchical levels

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	In Section 6.36.3, we present a new resource allocation method that can enforce the network-level fulfilment of HQoS policies with more than 2 hierarchy levels in arbitrary network topologies. The method uses programmable gateway nodes where the user activity is monitored and a policy-based DSCP tagging is applied. Other network nodes only need to implement conventional WRED AQM with three different RED profiles for the uses three DSCP values. The evaluation of the method is shown in Section 6.3.3. 6.3.3.

TABLE 6: OBJECTIVE 6 KPIS

Objective 6 (O6)	Develop a cross-domain, infrastructure-independent, software security by executable rewriting technology enabling trustworthy immersive process monitoring and remote control backed on lightweight permissioned Distributed Ledger Technology
KPI6.3: 100% of X-86 platform ELF formatted binaries (including P4 compiled binaries for software targets)	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	All ELF-formatted binaries and libraries, either deployed natively or containerized are supported by the SECaaS and D-MUTRA remote attestation solution. This covers P4 compiled programs (for x86 platforms).
KPI6.4: 20% maximum average runtime overhead incurred by the composite security compared to non-protected versions of representative sample of each targeted software type as defined in KPI6.3 above. 0% increase of the one-time authentication complete cycle of the self-contained authentication novel scheme compared to TPM based authentication (given in the range of 500 msec for reference)	
Status	Comment
Fulfilled	This KPI is related to and discussed in WP3. In fact, D-MUTRA and its attest after starting pattern brings a significant latency reduction compared to TPM based authentication, offering a unique 0-latency at start (compared to 500 msec for a TPM). This is made possible by our dynamic integrity verification of the loaded binary memory map as opposed to TPM static measurement made prior execution which uses the execution file.

TABLE 7: OBJECTIVE 7 KPIS

Objective 7 (O7)	To integrate components and to build PoC demonstrators validating the whole architecture
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KPI7.1: >1000 real/emulated devices, simultaneously requiring >100 heterogeneous realistic services (including ultra-low latency-bounded services)

Status	Comment
Fulfilled	<p>Pervasive monitoring of >100 heterogeneous realistic services is supported by INT in a scalable way, being able to collect transit metadata in a per-packet basis at wire-speed. (see Sections 7.2 and 7.3)</p> <p>In Section 6.4 of D4.2, we introduced a scalable packet marker implementation of PPV traffic management solution. The evaluation results show that our initial implementation running on a single Tofino instance can be scaled up to handle 35,800 individual users and with further simple improvements can be scaled up to more than 250,000 users with different resource sharing policies (services).</p> <p>The scalability of IML-LNFVO will be evaluated and measured in the demos and PoCs developed in WP5.</p>

2.3 Impact of the WP4-related DESIRE6G architecture on the 3GPP architecture

This section summarizes the main areas where changes to the 3GPP architecture are likely required to enable the WP4-related main innovations in the mobile networks.

2.3.1 SMO-related APIs and NF functionality

In the DESIRE6G concept, the service deployment is coordinated via the management plane (SMO) and it is assumed that a UE attaches to a specific service. In the 3GPP architecture, the NF UPs (UPF, CU-UP) provide specific functionality (or capability) that is known by the NF CPs (SMF, CU-CP) and based on this and the PDU Session requirements as well as other information, like the topology, the NF CPs make the NF UP selection.

In order for the SMF to have the necessary information for proper UPF selection and for the UPF to have the information for service mappings to NF DP sub-graphs the following is needed: i) SMF pre-

configuration by SMO (of which UPF/site(s) may be selected for a given service request & RAN site); ii) UPF (pre-)configuration by SMO. this should include NF sub-chain configuration for a given ServiceID, but also the mappings of how a given PDU Session info received from the SMF (DNN, S-NSSAI, QFI,...) maps to a ServiceID, siteID, UEID, etc.

2.3.2 DESIRE6G header related functionality

Currently, the NF router, NF DP business logic, the INT functionality and the transport routers need to support the DESIRE6G header to achieve proper service chaining (details in in D2.2), which - besides the implementation needs to properly process the DESIRE6G header - also means that the DESIRE6G header itself needs to be standardized.

2.3.3 IML APIs

In general, the interface(s) below the NF UPs (e.g., UPF) are out of scope of 3GPP. However, it should be verified that the P4Runtime northbound API of the ILM contains any relevant information that might come from the upper layers. The list of required features for this interface should probably be standardized.

2.3.4 Other enhancements to the current architecture

It should be noted that DESIRE6G allows for other, new features, for example:

- GTP removal/replacement option, i.e., allowing for any other L2/L3 tunnelling option between RAN and Core.
- E2E service support, extending the current edge-to-edge approach to include also the UE and the Server.
- Standalone handovers, when the user plane can act on its own to learn the new location without the need of control plane support as described in D2.2.

Since there is currently no support for such features in 3GPP, they would need significant additions to the current 3GPP specifications.

There is on-going work to analyse the impact on the WP4-related DESIRE6G architecture to the 3GPP architecture, which is planned to be documented in a scientific publication.

3 Components for deployment and configuration of network service subgraphs

In this section, we describe the two key components that take part in the deployment of the network service subgraph provided by the SMO in each DESIRE6G site, according to the processes detailed in D2.2 and D4.2, the Enhanced VIM and the IML's Local NFVO subcomponent.

The enhanced VIM provides a container runtime infrastructure supporting the deployment of both containerized NFs and application functions (AFs) on a Kubernetes cluster. It provides increased security and good performance. The Local NFVO gets the deployment requests directly from the SMO. The request is a service graph partition that contains NFs and AFs, their logical network interfaces and the logical links between them.

The Local NFVO is responsible for the deployment of NFs and AFs using the Enhanced VIM, or its built-in deployment plug-ins for hardware data plane targets. It also configures the interconnections between the different NF data plane components via NF Routing infrastructure functions.

The Local NFVO is also responsible of the configuration of other infrastructure functionalities (UE2Service Mapping, Transport adapter configuration in NF Routing). Note that the scope of these components is restricted to a single DESIRE6G site where a pool of computational resources including data plane hardware is available. These components have already been introduced in D4.2 [4]. In the following part of the section, we overview the final implementation of the components in a self-contained way and refer to previous deliverables, if possible, to avoid repetitions.

3.1 DESIRE6G site setup, components and roles

Figure 3 illustrates an example for a simple DESIRE6G site where network and application functions can be deployed in a Kubernetes (K8S) cluster while hardware accelerated network functions can be offloaded to a dedicated P4 Accelerator Switch. In the DESIRE6G, the K8S cluster is managed by the enhanced VIM detailed in Section 3.2. The site itself is controlled by a IML-LNFVO instance deployed on one of the servers (see Section 3.3). In this simple setup, the site is connected to the data network through a DESIRE6G Gateway that implements the UE2ServiceMapper, the NF Routing infrastructure

network functions and acts as an IP router to the external network domain. The DESIRE6G Gateway is a P4 program with a local control plane that is preinstalled on the gateway Tofino switch. In addition to the data network, the DESIRE6G-specific control messages are forwarded through a management network. The IML instance provides its API over the management network (e.g., VXLAN) to the SMO. If a network service subgraph is provided by the SMO, the IML instance deploys the network and application functions and optionally infrastructure NFs on the K8S cluster via the enhanced VIM. Hardware data plane implementations of NFs can also be deployed to the available accelerator hardware like the dedicated accelerator switch in the figure. The deployment is also managed by the IML-LNFVO through the deployment plugin preinstalled on the target device. As a last step of the deployment, the IML can also access the local control planes of all infrastructure NFs and configure them according to the received network service subgraph, this step is needed for the appropriate subgraph/network function chain execution.

FIGURE 3: EXAMPLE SITE SETUP

3.2 Enhanced VIM

In the final phase of DESIRE6G, we have delivered a lightweight and flexible VIM tailored for secure and latency-sensitive 6G workloads. The finalized runtime infrastructure supports the seamless deployment of sandboxed workloads with a strong focus on performance, isolation, and integration into existing

Kubernetes-based systems. It combines unikernel execution, microVM-based containers, and standard container packaging through three main components:

- **urunc**: a minimal, CRI-compliant runtime for launching applications packaged as unikernels or minimal Linux-based containers.
- **bunny**: a streamlined packaging tool that transforms both unikernel images and standard Linux userlands into OCI-compliant artifacts.
- **kata-containers**: a secure container runtime leveraging lightweight virtual machines (using Firecracker) for strong workload isolation.

This architecture provides operators and developers with a single, unified control plane, while supporting deployment flexibility across the isolation-performance spectrum.

3.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

At a high level, our VIM architecture integrates with Kubernetes via the Container Runtime Interface (CRI) and is structured around a multi-runtime design, enabling different isolation mechanisms under a consistent orchestration layer. The key architectural components are:

Runtime Layer (urunc + kata-containers):

urunc serves as a lightweight, pluggable CRI runtime designed for rapid spawning of unikernels and stripped-down Linux containers. It plugs directly into `containerd`, making it fully interoperable with Kubernetes, `k3s`, and other container orchestration systems.

kata-containers provides hardened isolation through Firecracker-based microVMs, suitable for workloads requiring strong separation and a hardened execution environment.

Image Layer (bunny):

bunny replaces the earlier `bima` tool and brings a much-improved user experience. It supports building OCI-compliant images from both unikernels and traditional Linux root filesystems. This makes it possible to package standard Linux-based services, such as web servers, proxies, or language runtimes, and run them through `urunc`, even if they are not specifically designed as unikernels.

This compatibility layer greatly improves the applicability of `urunc`, as it allows services that require familiar Linux interfaces to benefit from lightweight sandboxing without requiring major rewrites or repackaging.

3.2.2 Deployment and Integration (`urunc-deploy`):

We have developed `urunc-deploy`, a drop-in deployment tool that configures a Kubernetes node for `urunc` use in a matter of seconds. It handles all required CRI and containerd setup and ensures that packaged workloads (via `bunny`) can be launched with no additional configuration. This drastically reduces the time and effort needed to adopt the stack and makes it suitable for rapid edge or cloud deployments.

3.2.3 Implementation

The complete stack is production-ready and has been tested in Kubernetes environments with both manual and auto-scaled workloads.

- `urunc`: Capable of spawning workloads with sub-second latency and near-zero overhead. It now supports both raw unikernels and minimal Linux-based containers, giving operators a spectrum of options depending on application constraints.
- `bunny`: A major upgrade over `bima`, `bunny` includes an intuitive CLI, template-based image descriptions, and support for both single-purpose unikernels and full userland applications packaged for minimal Linux. It is CI/CD-friendly and supports multi-arch builds, including ARM and x86.

`kata-containers`: Integrated with Kubernetes via `containerd-shim-kata`, with `Firecracker` as the default hypervisor. We have contributed patches to improve VM startup time and in general the microVM lifecycle, and we have explored options to reduce the overhead of the networking setup in high-throughput workloads, aligning with the low-latency goals of DESIRE6G.

3.2.4 Usage and Interfaces

- **CRI-Compatible Execution:** All components are CRI-compliant, making it possible to launch unikernel or microVM-based containers using the same Kubernetes APIs and tooling.
- **Multi-Isolation Deployment Model:** Operators can deploy the same application as a regular container (via runc), as a microVM (via kata), or as a unikernel/minimal-Linux container (via urunc), using the same deployment spec and runtimeClass annotations.
- **Standardized Image Format:** bunny ensures compatibility with existing registries and CI/CD workflows, using the OCI image format. This simplifies image distribution and versioning across environments.
- **Rapid Onboarding and Deployment:** With urunc-deploy, a node can be made urunc-ready in under a minute, without manual configuration. This streamlines onboarding and encourages experimentation and adoption in hybrid edge/cloud setups.

3.2.5 Evaluation

We evaluated the complete stack using a cold-start benchmark based on a stateless HTTP echo function deployed through Knative. The same application was packaged in three variants: standard container (runc), microVM-based container (kata), and unikernel/minimal-Linux (urunc).

FIGURE 4: NORMALIZED RESPONSE TIMES AGAINST RUNC

Figure 4 plots the normalized response times against runc (the generic low-level runtime used in containerd/k8s) for our example HTTP echo function for the various runtimes used in the experiment. Results show:

- urunc offers the lowest cold-start latency, suitable for scale-from-zero serverless applications.
- kata provides strong isolation with a moderate performance cost.
- runc has the fastest spawn times but lacks strong sandboxing.

These results confirm that our modular runtime architecture supports flexible trade-offs without altering deployment or orchestration semantics.

3.2.6 Limitations and further plans

While the system is deployable and functional in Kubernetes-based environments, future work will focus on:

- Broadening application support, including networking stacks, languages, and frameworks that benefit from the urunc execution model.

- Enhancing bunny with composable templates for packaging complex services or service meshes.
- Evaluating the stack across more heterogeneous architectures (e.g., embedded ARM, RISC-V).
- Automating runtime selection at scheduling time based on workload profiles or policies.

All software components are released under open-source licenses and available for community use: urunc¹, bunny², kata-containers³.

3.3 IML-Local NFVO

The Local NFVO is a subcomponent of IML responsible for deploying a network function subgraph to a local site. The subgraph is provided in yaml format by the SMO to the IML and it describes the part of the network service to be implemented by the given DESIRE6G site and the transport network connections to other DESIRE6G sites (e.g., tunnels over the data network). The IML first refines this yaml, e.g., deciding on which node to place the NF-s and provides the resulting local network service descriptor (LNSD) to the LNFVO. The LNFVO component has already been introduced in D4.2 [4]. In this section, we mostly focus on the final architecture, the changes and new features we implemented in the last phase of the project and the functional and performance evaluations.

3.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The IML Local NFVO advances beyond existing ETSI-compliant NFVO implementations by introducing an orchestration paradigm that unifies cloud-native container orchestration with hardware-programmable data plane deployment in a single, site-local control domain. Current NFV orchestration solutions predominantly target homogeneous virtualized environments (e.g., VM- or CNF-based

¹ <https://github.com/urunc-dev/urunc>

² <https://github.com/nubificus/bunny>

³ <https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers>

workloads) and rely on standard Kubernetes scaling and networking features. In contrast, the Local NFVO presented here delivers several additional features:

- **Unified orchestration for heterogeneous targets** – Manages CNFs on x86, smart NICs, and P4-programmable switches (e.g., Intel Tofino) within a single framework, including automated P4 code compilation, loading, and execution, supports not only P4-programmable data plane targets but Bluefield-2 with a binary built with DOCA.
- **Hardware-aware service graph mapping** – Translates SMO-provided YAML subgraphs into deployable configurations with physical resource affinity, SR-IOV VF binding, and port mapping to satisfy the latency requirements of subgraph executions (latency between entering a packet to the site and leaving it or terminating at an AF).
- **Dual-networking orchestration** – Integrates SR-IOV/DPDK-based P4 inter-node paths with Multus-managed multi-interface networking, enabling packet forwarding in align with the NF service graph, allows the system to combine the flexibility of virtual networking with near line-rate throughput on hardware data planes.
- **Portable P4 NF deployment** – Enables the same NF to run as a DPDK-based CNF or on hardware accelerator (e.g., Intel Tofino, Netronome Agilio). This level of portability is not addressed in conventional NFV orchestration frameworks.
- **Decoupled scaling logic** – Separates initial deterministic deployment of NFs from runtime scaling, handled by the Load Optimizer IML subcomponents. AFs uses the conventional scaling approach of Kubernetes.

3.3.2 Implementation

Since the publication of D4.2, we extended IML-LNFVO with additional subcomponents. Its architecture is depicted in Figure 5. IML-LNFVO provides a REST API to the SMO through which the local network service descriptor (LNSD) describing the network service subgraph can be provided.

FIGURE 5: ARCHITECTURE OF IML-LNFVO

In contrast to the previous deliverable, where all the NF-DPs and AFs were deployed by the LNFVO, we modified the system to support pre-deployed functions and interfaces on a given site. A pre-deployed function could be served by a dedicated middlebox in the network or a K8S or OpenStack cluster not directly controlled by the IML. The pre-deployed functions and their interfaces are described in a site configuration (`site-config.yaml`) file as an input to be considered by the LNFVO when deploying a LNSD (see examples in Section 3.3.3).

IML-LNFVO implements three main steps:

- Placement:** During the first step, it assigns the network and application functions to various computational and data plane resources located in the DESIRE6G site. In this decision relies on 1) the Site Configuration data file, 2) the Site Resources local resource usage database, 3) the available NF-DP implementations. The optimization goal is to ensure the latency budget of the forwarding graph execution provided by the SMO in the `yaml` file and minimize the infrastructure cost. In the current implementation, we use a heuristical algorithm to prefer NF deployment on K8S and only deploy network functions to PDP hardware if the latency requirements cannot be satisfied otherwise. The outcome of this phase is an annotated `yaml`

file, where each NF is assigned to a node in the infrastructure and their implementations are also selected.

- **Deployment:** This phase gets the annotated LNFVO yaml file as input and performs the deployment of network functions and application functions via the hardware data plane plugins or the Enhanced VIM. If a deployment target is a hardware accelerated data plane, the target specific deployment plugin is used to prepare the data plane binary and load it to the hardware. The plugins are currently available for Intel Tofino (TNA arch.), Netronome Agilio and nVidia Bluefield2 (non-P4 programmable, executing DOCA code). For the deployment on Kubernetes, LNFVO uses Helm's templating engine and Kustomize's patching to customize, create the deployment Kubernetes manifests for NF and AF deployment, infrastructure NF deployments (NFR and UE2ServiceMapping) and the virtual L2 links between the interfaces of these containers. The templated Helm chart is then deployed via the Enhanced VIM to provision the network function graph defined in the network service descriptor provided by the SMO. The SR-IOV configuration ensures high-performance inter-node communication, while Multus facilitates attaching additional network interfaces to support multi-interface NFs. The Helm-based deployment method has already been described in D4.2.
- **InfraNF configuration:** As introduced D2.2 and D4.2, within the DESIRE6G domain we use a DESIRE6G header for routing across the different network function instances. This special header is attached to the packet and filled with service specific information by the UE2Service Mapping infrastructure function while the forwarding logic of the service subgraph is implemented by the NF Routing infrastructure functions. The LNFVO processes the annotated subgraph and synthesize the configurations (i.e., table entries for the different instances of infraNFs) for the UE2Service Mapping and NF Routing instances.

3.3.2.1 InfraNFs – Infrastructure Network Functions

Infrastructure network functions are data plane elements that ensures packet forwarding and processing according to the network service definition of DESIRE6G. These elements are part of the proposed DESIRE6G infrastructure and responsible for three tasks: 1) assignment of packets to a network service, 2) forwarding packets along a chain of network functions according to the service

graph, and 3) tunnelling between DESIRE6G sites interconnected with a transport network. These elements rely on a special DESIRE6G header detailed in D2.2. The infrastructure network functions are configured and controlled by the Local NFVO subcomponent of IML. Besides, some Infra NFs need to be configurable by external entities. For example, the UE2ServiceMapper would need to be configured with new PDU Session (UE) information by the UPF CP, based on the input from the SMF. In D4.2, we have already introduced the design and implementation of the introduced Infra NFs, while their high-level control plane interfaces (REST APIs) have already been detailed in D2.2. In this deliverable, we briefly introduce the changes we implemented during the integration with other components in the demo scenarios of WP5.

UE2ServiceMapper

UE2ServiceMapper is an infrastructure NF in DESIRE6G. Its main role is to map the traffic from a specific user to a specific service and RAN site the UE is connected to. In downlink direction, it maps the destination IP address (or other UE identifier) of incoming packets to a service id and RAN site location id. In downlink case, it is deployed at the first DESIRE6G site where the packet enters the DESIRE6G network domain. In case of a broadband Internet service, it is in the mobile core after the Internet gateway. In case of an end-to-end service, it is deployed near the application function generating traffic towards the UE or other application functions in the DESIRE6G domain. The current implementation creates and fills a DESIRE6G header with service id and RAN site location id and the id of the next NF to be applied in the forwarding graph of the network service and adds it to the packets (right after the Ethernet header). Note that in downlink direction this component has a role like the Packet Detection Rules (PDRs) and Forward Action Rules (FARs) in the 5G UPF. In uplink direction, the component is deployed in RAN sites or in the UE (in the end-to-end service deployment scenario) and assigns the packet to a network service and fills the RAN site location. Note that in this case, filling the RAN site location field in the DESIRE6G header is trivial and can be done without user classification, reducing the memory and computational overhead of this component at RAN sites.

The main structure of this component remained the same as it was detailed in D4.2. In D4.2, it only worked with IPv6 addresses, since then we have extended it with the support of IPv4 addresses. The L3 address is used to determine the UE and the network service identifiers that are then added to the DESIRE6G header. The UE2ServiceMapper also has a local control plane that provides a REST API as a

northbound interface and communicate with the HW/SW switches via P4Runtime. The northbound interfaces of the service have been described in D2.2.

NF Routing

NF Routing (NFR) is another infrastructure network function that plays a crucial role in the PDP layer of DESIRE6G. The component processes the DESIRE6G header and implements the forwarding logic of network service graphs. It is a special router that uses the service id, location id and nextNF id to steer the packets towards the responsible NF. In addition to routing, NF Routing is responsible for resolving the nextNF id when an NF finished with the packet's processing. In D4.2, we described the packet processing pipeline of NFR in details. The pipeline has remained the same, we slightly improved the implementation to support NF-DPs with multiple input and output interfaces (see D2.2) and L2 forwarding between NFR and the NF-DP instances. NFR also has a local control plane that provides a REST API as a northbound interface and communicate with the HW/SW switches via P4Runtime. The northbound interfaces of the service have already been described in D2.2.

Transport Adapter

Transport Adapter is the infrastructure NF responsible for interconnecting different DESIRE6G sites over non DESIRE6G-capable transport networks. This component implements different tunnelling protocols like VXLAN or GTP over the transport network between two DESIRE6G sites. As described in D4.2, Transport adapter is not a separate infrastructure NF but it is a subfunctionality to the NFR component implemented as a new action in the NFRouter table. Currently, we support GTP and VXLAN encapsulation and decapsulation.

D6GGateway

As UE2ServiceMapper act as a gateway at the border of the DESIRE6G network domain and it is the first element before the execution of the service's forwarding graph, we created an aggregated infrastructure network function that combines the pipelines of UE2ServiceMapper, NF Router and acts as a L3 router to the external domain (implementing L3 routing, ARP and partial ICMP functionalities). The D6GGateway was implemented in P4 for both TNA and v1model architectures.

Requirements against the network function data planes

As described in D2.2, each NF-DP may have multiple input and output interfaces through which it can ingress and egress packets. The input interfaces determine how the packet needs to be processed (i.e., the input state in addition to the packet headers), the output interfaces reflect the output state of the NF. We assume L2 forwarding between the NFR and NF-DP instances, thus these logical interfaces are identified by different MAC addresses. We assume that an NF-DP is a packet processing binary for a given target that meets the following requirements: 1) it implements Ethernet as L2 forwarding, 2) it can parse or simply skip the D6G Header in the packets, 3) it receives packet on one of the input interfaces and sends packets on one or multiple output interfaces (multiple output interfaces are used for, e.g., packet cloning or mirroring) and 4) it provides a P4Runtime interface for configuring the data plane objects. Note P4Runtime is a general control plane API that can also work with fixed function switches and non-P4 programmable targets.

3.3.2.2 Deployment plugins for hardware-accelerated targets

To seamlessly integrate different data plane targets into the IML-LNFVO, we created a simple plugin system with a REST API. Each plugin runs as a systemd service on the target or on machine hosting the target (e.g., smartNIC/DPU) and provides the same REST API to the IML-LNFVO service. The implementation of the API calls is target specific. The API calls are the following:

- **/prepare_nf** – is a POST method that requires two arguments: 1) an identifier that is a unique string for the NF-DP instance and 2) a file that contain the target specific project files (binary or source code). This call prepares the NF-DP implementation for execution by storing the binary in the appropriate folder or compile it for the given target and SDK. This call may take time and needs to work asynchronously.
- **/status/<identifier>** – is a GET method that returns a json with two fields identifier and status. The status describes if the NF-DP was loaded successfully or not, if the prepare_nf phase is finished or not. The status could be queued (waiting for preparation), running (preparation script is running), completed (NF-DP is ready for execution) and failed (preparation process failed).
- **/execute_nf** – is a POST method with a single identifier argument. If the NF-DP instance with the given identifier is in completed state, the call will terminate the running data plane program

and restart the target with the new NF-DP instance. The start-up process may take few seconds depending on the target. This call is also asynchronous.

- **/execute-status** – is a GET method that returns information on the executed NF-DP instance. It returns a json file with two fields: 1) identifier of the NF-DP instance under execution and 2) status of the execution that could be Starting, Running and Failed. If the status is Running, the NF-DP instance has successfully been launched on the target.

We have implemented the deployment plugin for Tofino ASIC, Netronome Agilio smartNIC and nVidia BlueField-2 DPU, available on GitHub: <https://github.com/desire6g> (e.g., iml-tna-plugin).

3.3.2.3 Helm-based Kubernetes deployment

The deployment process begins with the local network service descriptor (LNSD) (see D2.2 [2]), which contains:

- Kubernetes manifests for each NF
- A list of links representing the NF graph structure.

Using this information, the IML's Local NFVO dynamically populates the values.yaml file with variables needed for the Helm chart used for the templating of the deployment. Each NF's deployment manifest is further customized and extended using Helm's templating engine and Kustomize's patching to incorporate desired parameters and connections. The templated Helm chart is then deployed to provision the network function graph defined in the network service descriptor provided by the SMO. The SR-IOV configuration ensures high-performance inter-node communication, while Multus facilitates attaching additional network interfaces to support multi-interface NFs. The key changes in the LNFVO implementation are listed below:

- The Helm-based deployment framework has been detailed in D4.2. During the integration we implemented some new features and changed some parts of the subsystem: In the LNSD there is a new field in the Functions declarations: `domain` which can be `internal` or `external` this denotes whether the function can handle the Desire6G header or not.
- There is now a distinction between a Network Function (NF) and Application Function (AF): NF is always internal, and AF can be both. Furthermore, an AF can be considered a User Equipment

(UE) if its `is-ue` field is true, this is needed for the automatic filling of the table entries of the UE2SM.

- The UE to Service Mapper (UE2SM) Infrastructure NF (Infra NF) is now deployed automatically on a node if there is an external AF or UE on that node, aggregated with the Network Function Router (NFR). This aggregated NF acts as a gateway to the Desire6G domain for external pods and as such responds to ARP and ICMP queries. This NF is called Desire6G-Gateway (DESIRE6G-GW).
- If there are some pre-deployed functions/interfaces on a site it can be described in a site specific config and included in the service graph, that way the control plane is automatically filled for the Infra NF-s.
- This can be also used in the scenario where the UE/AF is not deployed by the LNFVO and just communicate with it through a bridge on the host.
- If a service graph spans multiple sites, the site-to-site connection can be described in the LNSD, describing the nextNF on the other site and the transport adapter.
- Furthermore, there were some simplifications and renames of some fields.

3.3.3 Functional evaluation and examples

The Infra NF-s can be run with the BMv2 software switches which is optimal for debug purposes, this was used for functional evaluation. A minimal viable NF (reflector) was made for debug purposes which is just swapping the packet's source and destination MAC addresses, this is a minimum functionality which is required of an NF to allow (optional) interim switches between them.

The following figures depicts some example topologies detailing the resulting deployed pods from the logical graph.

FIGURE 6: EXAMPLE WITH NFR CONNECTING A CONTAINERIZED NF-DP

In Figure 6, two AFs (pkt-src and pkt-dst) deployed on Node 1 exchange messages through a reflector NF. The traffic was emulated with the iperf tool. The network function reflector is deployed on Node 2. On Node 1, the two AFs require traditional IP network stack so for assigning DESIRE6G headers to the

packets the full DESIRE6G-GW function is needed. However, on Node 2 the deployment of a single NFR instance is enough to coordinate the packet streams.

FIGURE 7: EXAMPLE FOR A DESIRE6G SITE CONFIGURATION

In Figure 7, there are some pre-deployed functions on a DESIRE6G site which is described in the site-config.yml: pkt-src and a DESIRE6G-GW on Node 1 with their interfaces. A pre-deployed pod cannot be modified by the LNFVO, therefore it needs to have extra interfaces to be able to connect to later deployed NF-s. When the LNSD is deployed to the site, these pre-deployed functions are taken into account and the DESIRE6G-GW control plane is filled with entries accordingly via the given management IP (controlplane-ip). In this example there are some predeployed functions on the site that are described in the site-config and taken into account during the deployment of the LNSD

FIGURE 8: EXAMPLE SHOWING THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN TWO DESIRE6G SITES

When a service graph spans multiple sites, the site-to-site connection needs to be defined in the LNSD of the respective sites. In this example topology, Site 1 contains only the pkt-src and Site 2 contains the AF pkt-dst and an interim NF (reflector). In this case the transport type is external (not DESIRE6G-aware, e.g., normal IP network), the transport adapter (TA) is encapsulating/decapsulating the DESIRE6G packets in VXLAN, for this process the source and destination addresses need to be specified. Furthermore, the subsequent NF in the other site needs to be specified as well for the DESIRE6G header needs to be filled accordingly before the transport adapter. After the execution of the This example topology demonstrates a site-to-site connection

When a service graph spans multiple sites, the site-to-site connection needs to be defined in the LNSD of the respective sites. In this example topology, Site 1 contains only the pkt-src and Site 2 contains the AF pkt-dst and an interim NF (reflector). In this case the transport type is external (not DESIRE6G-aware, e.g., normal IP network), the transport adapter (TA) is encapsulating/decapsulating the DESIRE6G

packets in VXLAN, for this process the source and destination addresses need to be specified. Furthermore, the subsequent NF in the other site needs to be specified as well for the DESIRE6G header needs to be filled accordingly before the transport adapter.

FIGURE 9: DEPLOYMENT OF A FORWARDING GRAPH WITH A BRANCH

In Figure 9, there is a simple network function called alternator which has two interfaces and works the same way as the reflector except for each incoming packet it sends the outgoing packet alternating between the two interfaces. In order to differentiate between the two interfaces in the graph description, there is an interface index (i.e., alternator:1 and alternator:2). This way the network function router (part of DESIRE6G-GW in the figure) decides the next logical component in the forwarding graph, determining based on the outgoing interface (1 or 2).

3.3.4 Performance evaluation

We extended the initial evaluation presented in D4.2 with two new aspects.

We measured the time of the service graph deployment using LNFVO for two examples shown in Figure 6 (NFR-only), Figure 9 (Branching) and Figure 8 (Site-to-site) in the previous section. In the case of the

nfr-only the whole deployment takes ~3.4s , for the branching case it is ~3.7s and for the site-to-site it is ~3.5s. The deployment can be break into the following stages and their respective times:

- **gen (LNFVO)**: generating the values.yml from the Insd.yml in memory
- **dump (LNFVO)**: dumping values.yaml to disk
- **helm (K8S)**: calling helm with the graph chart values.yaml and post-render with kustomize
- **startup (K8S)**: waiting for the D6G-Gateway pod to be reported as ready by k8s
- **cp-fill (LNFVO)**: filling of the match-action tables of D6G-Gateway instances

The table below shows the contribution of different processing steps in the total deployment time split between K8S and IML-LNFVO. The most significant components are the K8S deployment (helm) and the startup time of the pods (startup). The yaml processing and the preparation of the helm configuration have negligible overhead (18-30 ms) and the configuration of the infraNFs is also quite fast and can be done in a parallel way, ensuring scalability.

	NFR-only	Branching	Site-to-site
<i>gen</i>	0.0003 s	0.0003 s	0.0003 s
<i>dump</i>	0.0153 s	0.0270 s	0.0261 s
<i>helm</i>	0.9250 s	1.2556 s	1.1069 s
<i>startup</i>	2.4272 s	2.2917 s	2.2253 s
<i>cp-fill</i>	0.0972 s	0.1852 s	0.1444 s
Total deployment	3.465 s	3.7598 s	3.503 s
Total IML-LNFVO	0.1128 s	0.2125 s	0.1708 s

In D4.2, the interconnection of NFs and infraNFs (e.g., NFR router, UE2ServiceMapper) in the normal mode relied on Linux L2 bridges and veth pairs, introducing a 1Gbps (with 1500B packet sizes, ~83000 packets per second (PPS)) performance ceiling along an NF chain. We replaced the L2 bridges for interconnecting NFs to a VPPSwitch running on the host OS. The VPPSwitch supports Memif interfaces that is now used to interconnect DPDK-based NF and NFRouter instances. Memory interfaces designed for efficient communication between VPP and containers, enabling zero-copy packet processing, reducing latency and improving throughput compared to veth pairs and traditional L2 bridges. In the

normal mode with the same scenario shown Figure 4 in D4.2, the performance was increased from 83000 PPS to 2.1 million PPS, assigning a single CPU core to the VPPSwitch for packet processing. We plan to complete the evaluation measurements with more complex scenarios developed in WP5 (based on demos and PoCs).

3.3.5 Limitations and further plans

Subfunctions can be leveraged instead of SR-IOV VF-s, but currently there is no working k8s CNI plugin for it, only device plugin exists. The automatic Infra NF deployment and networking connectivity could be contained in a k8s CNI plugin for easier adoption in the future. The IML-LNFVO is now available under an open-source license on GitHub: <https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-LNFVO>

4 Infrastructure network functions for network service execution

The core infrastructure network functions UE2Service Mapper Transport Adapter and Network Function Router have been described in detail in 3.3.2.1, including the advancements of these components and the main changes we have made since D4.2 [4]. This section is only an explicit reference to the part of the document where the infrastructure network functions are discussed. The main reason to merge the Infra NFs with the IML-LNFVO is that the IML-LNFVO's main role is the deployment and configuration of these Infra NFs.

5 Cloud-native data plane components

In this section, we focus on the cloud native data plane optimization patterns implemented through the Control Plane Proxy layer of IML. Most components and mechanisms have been introduced and detailed in D4.2 [4]. In this section, we focus on the final implementations, implemented new features, changes and evaluation results.

5.1 IML-Control plane proxy layer

IML’s Control Plane Proxy serves as a separation layer between the data and control planes of packet processing NFs as depicted in Figure 10. Its primary role is to enable data plane optimization, including rearrangement, aggregation, or disaggregation of P4 programs in a manner that remains invisible to the network function control planes. Additionally, it introduces a persistency layer, ensuring that even if the data plane structure is modified, the control plane does not need to re-upload the active match-action table entries or reconfigure other data plane objects.

FIGURE 10: IML CONTROL PLANE PROXY HIDING DATA PLANE OPTIMIZATIONS

Building upon the foundational work detailed in D4.2 [4], the IML Control Plane Proxy has undergone significant advancements in the past phase of the project. Our development efforts have been rigorously focused on addressing previously identified limitations, particularly concerning message throughput, latency, and the proxy's applicability in diverse, real-world network scenarios, aligning directly with DESIRE6G's overarching goals for a unified programmable data plane layer.

5.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

FlowVisor [6] is a pivotal tool in the OpenFlow [7] ecosystem, enabling hardware virtualization and isolating control plane access in SDN. By acting as a transparent proxy between OpenFlow controllers and network switches, FlowVisor partitions the underlying physical network into multiple virtual networks. Each virtual network, or slice, operates independently and is managed by its respective controller, facilitating multi-tenancy and resource sharing without compromising isolation.

Currently, there is no direct equivalent of FlowVisor for P4 data planes, but similar tools and frameworks like P4Visor [8] exist to enable data plane virtualization, multi-tenancy, and control plane isolation in P4-based systems. These tools are however limited to BMv2 and not actively developed and do not support data plane optimizations we target. The IML Control Plane Proxy integrates multiple use cases and hides data plane transformations like load balancing, aggregation, disaggregation, heavy hitter handling. Initial results on the control plane proxy have been published in [9][10].

5.1.2 Implementation

Each control plane proxy initiates a set of gRPC servers and clients used for P4Runtime messaging. The NF control planes connect to the servers, where the proxy emulates a network node. Meanwhile, the clients within the proxy connect to the P4Runtime interface of data plane hardware or software switches, presenting themselves as controllers to these nodes. The initial proxy implementation has been described in Section 5.2.2 of D4.2. The structure of the final implementation is depicted in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11: IMPLEMENTATION STRUCTURE OF THE CONTROL PLANE PROXY

The key elements are the following:

- 1) Request processing: The P4Runtime communication relies on gRPC that uses Protobuf to define the communication protocol. The proxy creates a gRPC server ((1) in the figure) for each controller to act as data plane for controllers. It uses integers to recognize tables, actions, and each type of entity. This mapping between names and integers is generated during the compilation of the P4 file. For each entity (or update) in an arrived request, the proxy transforms the integer identifiers to a string identifier based on the source P4 program. After that, it adds the configured prefix and then converts to an integer identifier used in the aggregated or disaggregated P4 program and the target device where the identified data plane object is located ((2) in the figure). In contrast, when an answer arrives from the data plane target, we have to convert it to a string identifier, find the correct prefix, remove it, and convert to the integer identifier of the source P4 program to look exactly the same for the controller like if there would not be any data plane optimization.

- 2) Persistence: To ensure the persistence of the entries, the proxy stores every incoming request and saves them to Redis (element (3)). When the structure changes, we can replay all the requests that arrived, transforming the identifier based on the new structure.
- 3) Batching: While the proxy is aggregating, it can batch table updates with a delay-based approach, which means that it can wait for a specific amount of time and compress the table updates into bigger, aggregated requests ((4) in the figure).
- 4) Rate limit: The proxy itself can rate limit the outgoing throughput of control plane requests to avoid overloading the data plane ((5) in the figure).
- 5) Sending to device(s): For the data plane, the proxy creates a P4Runtime client that connects to one or more devices, performs the master arbitration, and optionally sends the data plane program to the devices ((6) in the figure).
- 6) Resource sharing policy: The proxy can be configured by the higher layer. It can also change the rate limit, batching settings, and the aggregation structure (element (7)).

In the last phase of the project, the proxy implementation has also gone through a performance enhancement. As outlined in Section 5.2.4 of the D4.2 [4] report, the initial Python-based gRPC implementation of the proxy introduced a measurable processing overhead, limiting the achievable P4Runtime message throughput. To directly tackle this, we initiated comprehensive investigations into the precise table write times, which we henceforth refer to as latency. This detailed analysis was crucial for pinpointing bottlenecks and understanding the exact message propagation delays within the proxy, aiming to ensure optimal responsiveness and efficient resource utilization.

A major breakthrough in mitigating these performance constraints was the successful implementation of a delay-based batching mechanism. This strategy allows for the intelligent aggregation of P4Runtime messages, significantly reducing the overhead associated with processing individual requests. Through this optimization, we have achieved an impressive approximately 1.5x increase in overall throughput. Crucially, this throughput improvement was realized with an accompanying reduction or maintenance of low latency, demonstrating the efficiency gains from bundling messages without introducing undue delays.

Further substantial performance enhancements were unlocked through the strategic introduction of the `asyncio`⁴ library. As mentioned in Section 5.2.5 of the D4.2 report, we had begun investigating how to resolve the limitations of the Python-based gRPC library. The adoption of `asyncio` directly addresses this by enabling highly efficient, non-blocking I/O operations within the proxy. This architectural shift has yielded another approximate 1.5x improvement in performance.

5.1.2.1 Supported data plane optimization patterns

The key role of IML Control Plane Proxy is to hide data plane optimization from the control planes of the network functions. We identified four different optimization patterns that are currently supported by the Control Plane Proxy.

FIGURE 12: PATTERN #1: DATA PLANE AGGREGATION

FIGURE 13: PATTERN #2: DISAGGREGATED DATA PLANE

The **aggregation pattern** assumes that different pipelines are co-located on the same executing data plane target. It has two variants: 1) In vertical aggregation the two network function data planes (i.e., P4 programs) run on the same target independently. After receiving the packet, the target decides the data

⁴ <https://docs.python.org/3/library/asyncio.html>

plane pipeline to be executed and processes the packet accordingly, emulating virtualization and multitenancy. In this case, the Control Plane Proxy provides isolated access points for the control planes of each network function, ensuring that each control plane can only get access to data plane resources it is responsible for. 2) In horizontal aggregation, the two pipelines are chained after each other to save the I/O overhead of unnecessary packet recirculation. In this case, if the packet went through the first pipeline, it is immediately passed to the second pipeline. Note that in case of software targets horizontal aggregation can merge the packet parsing, reducing the overhead of packet parsing, in addition to packet I/O operations. However, the two pipelines implement a different network function and thus have different control plane entities. The Control Plane Proxy hides that multiple pipelines are chained together by providing isolated access points to the data plane resources similarly to the vertical case. The access points in the current implementation are gRPC/P4Runtime service endpoints listening on different TCP port numbers as illustrated in Figure 12.

The **disaggregation pattern** splits the packet processing pipeline of a network function into multiple pipelines to be executed on different hardware or software data plane targets as shown in Figure 13. The disaggregation can help in better exploiting the data plane resources. In case of a complex pipeline, disaggregation may be the only option for deploying it on constrained hardware targets. The Control Plane Proxy is responsible to provide a unified – single instance - view of the distributed data plane pipeline to the corresponding control plane entity and manages the data plane objects seamlessly (e.g. inserts entries into a table in one or multiple appropriate data plane target(s)). The Control Plane Proxy currently supports two variants of disaggregation: 1) Vertical disaggregation when multiple instances of the same pipeline are running on different targets in the network and the table entries are disaggregated among the instances. 2) Horizontal disaggregation when the packet processing pipeline itself is split into multiple less complex subpipelines and each subpipeline is executed by a different data plane target. For example, table A and table B of a pipeline are executed one after another, but they are implemented by two different data plane targets. In this case, the proxy needs to keep track the location of each table in the network and coordinate rule injections accordingly.

FIGURE 14: PATTERN #3: LOAD BALANCING

FIGURE 15: PATTERN #4: HEAVY HITTER OFFLOADING

In contrast to the aggregation and disaggregation pattern, the **load balancing pattern** shown in Figure 14 also requires an extra data plane component (Load Optimizer in the figure) that steers the traffic to the responsible data plane instance. This decision is based on a load-balancing key as defined in D4.2. The proxy is responsible for the key-based rule distribution and the configuration of the load optimizer data plane (LO-DP). The NF Control Plane is unaware of the actual target serving the traffic group of a load balancing key. In case of rule injection, the proxy needs to know if a rule is global or belongs to a load balancing key.

Finally, Figure 15 shows the **heavy hitter offloading pattern** that also requires a load optimizer data plane component. In this optimization scenario the heavy users or the flows with low latency requirements are served by a high-performance hardware data plane while inactive, non-heavy users are handled by a software data plane instance. The load distribution is based on the current activity of the users which may change dynamically. The proxy and the load optimizer component together solve the migration of users between the heavy hitter and non-heavy hitter instances of the data plane seamlessly. This runtime optimization is hidden from the control plane and can be done in less than 50ms as shown in Section 5.2.

5.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

The configuration files and usage of the proxy have already been described in D4.2 [4].

5.1.4 Evaluation

As described in the previous sections, the Control Plane Proxy has gone through a performance enhancement that yielded significant improvement in the message processing throughput, as vividly illustrated in Figure 16. The figure clearly demonstrates how configurations utilizing asyncio, particularly the "Asynchronous real proxy," achieve higher request rates at various sending capacities compared to their synchronous counterparts ("Real proxy"), pushing past the previous throughput ceiling of 1,500 messages per second as mentioned in D4.2.

FIGURE 16: MESSAGE PROCESSING PERFORMANCE OF A CONTROL PLANE PROXY INSTANCE

5.1.4.1 Expanded Testing and Real-World Validation

Beyond core performance, we expanded our testing methodologies to ensure the proxy's robustness and versatility across various network functionalities. We have extensively tested the proxy's capabilities using real-world P4 program NF data plane examples, including crucial network functions like SMGW (Small Gateway) and ARP/ICMP. These practical test cases go beyond basic packet processing, validating

the proxy's ability to seamlessly handle complex P4 programs and their corresponding control plane interactions, supporting the decomposition of network functionalities into smaller, modular elements as envisioned in Section 5.2 of the D4.2 report.

To facilitate more accurate and deployment-ready measurements, especially beyond the simulated BMv2 environment, we developed a dedicated measurement program in P4 itself. This allows for performance metrics to be collected directly on real P4-capable hardware, providing crucial insights into the proxy's behaviour in production-like environments and addressing the limitation of similar tools being "limited to BMv2" as noted in Section 5.2.1 of the D4.2 report.

5.1.4.2 Enhanced Resource Management and Fairness

A critical aspect we have confirmed is the proxy's fair resource handling mechanism. Our tests have shown that in multi-tenant or multi-controller environments, if one Network Function (NF) attempts to send an excessive volume of requests, the proxy intelligently manages the flow. This prevents any single NF from monopolizing data plane resources and inadvertently starving other active NFs, thereby guaranteeing stable and predictable operation for all connected control planes. This contributes significantly to the proxy's trustworthiness and reliability in managing isolated, shared resources.

In summary, the developments have markedly advanced the IML Control Plane Proxy, transforming it into a more performant, robust, and versatile component critical for realizing the full potential of the unified programmable data plane layer within the DESIRE6G project. These improvements directly addressed the limitations and future plans outlined in our D4.2 report [4], bringing us closer to a fully optimized and reliable network infrastructure.

5.1.5 Limitations and further plans

The proxy was implemented in Python using the standard gRPC library that proved to be a bottleneck limiting the achievable message rate. We have enhanced the implementation with the use of `asyncio` library and managed to reduce the overhead of the proxy. However, we think that a more efficient `grpc` implementation in C or C++ could further improve the proxy's performance. The proxy mediates between multiple NF-DP and NF-CP instances and is responsible for the isolation between them. The

current implementation can easily be extended with authentication and authorization mechanisms to ensure trustworthiness and security. This is not implemented yet, but we plan to add this feature to this component in the future. The proxy will be further developed as an open-source project on GitHub: <https://github.com/DESIRE6G/IML-CP-Proxy>

5.2 Run-time Load Optimizer

In the pursuit of a cloud-native, unified implementation of the data plane, we address the complexity of physical network deployments, which typically involve multiple instances of network functions (NFs). For efficient traffic steering among these instances, load balancers are essential. In order to unify and simplify the interaction between the control plane and the data plane while abstracting implementation details, we propose a Load Optimizer (LO) method that comprises two components: the Load Optimizer Control Plane (LO-CP) and the Load Optimizer Data Plane (LO-DP). The LO-CP functionality is also available through the IML's control plane proxy as presented in Section 5.1.2.1. LO-CP is responsible for configuring and managing the NF instances and load balancing rules between them. LO-CP can dynamically adjust the number of NF instances, perform state migration and configure the LO-DP. To effectively manage the diverse traffic demands within the unified data plane, the Load Optimizer (LO) method also targets the challenge of handling Heavy Hitter (HH) users—traffic groups that require significantly higher throughput than their Non-Heavy Hitter (non-HH) counterparts, balancing the users' load between hardware and software instances of the same NF data plane. Figure 17 overviews the different components of the proposed method.

FIGURE 17: LOAD OPTIMIZER OVERVIEW

The run-time load optimizer, its main mechanisms and the data plane and control plane algorithms have been described in D4.2 [4]. That deliverable mostly focused on the concept and the preliminary implementations. Since then, we have advanced the implementation and ported fully to Intel Tofino and conducted different performance measurements to demonstrate the method's applicability and the performance gains we can obtain.

5.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

- Current related works [11][12][13] do not fully address the challenges associated with efficiently managing heterogeneous environments of multiple instances of network functions and their deployment across diverse data plane implementations, particularly when it comes to dynamically mapping traffic flows to the appropriate NF instances. The load optimization method effectively addresses the following: Dynamic Mapping: Implementing a framework that dynamically allocates traffic to the most appropriate NF instances based on factors like real-time flow characteristics.
- State Migration: Enabling the transfer of the changing states of user's traffic (state migration) during runtime to different instances seamlessly while minimizing both state migration time and packet loss rates. It includes the migration of both static (e.g., lookup table entries) and dynamic (e.g., values stored in registers) states.

- **Unified View:** The optimization details (e.g., number of instances, type of instances, etc.) are hidden from the control plane entity of the NF.

5.2.2 Implementation

To effectively manage a substantial number of non-HH users, software-based NF data planes can be employed for efficient service delivery. However, the resource-intensive nature of HH traffic requires the deployment of hardware data planes, such as those operating on constrained platforms like Intel Tofino, with limited SRAM and TCAM capacity. The designed Load Optimizer comprises two primary components:

- **Load Optimizer Control Plane (LO-CP) component:** It is a subcomponent of the Control Plane Proxy within the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML), responsible for dynamic state migration orchestration between instances, load balancing rule administration, and seamless integration with the other functions of the control plane proxy. The main mechanisms, the key algorithms and main interactions between the data and control planes have been described in Section 5.1.2 of D4.2 [4].
- **Load Optimizer Data Plane (LO-DP):** Implemented in P4 for the v1model and TNA architecture, it provides heavy hitter offloading and load balancing. The data plane algorithms implemented by this component has been detailed in Section 5.1.2. of D4.2 [4].

In the last phase of the project, we improved the finalization step of the dynamic state migration process. In the original algorithm, the dynamic state migration was closed by the LO-CP as the state migration packet was sent back to it and after that the LO-CP changed the forwarding path for the given user in the LO-DP. This interaction between LO-CP and LO-DP introduced an approx. 8 ms overhead in the total migration time. The implemented key mechanisms with the introduced optimizations are the following:

- **Initiating the migration:** migration is triggered if a packet arrives with different heavy hitter status encoded in the DESIRE6G packet header (i.e., a HH flow becomes non-HH or vice versa). Upon detecting this migration event, the data plane sends a digest message to LO-CP, signalling the need for action. Once notified, LO-CP initiates the migration process by inserting the static rules of the migrated user (rules belonging to the same load balancing key) into appropriate

tables in the new NF instance. After that LO-CP generates a migration packet sent to the original/source NF data plane instance from which migration is required. This packet includes a field identifying the user/UE whose state is being migrated, and fields containing the dynamic states associated with that user. Note that dynamic states in P4 targets are stored in registers and their values can change from packet to packet. Upon receiving the migration packet, the source data plane populates its header fields with stored dynamic states and forwards the packet to the target data plane instance, the new instance where the user is served after migration is completed.

- **Completing the migration:** Once the source data plane instance forwards the migration packet to the target instance, it enters into forwarding state. During this state, all packets associated with the migrated user/UE ID are forwarded to the new data plane instance instead of being processed locally. Upon receiving the migration packet, the target data plane instance extracts and loads the dynamic states into its registers. To complete the migration process, it sends a notification packet back to the load optimizer. This notification serves to confirm that the migration has been successfully finalized and that subsequent packets can now be forwarded directly to the new data plane instance. The finalization of the migration occurs entirely within the data plane, as the information regarding which instance a given flow should be forwarded to is maintained in a register (indexed by the user/UE ID mentioned earlier) that can be updated directly within the data plane. This approach ensures efficiency and minimizes overhead during the migration process and does not require the involvement of the LO-CP component.
- **Load balancing of Non-HH users:** As described in D4.2 [4], the load optimizer also implements load balancing between multiple software instances. In case of up- and downscaling, the instance allocation changes, and some users may be migrated to another software instance. The instance is identified by hashing the user/UE ID to an operating instance number. To handle the issue of packet ordering, we implemented a mechanism to migrate users only at flowlet boundaries (if there is a gap in the packet stream).

5.2.3 Usage and Interfaces

In LO-DP, the configuration can be performed via BFRT and P4Runtime interfaces. The LO-CP functionality is part of the Control Plane Proxy described earlier. The proxy provides a northbound P4Runtime API for the NF-CP and connects to the NF-DP instances. Note that we also implemented the LO-CP functionality with the Tofino ASIC's standard BFRT API.

5.2.4 Evaluation

The evaluation was conducted in the same dedicated testing environment that was presented in Section 5.1.4 of D4.2, utilizing an Intel Tofino switch with four pipelines and two x86 servers (AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3970X 32-Core Processor, 3.7GHz, 128GB RAM) acting as a traffic generator and a K8S cluster running the containerized NF. Each pipeline of the Tofino switch runs different P4 programs. Two pipelines are employed: Pipe-1 for the LO-DP implementation and Pipe-2 for the NF-DP instance handling the traffic of Heavy Hitter (HH) users. In the K8S cluster, we run a single instance of the NF-DP program with the DPDK-based (Data Plane Development Kit) P4 compiler and software switch framework called T4P4S. This instance only uses a single CPU core. The role of this instance is to handle the traffic load of Non-Heavy Hitter (non-HH) users. This setup allows for a comprehensive assessment of the efficiency and performance of the proposed load balancing strategy. In the evaluation scenario, a HH user becomes a non-HH and thus its states are moved from the Tofino-based NF-DP instance to the software instance. The NF-DP we use is a simple stateful firewall implemented for both v1model and TNA. Note that the test traffic was generated by the Traffic Generator server on one of its 100Gbps ports. After the NF execution was completed, the packets were forwarded back to the Traffic Generator node on the other 100Gbps port.

For the evaluation, we generated 100 traffic flows using 64-byte UDP packets. The evaluation was structured in three phases, with the second phase focusing on three main scenarios. In each scenario, when the load balancer detects anomalies or there are dynamic changes in traffic patterns, the relevant state migration mechanisms are activated to optimize resource allocation. The three scenarios mentioned above are detailed in the following subsections.

5.2.4.1 Heavy Hitter flow overloading the software instance

In this case, the traffic of a user rapidly increases in volume, reaching heavy hitter status and pushing the overall network load above 2 million packets per second (MPPS). This surge overwhelms the containerized network function (NF), exceeding its processing capabilities. The load optimizer detects the user's transition to heavy hitter by checking the heavy hitter field in the DESIRE6G header and immediately begins the migration process. Figure 18 highlights the increase in delay during this overloaded interval. The measured delay is the time between generating the probe packet and receiving it at the TRES traffic generator. The propagation latencies between the nodes are negligible.

FIGURE 18: DELAY OF THE HEAVY-HITTER FLOW ON THE SOFTWARE INSTANCE (OVERLOAD SCENARIO)

FIGURE 19: LOSS RATIO ON THE SOFTWARE INSTANCE (OVERLOAD SCENARIO)

Due to the relatively long duration required for migrating static states, the containerized NF continuously experiences an increased load that exceeds its capacity and influences its performance. Consequently, packet loss occurs, as shown in Figure 19. Note that the control and data plane interaction in Tofino switches are the most time-consuming part of the migration process; it is more than 42ms in the example. Once static state migration is finalized, dynamic state migration proceeds much faster. By the time the control plane records the end of the migration (noting that the control plane is only involved for monitoring and not in the operational path), delays for both HH and nonHH flows have already stabilized and returned to the normal range, as indicated in Figure 18 and Figure 20.

FIGURE 20: DELAY OF THE NON-HEAVY HITTER FLOWS ON THE SOFTWARE INSTANCE (OVERLOAD SCENARIO)

After migration, the heavy hitter user is handled by the Tofino switch, which processes packets at line-rate with basically deterministic delay, leading to a dramatic reduction in delay for that flow.

5.2.4.2 Heavy Hitter migration without overloading the software instance

In this scenario, a flow similarly becomes a heavy hitter, but the total network load is constrained to 1.6 MPPS, not overloading the software instance of the NF. Figure 22 shows the increased delay values due to the higher processing demand, but no packet loss is observed. Even in the absence of overload, offloading the heavy hitter user to the Tofino switch is beneficial, as it reduces latency and preserves capacity for future high demanding users.

After detecting the HH state, the load optimizer starts the state migration, and delay values remain low for some time because of the available buffer space at the containerized NF. Once delay values reach approximately 600 microseconds, migration is finalized and the heavy hitter is moved to the Tofino switch instance, as shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22.

FIGURE 21: DELAYS OF THE HEAVY-HITTER FLOW (NON-OVERLOADING SCENARIO)

FIGURE 22: DELAYS OF THE NON-HEAVY HITTER FLOWS (NON-OVERLOADING SCENARIO)

FIGURE 23: DELAYS OF THE ONCE HEAVY HITTER FLOW (OFFLOADED-TO-NORMAL SCENARIO)

5.2.4.3 Heavy Hitter user becomes inactive

This scenario examines the reverse process, where a previously offloaded heavy hitter user decreases in volume and is reclassified as a normal user. The user's traffic is then migrated back from the Tofino switch to the containerized NF. As depicted in Figure 23, delays are initially very low (around microsecond) due to the switch's line-rate processing speed. After migration, the flow is processed by the software instance of the NF, resulting in an average delay of about 50 microseconds, reflecting the lower software-based packet processing speed. This step is performed to free Tofino switch resources for future heavy hitter users to be offloaded. More results on the load optimizer will be published in [14].

5.2.5 Limitations and further plans

As shown in the previous section, the interaction between the LO-DP and LO-CP could introduce latency during instance migration – the static state migration took more than 30ms. Note that this value may be different on future P4 targets. The method relies on the HH-flag and key (UE ID) carried by the DESIRE6G header. As this is a custom header, we plan to support other header types (e.g., IPv6 extension header, SRv6 headers, etc.) for carrying the required information (load balancing key and HH state) in the future. A potential security issue may be if an attacker falsifies these header fields in the network. We currently assume that each DESIRE6G site is a private network while communication between

DESIRE6G sites is carried out over encrypted tunnels. The dynamic state migration requires an extra protocol header to store register states. The current implementation assumes a single register and a single 64-bit long value to be transferred per NF. This limitation can easily be handled in the future but may introduce extra computational overhead in both the hardware and software NF instances. The source code of the load optimizer with some helper scripts is available on GitHub: https://github.com/kkaroly42/state_migration

5.3 P4 Data Plane Aggregator

The current P4 programmability model assumes that a P4 programmable device is owned and controlled by a single tenant. However, in typical NFV scenarios, support for multiple tenants is desirable. When each tenant may want to deploy its own P4 pipeline offering different network functions, supporting multiple co-existing tenant pipelines on a single platform is difficult because it requires pipeline merging, control plane support, and resource management of the platform. In DESIRE6G, we developed novel compiler-addons for automatic merging multiple P4-pipelines. This meta-compiler we call P4-MTAGG [9][10] combines multiple P4-pipelines while preserving individual functionality and injecting additional functionality into the aggregated pipeline for packet classification, resource management and monitoring. The meta-compiler i) merges individual parsers into a single one capable to parse packets as defined in all source pipelines, ii) combines the match-action stages from all pipelines, dealing with possible naming collisions and iii) adds additional tables and parser states to identify incoming packets based on control headers (DESIRE6G or SRv6 header) and the NF IDs provided in the configuration and apply the correct NF, collect statistics about per tenant NF packet processing rates and resource (e.g., bandwidth, memory) usage and apply rate-limiting to each NF as configured by the proxy defined in Section 5.1. We note that currently the meta-compiler supports two control header types: i) DESIRE6G header where the NF identification is based on the nextNF field, 2) SRv6 where the segment ID is used to determine the NF pipeline to be executed.

5.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Supporting multiple tenants in a single programmable target poses multiple challenges, including i) how to merge the individual tenants' NFs so that they can be deployed on the target (as the target typically has less pipelines than number of NFs of all tenants that should be deployed), ii) how to provide control plane access to individual tenants, as the merged NFs typically only expose a single control plane interface that all tenants must share and iii) how to manage the target resources between tenants, such as memory (e.g., TCAM entries, SRAM) processing power (e.g., processed packets per second) or control plane load (e.g., number of installed/updated rules per second).

Some recent works tackled similar issues. For example, μ P4 [15] proposes a novel programming language/framework based on the P4-standard that focuses on modularity and interoperability of different functions. However, support of different tenants is not provided. Our framework allows for modularity without deviating from the P4-16 standard, significantly enhancing interoperability with other projects based on the standard. Placement of NFs and its impact on performance and resource consumption have been discussed in [16]. While it assumes that a host is capable of deploying multiple NFs, the process to support this has not been solved. Supporting multiple tenants on a single platform with implications on the control interface has been discussed in [17], but is limited to fixed-function multi-tenancy. Lemur [18] allows to merge multiple NFs but does not consider multiple tenants and resource sharing policies between the different NFs.

5.3.2 Implementation

The P4-MTAGG compiler extension is based on the T4P4S [19] compiler developed by ELTE, utilizing its high-level intermediate representation module HLIR for internal P4-representation and manipulation. The compiler extension takes multiple P4 files as input and outputs a single P4 file of the aggregated pipeline as well as corresponding P4Runtime-information for use in the control plane proxy.

FIGURE 24: THE MAIN STEPS OF THE P4-MTAGG META-COMPILER

Figure 24 shows the different steps of the code aggregation process. HLR is a Python library to generate a program graph with all the object defined in the P4 code. The meta-compiler then applies different code transformations on the input HLRs that have already been detailed in Section 5.3 of D4.2. The P4-MTAGG metacompiler's implementation has not been conceptually modified.

In the last phase of the project, we extended P4-MTAGG metacompiler with optional traffic metering and shaping capabilities, enabling resource allocation between the different tenants. For example, having two different tenants with different data plane pipelines. The aggregated program runs on the same P4 target having, e.g., a 40 Gbps port. With this capability, we can define the maximum allowed data rates for each tenant, for example 30 Gbps for tenant 1 and 10 Gbps for tenant 2. The isolated access to the data plane objects and the run-time reconfiguration of the tenant meters are both ensured by the Control Plane Proxy discussed in Section 5.1.

5.3.3 Usage and Interfaces

The P4-MTAGG compiler can either be used as a command line tool or as a Python library. An orchestrator command line tool has also been developed to automate the aggregation, deployment and control plane proxy configuration processes.

5.3.4 Evaluation

The initial evaluation of the P4-MTAGG meta-compiler has already been presented in D4.2. We extended the results and present them in this section. Our evaluation focuses on identifying the performance impact of deploying multiple pipelines on the same target. The evaluation setup consists of a Barefoot WEDGE as a smart Top of Rack Switch, multiple Netronome SmartNICs and Intel 810 NICs. All data-

plane connections are made through an Arista 100G Switch. The traffic generator utilizes Mellanox ConnectX-5 cards and is based on Cisco T-Rex. All test packets are 164 bytes long. The packets carry two NF IDs belonging to two different network services (i.e., tenants). All tests are run using the Netronome SmartNIC (2x40G). Global reordering and Flowcache modules are disabled, to allow larger aggregated programs to also run on the smartNIC.

In the first scenario, we aim to systematically evaluate the effect of aggregating network functions of different complexity. To this end, we aggregate two different test network functions with different number of match-action tables. The tested NFs apply 1, 2, 3, ..., 10 match-action tables on the received packets. However, the total number of tables in all aggregated pipelines is the same (10). The test traffic mixes packets for the two tenants according to a predefined share. Therefore, at 50% packet share, all pipelines should have the same throughput. Figure 25 shows the throughput and latency for aggregated pipelines with 0-10 tables to 5-5 tables. Average throughput of the pipelines is similar, with packet rates ranging from 10.17 (0-10) to 9.00 (5-5) MPPS (million packets per second). The latency values also correlate with the number of tables applied to a specific packet, with round trip latencies ranging from 210 microseconds for 0 tables applied to 238 microseconds for 10 tables applied.

FIGURE 25: THE EFFECT OF AGGREGATION ON THE EXPERIENCED THROUGHPUT AND LATENCY VALUES

In the second scenario, we focused on quantifying the aggregation overhead. We tested the overhead by gradually introducing the new P4-constructs (parsing, tenant identification and metering) to the original pipeline and measuring the effect on throughput and latency. Figure 26 shows the overhead of additional control structures inserted into the pipeline by P4-MTAGG. Accordingly, extracting the network function id and identifying the function to be applied have the biggest effect on throughput, while the effect of parsing the additional header and applying metering for data plane resource control is negligible. Note that other targets may experience other effects. For example, on Tofino ASIC the performance is not affected by the aggregation if the aggregated pipeline fits into the available data

plane resources. The tenant classification and the meter-based traffic shaping requires two additional computational stages that needs to be considered when aggregating P4 programs.

FIGURE 26: OVERHEAD OF ADDITIONAL DATA PLANE PROCESSES NEEDED FOR THE PIPELINE AGGREGATION

5.3.5 Limitations and further plans

The current implementation of P4-MTAGG only supports the v1model and the TNA P4 architectures. New targets with different architecture models require the extension of the meta-compiler and the underlying intermediate representation (HLIR) of the T4P4S compiler. The currently available P4 hardware targets do not support the change of the P4 program without interrupting the operation, leading to more than 30 sec service outages if a new pipeline needs to be loaded in a Tofino ASIC. This may change in the future with other targets. One solution to bypass this limitation is if we use a spare instance of the same hardware device and in case of a pipeline update the spare hardware takes over the role of the old hardware instance with the new P4 program. After that the old instance becomes the spare device. This approach can eliminate the service unavailability caused by the long startup times. Investigation of this deployment option is part of our future work.

P4-MTAGG has been published in [9] and [10], and the initial code is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/FBrisch/t4p4s>

Currently, we work on an extended paper of this approach. The final version of the source code will also be published together with the paper.

6 Performance isolation for supporting deep slicing

As broadband access speeds continue to increase across both mobile and fixed networks, new and pressing challenges are emerging in the Access-Aggregation Network (AAN), which plays a critical role in delivering high-speed data services to end users. While advances in access technologies have driven impressive growth in last-mile speeds, they have inadvertently shifted bottlenecks to the AAN itself. This trend threatens to undermine the full benefits of broadband access if transmission constraints within the AAN are not addressed with effective scalability and isolation mechanisms. Performance isolation ensures that the congestion level and resources utilized by a slice do not negatively affect the performance of another [20]. Moreover, within a slice, when high-speed links are shared among thousands, or even millions, of subscribers without right performance isolation, competition for bandwidth increases, especially during peak traffic times. In such cases, the resource sharing depends largely on the number of active flows each subscriber has, and the specific congestion control mechanisms employed. This lack of control over how resources are shared among subscribers can lead to an unpredictable and often unfair distribution of bandwidth, degrading user experience and limiting the quality of service for latency-sensitive applications such as streaming, gaming, and real-time communication.

Scheduling and Active Queue Management (AQM) are critical for ensuring performance isolation, as they directly influence how resources are allocated and managed among different slices, as well as within each slice between users, since scheduling ensures appropriate and efficient allocation of network resources, while AQM manages congestion and queue performance. However, traffic management in current switches is rigid, supporting only a limited set of predefined algorithms. Thus, operators are restricted to reconfiguring algorithm parameters without the ability to modify the underlying algorithm logic. While numerous algorithms have been developed for various network scenarios, fixed packet scheduling and complementary AQM schemes struggle to adapt to the complexities of network environments, especially looking into the intricacies and hard requirements of mobile network traffic. The ability to program the data plane offers a unique opportunity for implementing flexible and customizable traffic management within and across network slices. An extensive list of programmable scheduling and AQM approaches is provided in [21].

6.1 Per user performance isolation with packet tagging

In Section 6.2 of D4.2 [4], we introduced our performance isolation method based on the Per Packet Value (PPV) framework. The PPV method relies on the core-stateless resource sharing principle, using two key elements:

- a **packet marker** which assigns values to each packet of a user (or more generally a traffic aggregate) according to a predefined resource sharing policy.
- a **scheduler and Active Queue Management (AQM)**, which uses the values carried by packets to decide whether to drop a packet or mark it with ECN Congestion Encountered (CE) flag if the buffer is getting full.

Each traffic aggregate (e.g., UE generated traffic) within a slice can be marked with PVs independently. The marker labels incoming packets with a drop precedence level known as the Packet Value (PV). This marking process is stateful because it depends on the throughput of the traffic aggregate and the specific resource-sharing policy defined by a policy function called Throughput-Value Function (TVF). Each packet marker operates independently of other markers, network topology, and current network conditions.

The scheduler is deployed at each node (e.g., routers, end-hosts) within the PPV domain, as any node can potentially become a bottleneck. During periods of congestion, these nodes prioritize packets by PV, dropping or marking packets with the smallest PVs first, rather than using traditional methods like dropping the last packet or dropping uniformly at random. The PV is encoded in the DESIRE6G header (as an extension header).

The essential part of implementing the framework is to tag packets with PVs, using a Throughput-Value Function (TVF), which is derived from a utility function. The utility function expresses the relationship between the allocated throughput and the user's satisfaction. The derivative of the utility function represents the extra value (e.g., the increase in the user's satisfaction) gained by providing an extra unit of throughput to the user.

Practically, the packet marker for each user measures the sending rate R , selects a rate x uniformly from the range $[0, R]$ when a packet arrives, and assigns a PV $p=V(x)$ to the packet where $V(\cdot)$ is the throughput-value function mapping rates to PVs. This results in a distribution of PVs for each traffic aggregate, enabling differentiated treatment in the network.

FIGURE 27: EXAMPLES FOR THROUGHPUT-VALUE FUNCTIONS (TVF) AND RESOURCE SHARING WITH THE PPV METHOD

Figure 27 illustrates how the TVFs and PVs can be used to share the bottleneck capacity between various users. In the first case, the bottleneck capacity is 10 Mbps shared between three user flows. The red, blue and green curves on the right side represent the TVFs of Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. The gray dotted line illustrates the cutoff value that results in a resource allocation 0, 6.25 and 3.75Mbps for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. This allocation is ensured by only transmitting packets with PV above the cutoff level. One can observe that Flow1 has no packet with PV above this threshold and thus it cannot even transmit a single packet. In the case of a 45Mbps bottleneck, the cutoff value is much smaller and thus all three flows have non-zero assigned throughput. The purple dotted line represents the cutoff value, leading to 10, 17.5 and 17.5Mbps throughput allocation for Flow1, Flow2 and Flow3, resp. In this case, packets below the threshold marked by the purple line are only dropped (or marked with ECN CE).

As shown in [29], the PPV concept also supports HQoS policies but at the expense of higher computational complexity in the packet marker component.

6.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

With regards to the scheduling approach, adopting traditional fairness mechanisms, such as Fair Queueing (FQ) scheduling [22], are theoretically capable of enforcing equal (or weighted) resource

distribution across users. However, these methods struggle to scale effectively as the number of subscribers grows, due to the impracticality of maintaining large number of queues, and processing flows individually. As broadband access expands to support dense urban populations and remote regions alike, a scalable solution that can isolate performance effectively at high user counts is becoming essential. Implementing weighted fairness for 1 million users is challenging due to many factors: 1) it requires significant resource constraints on network hardware, such as limited memory and processing power, which makes it difficult to track and manage per-user state at high speeds. 2) Ensuring fair queueing requires many queues or complex scheduling algorithms that do not scale well, especially as traffic demands shift dynamically and require real-time adjustments. 3) These fairness mechanisms may increase latency and computational load, which can disrupt high-throughput, low-latency applications. Solutions often involve trade-offs, like grouping users or using approximate methods, to balance scalability with practical performance. Looking into performance isolation between different network slices, authors in [23] employ a customizable AQM-driven virtual queue per slice to meet their bandwidth allocation and delay demands. Virtual queue-based traffic management schemes (e.g., AQM [25], scheduling [24], etc.,) have been widely employed for legacy switching devices. The programmable traffic management approach described in [20] has been employed for a packet-based, software-defined transport network, demonstrating the efficiency of the approach for 5G network slices. In D4.1 (Section 3.2.1 of [1]) we advocated the use of virtual queues (slice-level) and rank/value-based (UE level) methods for HQoS resource sharing policies. To this end, we designed and implemented a scalable, data plane-based packet marker method for the core-stateless resource sharing scheduler called CSAQM [26][27], specifically implemented for the Tofino ASIC. We show that the packet marker running on a single Tofino switch can mark the traffic of over one million users at line rate, indicating a substantial leap forward in scalable, fair resource allocation within the AAN. We also extended the packet marker with a simple, yet flexible policy configuration interface to support the adaptation of the HQoS policies via the IML.

6.1.2 Implementation

In D4.2 [4], we presented a new packet marking algorithm fully implemented in the data plane that can be executed by a Tofino- switch at line-rate. The method can easily be scaled up to support hundred

thousands or even 1 million users with a single Tofino switch. This scalable marker algorithm has been integrated with the D6GGateway infrastructure NF and is used in Demo 2 in WP5. The implementation details of our new marker algorithm were described in D4.2 in depth.

To support the widespread deployment of Per Packet Value method we have also created different implementations of the scheduler and the packet marker components: 1) a Linux kernel module implementation of the scheduler that can be loaded with the tc command, 2) an eBPF/XDP implementation of the packet marker implementation, 3) Tofino-based implementation of the scheduler and the scalable packet marker, and 4) a DPDK-based implementation of the HQoS packet marker algorithm (part of the code is open sourced) that was used in the DESIRE6G demo presented at EUCNC 2025. The source codes are available under the DESIRE6G GitHub organization: <https://github.com/DESIRE6G>

6.1.3 Usage and interfaces

To streamline the configuration of the Per Packet Value (PPV) framework, we introduced a simple yet flexible policy definition interface in D4.2. This interface allows users to define policies that are subsequently mapped to a throughput-value function in the Packet Marker component. The defined policies are loaded into the PolicyFunction table of the packet marking program detailed in Section 6.2.1 of D4.2. According to the requirements of the EUCNC 2025 demo and the final version of the digital twin demo, we slightly revised the configuration interface, and the rules used for converting the configuration to the throughput value function expressing the policy in PPV framework. We also extended the configuration with a more flexible per-hop latency requirement definition, allowing three modes: low latency enforcement when packets are always treated as L4S traffic resulting in <2ms queueing latency, normal latency (i.e., non-latency-sensitive) ensuring normal bounded queueing latency (<20ms) and auto latency setting when the ECN marking automatically determines if the packet requires low or normal latency. An example for the modified configuration is presented below:

policy:
id: 0
ns-id: 1
traffic-group-id: 0
latency-class: auto
segments:
- type: guaranteed
bandwidth_limit_kbps: 2000
weight: 4
- type: best_effort
bandwidth_limit_kbps: 100000
weight: 1

One can see that the latency-class has been introduced to express what is the queuing delay requirements. It could be L4S, normal and auto, as described above. The bandwidth segments play the same role as in D4.2. We only modified the attribute names to make the measure unit clear: bandwidth_limit_kbps defines the bandwidth of the given segment where the weight denotes the proportional weight of the user in the given bandwidth range.

We also extended the packet scheduler implementation with the ability to collect congestion measurements – expressed as the maximum value of the dropped or ECN tagged packets. This data is periodically reported and together with the applied policy it can be used to check if the guaranteed bandwidth requirements are met or violated, enabling IML to notify SMO if the SLAs are not met and redeployment of the network service or reallocation of the resources are needed. In our Tofino implementation, the congestion measure is calculated in every 8ms by the control plane component of the PPV traffic manager.

6.1.4 Limitations and further plans

Despite its advantages, the PPV-based QoS solutions face a few practical limitations. First, deploying it in a production network requires specialized hardware or programmable switches capable of running packet-value-based schedulers. Second, the HQoS marker algorithm introduced in [29] may incur substantial computational overhead when a traffic aggregate contains numerous subflows. As a result,

scalability and real-time feasibility could be compromised in large-scale or highly dynamic environments. Nonetheless, simpler packet tagging approaches can be deployed on programmable switches or within packet processing frameworks such as DPDK or eBPF/XDP without any scalability issues. Finally, PPV requires a field in a protocol header where the packet value is stored. In DESIRE6G, we use the custom DESIRE6G header for this purpose.

6.2 RAN inter-slice scheduler

Efficient real-time resource allocation in the RAN requires a lightweight framework that can run within the constrained computational environment of the mobile edge, ensuring timely computation and communication within each Transmission Time Interval (TTI). To achieve this, algorithms must make fast decisions using partial and noisy information about channel quality and traffic demand, without relying on complete knowledge of the current or future system state. In DESIRE6G, the programmable RAN—enhanced by edge intelligence and guided by O-RAN principles—should incorporate online learning mechanisms that adapt resource allocation continuously to meet SLAs in real time. Since SLA fulfilment can only be observed after resources are allocated, once actual user load, channel conditions, and service outcomes are known, this calls for learning-driven algorithms that work without prior traffic or channel statistics, refining allocation decisions dynamically as conditions evolve. To this end, we propose a resource allocation framework leveraging online learning techniques to dynamically adjust resource distribution under non-stationary and unpredictable conditions.

6.2.1 Novelty beyond state-of-the-art

Recent studies on online resource allocation for RAN slicing have explored various approaches to meet dynamic service demands and SLA requirements. In [45], Model Predictive Control is used to estimate minimal PRB requirements per slice, targeting app-level SLA guarantees. OranSlice [46] extends OAI with a slice-aware MAC scheduler compatible with O-RAN's E2 Service Model (E2SM) Cell Configuration and Control [59] specification. Programmable RAN architectures have further enabled dynamic control over low-level operations. For example, [47] introduces a flow-level traffic control pipeline driven by near-RT RIC policies to enforce 5G QoS across RLC layers. Similarly, [48] leverages P4-programmable data

planes to offload modulation mapping to Tofino switches for high-throughput scenarios such as massive MIMO.

Parallel to these system-level developments, learning-based methods have emerged to handle the variability and partial observability inherent in RAN environments. Reinforcement learning methods, including deep RL, have shown promise in adapting to changing environments, but typically require extensive training data and may suffer from slow convergence in real-time settings [49][51][52][53].

Online Convex Optimization (OCO) techniques have gained attention for their ability to make sequential decisions without prior statistical knowledge, enabling adaptation to unknown and time-varying conditions [53][54]. Closer to the current work, [55] addresses a resource reservation problem in a virtualized RAN market, where service providers lease resources under dynamic spot pricing and unknown user demand. The authors adopt a Follow-the-Regularized-Leader (FTRL) algorithm combined with gradient prediction to minimize regret under a concave utility model. While these approaches differ in system architecture and objectives, they collectively highlight OCO as a robust and lightweight framework that could be employed for learning-driven control in programmable RANs.

Motivated by these observations, we propose an inter-slice scheduling framework that formulates SLA-aware RAN resource allocation as an OCO problem, enabling real-time, slice-specific adaptation to unknown and time-varying demands. The approach operates at TTI granularity on the real-time RIC, adapting slice-level PRB allocations to meet SLAs under time-varying channel conditions. Unlike prior efforts that operate at coarser timescales or require explicit traffic modelling, our method assumes no prior knowledge of system dynamics and relies only on local feedback. The resulting algorithm is lightweight, requires minimal computational overhead for edge deployment, and dynamically adjusts allocations based on CQI feedback. We evaluate the framework on real channel traces, showing that it significantly reduces SLA violations.

6.2.2 Implementation

We consider a RAN environment in which multiple slices dynamically share physical resources to meet diverse and evolving QoS requirements. The infrastructure is composed of distributed edge nodes, each responsible for managing resource allocation within its coverage area. At each edge node, finite resources (PRBs, MCS, transmission power) are allocated among slices. In general, more allocated PRBs

per slice result in higher throughput and reduces packet queuing, while the MCS, determined by channel conditions, specifies how many bits can be transmitted per PRB in one TTI. The system's objective is to optimize utilization of resources while ensuring that each slice meets its SLA constraints, defined by minimum throughput and maximum latency.

We consider that resource allocation is performed over discrete TTIs, with each interval serving as a scheduling window in which allocations are adapted to real-time traffic demands. At each edge node, a scheduler processes slice resource requests, ensuring that the allocated bandwidth never exceeds available capacity. Its goal is to balance resource efficiency with SLA compliance, dynamically adjusting allocations to avoid both under-utilization and over-provisioning. In our approach, this is achieved through online learning techniques, enabling adaptive behaviour even in non-stationary conditions. Specifically, we formulate the problem of inter-slice scheduling as an online convex optimization problem, with regards to PRB allocation.

The proposed problem formulation aims to allocate PRBs over time to maximize the total SLA satisfaction across slices, where each slice's score ranges from 0 to 1 depending on throughput and/or latency targets. This score is computed using a concave, saturating activation function that normalizes performance metrics and enforces diminishing returns, rewarding near-complete compliance while heavily penalizing partial SLA satisfaction. Throughput is estimated from UE-level CQI reports mapped to spectral efficiency, which is then used to derive both slice-level bandwidth (by summing the effective rates of all UEs in the slice) and slice-level latency (by computing the average of per-UE transmission delays inversely related to throughput). The objective is to maximize the number of slices being served, by maximizing the sum of slice scores, ensuring that allocations reflect the statistical composition and channel conditions of each slice. To prevent inefficient use of resources, a penalty term is applied when a slice's allocation exceeds the amount needed to reach its SLA target, discouraging over-provisioning and freeing PRBs for other slices with tighter QoS requirements.

Formally, the problem is to allocate PRBs across slices and time slots to maximize the total SLA satisfaction. Let x_{ut} denote the fraction of PRBs allocated to user $u \in U_i$ of slice $i \in S$ at time slot t , and:

$$x_{it} = \sum_{u \in U_i} x_{ut}$$

denotes the aggregate allocation for slice i . Each slice utility $F_i(\widetilde{T}_{it}, \widetilde{L}_{it}) \in [0,1]$ is a normalized, saturating function of the slice throughput \widetilde{T}_{it} and latency \widetilde{L}_{it} , capturing SLA compliance and penalizing

over-provisioning; for a detailed design of $F_i(\cdot)$ that is compatible with the OCO framework, we refer the reader to [38]. The objective for the optimization problem is:

$$\max_{x_{ut} \geq 0} \frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in S} F_i(\widetilde{T}_{it}, \widetilde{L}_{it})$$

subject to:

- Admission control:

$$z_i \in \{0,1\}, \quad y_i \geq y_i^* z_i, \quad \forall i \in S$$

Here, z_i indicates admission of slice i and y_i denotes the slice SLA score, ranging from 0 to 1 depending on whether throughput or latency requirements are met (based on admission threshold score y_i^*), and is computed as a function of \widetilde{T}_{it} and \widetilde{L}_{it} .

- PRB allocation:

$$0 \leq x_{it} \leq z_i, \quad \forall i \in S, \forall t \in T$$

This formulation preserves the original admission-control constraint, where admitted slices must satisfy their SLA.

- PRB budget across slices, per time slot:

$$\sum_{i \in S} x_{it} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in T$$

Ensuring that allocated PRBs at any given timeslot cannot exceed the available capacity of the system.

- Slice budget distributed to UEs:

$$\sum_{u \in U_i} x_{ut} = x_{it}, \quad x_{ut} \geq 0, \quad \forall i \in S, \forall t \in T$$

Indicating that slice's PRB allocation is fully distributed among its users.

Slice throughput and latency are defined as aggregates of user-level rates as following. The achievable throughput $R_u(x_{ut})$ is obtained from a physical-layer model, e.g., a Shannon-capacity expression or a 5G CQI to SE mapping.

$$\widetilde{T}_{it} = \sum_{u \in U_i} R_u(x_{ut}), \quad \forall i \in S, \forall t \in T$$

$$\tilde{L}_{it} = \frac{1}{|U_i|} \sum_{u \in U_i} \frac{MTU}{R_u(x_{ut})}, \quad \forall i \in S, \forall t \in T$$

The problem can be addressed within an OCO framework [39], where at each time slot the controller selects an allocation x_t , observes the resulting utility function induced by instantaneous channel conditions, and updates its decision for the next round. OCO is well-suited here because it enables per-slot adaptation without requiring stationarity or full knowledge of future CQIs, while offering theoretical guarantees on regret minimization relative to the best fixed allocation in hindsight.

6.2.3 Usage and interfaces

In the O-RAN architecture, real-time controllers operate on short control loops, typically under 10 ms and in some cases as low as 1 ms, allowing direct intervention in PHY and MAC layer functions with minimal computational and signalling overhead. A benefit of RT-RIC deployment is its capability to act on freshly captured channel state information, such as SINR, CQI, and buffer occupancy, with minimal latency. By closing the control loop within real-time bounds, the RT-RIC ensures that its actions remain aligned with the instantaneous radio conditions, reducing the risk of performance loss due to outdated or misaligned control decisions.

A representative implementation is EdgeRIC[56], a Real-Time RIC (RT-RIC) that extends the standard O-RAN control hierarchy to support time-critical decision-making. Unlike the Near-RT and Non-RT RICs, the RT-RIC enables a new class of applications, known as micro-apps (μ Apps), that interface with fine-grained radio resource management functions such as scheduling, modulation and coding adaptation,

and buffer status handling. The interaction between RT-RIC components and the underlying RAN elements is illustrated in the figure below, which outlines the relevant control interfaces.

FIGURE 28: O-RAN ARCHITECTURE AND EXTENSIONS TO THE REAL-TIME AND USER-PLANE DOMAINS[58].

EdgeRIC is designed for low latency control directly at the base station. The controller operates via a real-time E2 (RT-E2) interface, which replaces the conventional ASN.1-based E2AP with a telemetry message encoding implemented using protocol buffers [57]. Its control plane is integrated directly into the gNB scheduler, allowing near-instantaneous execution of control actions. The platform supports periodic telemetry exports, including buffer occupancy, uplink SNR, and downlink CQI for each UE, and applies per-TTI PRB allocation decisions through shared memory hooks. This tight integration enables the scheduler to exploit the most recent radio measurements, ensuring that scheduling and resource management decisions are both timely and context aware. The proposed inter-slice scheduling approach is implemented as a μ App using EdgeRIC.

6.2.4 Evaluation

The performance of the inter-slice scheduling approach is evaluated using two primary metrics: (i) SLA Satisfaction Rate, measured through slice utility values that capture the per-TTI degree of compliance with each slice's SLA requirements; and (ii) PRB Utilization, defined as the proportion of total available Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) allocated across all slices in each TTI.

FIGURE 29: CQI TRACES FOR THE UES COMPOSING THE RESPECTIVE SLICES

The proposed inter-slice scheduler operates on a CQI-driven throughput model consistent with EdgeRIC’s μ App interface, with the objective of maintaining stable SLA satisfaction in the presence of temporal CQI variations. The test scenario includes two network slices: the first slice contains two moving vehicles, traveling at 10 mph and 12 mph, with an SLA-defined throughput of 1 Mbps. The second slice includes two rotating mobile UEs with throughput SLAs of 1.1 Mbps. Each UE within each slice exhibits distinct CQI dynamics, using traces from [34]. The evaluation is conducted using real CQI traces derived from heterogeneous mobility profiles, as illustrated in Figure 29.

Inter-slice allocation is managed by the proposed OCO-based scheduler, which dynamically redistributes PRBs to mitigate poor channel conditions and defines the maximum number of PRBs each slice can use. Within each slice, a proportional-fair scheduler allocates scheduling weights to the UEs. The results indicate that, despite abrupt allocation changes that occur in response to transient channel degradation as indicated in Figure 30, slice utility values remain rather stable (Figure 31), as the reward function penalizes overprovisioning triggering fast corrective actions. We can trace such a reaction in the algorithm’s response to the sudden improvement in channel conditions for UE 3 of Slice 1 (Figure 29): shortly after TTI index $15 \cdot 10^3$, the allocation to this slice is rapidly reduced (Figure 30), since the gain in spectral efficiency lowers the PRB requirement to sustain the same throughput demand. The resulting drop in the respective slice utility (Figure 31) reflects this reduced need for resources triggering a corrective action to avoid overprovisioning. Thus, we are validating the scheduler’s effectiveness in meeting SLA targets under realistic, time-varying conditions.

FIGURE 30: PRB ALLOCATION PER SLICE OVER TIME

FIGURE 31: SLICE UTILITY OVER TIME UNDER THE OCO-BASED RESOURCE ALLOCATION SCHEME

6.2.5 Limitations and further plans

We looked into a real-time, SLA-aware PRB allocation framework for programmable RANs, formulated as an Online Convex Optimization (OCO) problem and deployed at TTI granularity on the O-RAN edge. Evaluations on real CQI traces with EdgeRIC [56] demonstrate high SLA compliance. The concave utility design enforces SLA targets while avoiding over-provisioning and ensures fairness across heterogeneous slices. The OCO algorithm further learns to adapt allocations effectively under non-stationary channel conditions.

The current limitations are threefold: the focus on PRB allocation only, the assumption of instantaneous error-free feedback, and the lack of multi-cell coordination. Future work will extend the framework to

multi-resource scenarios, incorporate predictive models for proactive scheduling, and evaluate performance under realistic measurement delays and feedback errors.

6.3 Network-wide Hierarchical Resource Sharing with DSCP marking

In D4.1 and D4.2, we have introduced a traffic management approach based on the Per Packet Value (PPV) method and its implementation for Tofino ASIC. In addition to the deliverables, we have also shown in [29] that the framework is capable to enforce Hierarchical QoS (HQoS) policies. Despite its advantages, this method faces practical limitations. First, deploying it in a production network requires specialized hardware or programmable switches capable of running packet-value-based schedulers. This requirement can significantly increase both deployment costs and technical complexity. Second, the applied HQoS packet marker algorithm may incur substantial computational overhead when a traffic aggregate contains numerous subflows (i.e., in case of complex HQoS policies). As a result, scalability and real-time feasibility could be compromised in large-scale, highly dynamic and non-programmable environments. Third, a special header (e.g., the DESIRE6G header) is needed for storing the packet tag/value and traffic control is based on these values within the Desire6G network. However, packets can cross network segments where PPV method is not supported (e.g., transport network between DESIRE6G sites). For this reason, we created a new solution that can work even if the PPV-based traffic management cannot be deployed. It continuously monitors the user activities and periodically computes the resource allocation of the applied HQoS policy. The throughput allocation is then translated into three drop precedence levels encoded into the DSCP field of IP packets. The policy enforcement at each bottleneck is implemented by the standard WRED AQM method that applies different WRED profiles according to the DSCP field's value. This policy enforcement approach is supported by most commodity switches used in production networks nowadays. In addition, the proposed method aims to ensure that the required HQoS policies are met at the network level, and not at the level of each individual link.

FIGURE 32: NHQoS PACKET MARKER SETS THE DSCP FIELD OF EACH PACKET AND NETWORK NODES APPLY SIMPLE WRED AQM WITH DIFFERENT PRECONFIGURED DROP PROFILES

6.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Most existing access aggregation networks rely on commodity switches and routers, and has both wired and wireless links (e.g., microwave). The traffic management capabilities of these fixed function devices are limited to ensuring simple hierarchical resource sharing policies among few traffic classes. Per-user performance isolation is far beyond their capabilities. However, in future applications with wide range of service requirements (e.g., throughput demand, latency) the extension of hierarchical policies to the users will also be needed in addition to the handling of more traffic classes than today. Currently, the hierarchical resource sharing or hierarchical quality of service (HQoS) policy is configured on each link that is simple to implement but cannot provide network-wide optimal resource sharing as the users are not evenly distributed in the cell sites, their load is not static, and the network topology and link capacities also raise constraints to be considered.

In link-by-link HQoS (LHQoS), the quality-of-service policy is enforced independently at each link, requiring individual reconfiguration of every node and link in the network when policy adjustments are needed. This decentralized approach poses significant challenges, as it lacks global awareness of network conditions and cannot guarantee policy enforcement at the network level. The HQoS policy mandates an equal (1:1) allocation of network resources between the two operators, with uniform weight distribution across all users.

6.3.2 Implementation

The solution is to provide DSCP levels instead of PV values. Our marker solution is based on an offline algorithm that calculates the maximum capacity that can be allocated to each flow. Then, for each flow, we set the DSCP levels based on how much the flow uses relative to the allocated capacity. If it uses less, it is set to LOW, if it uses a constant multiple (c) of its capacity, e.g. 90%, it is set to MEDIUM and if it uses more than it has been allocated, it is set to HIGH. AQMs can then manage DSCP levels based on a set WRED profile. The algorithm can be read in more detail in the submitted article[28].

To address the deployment and scalability challenges of the core-stateless approach, we propose a hybrid method that does not require specialized packet scheduling and programmable switches at each potential bottleneck. The method consists of two primary components:

- **Offline Resource Allocation:** An offline process periodically recalculates the optimal throughput allocation among traffic aggregates based on the predefined HQoS policy. Specifically, a modified waterfilling algorithm is employed to approximate the ideal, network-wide behaviour of core-stateless, packet-value-based resource allocation.
- **DSCP Configuration:** The resulting throughput allocations are used to set the DSCP field in the IP header. To provide greater flexibility than strict rate-limiter-based bandwidth enforcement, three distinct drop precedence levels are encoded in the DSCP field.

Furthermore, we assume that all potential bottleneck nodes employ an active queue management (AQM) mechanism that supports multiple drop precedencies (e.g., WRED, with separate drop profiles for distinct DSCP code points). DSCP based traffic filtering and WRED enjoy wide support among commodity switches. Although DSCP tagging may involve non-traditional data plane operations, it remains straightforward to implement using programmable data plane technologies (e.g., P4, NPL, DPDK, eBPF/XDP).

The second component sets each packet's drop precedence field (i.e., DSCP) according to the rate allocation determined by the proposed offline method. The method executes the offline resource allocation method as an independent process that periodically read flow rates from the data plane and it estimates the flow demands. The allocated throughputs are then updated in the data plane (e.g., storing them in a match-action table (SRAM) or in registers (SRAM)). When a packet arrives the data

plane process first update the data rate ($R(u)$) of u and it takes a random number r between 0 and the rate of the u user ($R(u)$). After that it reads the allocated throughput of the user ($A(u)$) from a data plane object. When the r is higher than the $A(u)$ then it sets the drop precedence (e.g., DSCP) to level HIGH. When the r is between $A(u)$ and $c * A(u)$ where $0 < c < 1$ is constant, the DSCP level is set to MEDIUM. In other cases the DSCP level is LOW. In our example, c was set to 0.9. Note c is a configuration parameter of the method.

For different DSCP values, the networking node applies distinct RED profiles (Figure 33) to determine the drop or ECN marking probability. This probability is used by the RED early drop/ECN-marking mechanism. All traffic destined for the same egress port shares a single egress buffer/queue within the node's traffic management engine, which simplifies queue management. The AQM is calibrated so that packets deemed less important (shown by the green curve in Figure 33) are dropped or ECN-marked first, followed by those with medium, then low drop precedence. These three RED profiles enable the system to respond to sudden changes in network congestion before the offline algorithm recalculates the allocation. For instance, if traffic intensity spikes due to a new flow, each flow will experience packet drops proportional to how much its throughput exceeds the ideal allocation. Flows that exceed their ideal share experience more packet drops than those operating within or below their allotted rates.

FIGURE 33: WRED PROFILES

6.3.3 Evaluation

We show an example with the algorithm. We used a simple topology, where there are two links (AB, AC) with different capacities (1Gbps, 2Gbps). This topology is used by two mobile network operators (OP1, OP2). OP1 has one user on the AB link and three users on the AC link. OP2 has nine users on the AB link and three on the AC link. The offline algorithm calculates the demand for the users. Figure 34 shows the results of the algorithm. On Figure 35, we can see the result with PPV marking and on Figure 36 we can see the result of the DSCP marking. The result is similar. The overshoot is higher with PPV than with DSCP, because the flows are sent at a constant rate and the PPV uses values from a higher PV range randomly. In this case, we used the DCTCP congestion control algorithm.

FIGURE 34: THE RESULT OF THE OFFLINE ALGORITHM
 FLOW NUMBER ARE 1 (A-B-OP1) - 9 (A-B-OP2) - 3 (A-C-OP1) - 3 (A-C-OP2)
 THE CAPACITY OF THE AB IS 1GBPS AND AC IS 2GBPS

FIGURE 35: NHQOS WITH PPV MARKING

FLOW NUMBER ARE 1 (A-B-OP1) - 9 (A-B-OP2) - 3 (A-C-OP1) - 3 (A-C-OP2) WITH DCTCP

FIGURE 36: NHQOS WITH DSCP MARKING

FLOW NUMBER ARE 1 (A-B-OP1) - 9 (A-B-OP2) - 3 (A-C-OP1) - 3 (A-C-OP2) WITH DCTCP

The algorithm can work with multiple layers, such as operators, slices and users. Figure 37 shows an example hierarchy representation on the same topology. We can see the infrastructure is used by two operators (OP1, OP2) with 1:1 share. Both operator has a two slice (slice1, slice2) with 3:1 share, which the aggregate throughput of Slice1 is three times as much as Slice2. On the third layer, there are the users with fair share to each other.

FIGURE 37: 3-LAYER HIERARCHY EXAMPLE

The simulation ran 10 seconds. Figure 38 shows the aggregate throughput of the two operators. The topology has 1Gbps and 2Gbps links, so the aggregate capacity is 3Gbps. We can show on the figure that it is not fair, because OP2 has a higher rate, but it comes from the user distribution. OP1 on Slice2 does not use the A-C link, which is the 2Gbps, and this is the reason for the lower rate, but the two throughputs are close to each other, so this is fair.

FIGURE 38: THROUGHPUT ON OPERATOR LEVEL

Figure 39 and Figure 40 show the aggregate throughput of the slices of the OP1. Both case the share is 3:1. We can see in Figure 39 that share is not what is expected, but here is the same situation like on operator level. The Slice2 (op1-s2) does not use the A-C link, and that capacity can use the Slice1 (op1-s1). On Figure 40 we can see that OP2 uses all the links, and the share between the two slices is close to the expected 3:1 share.

FIGURE 39: AGGREGATE THROUGHPUT OF THE SLICES OF OP1

FIGURE 40: AGGREGATE THROUGHPUT OF THE SLICES OF OP2

Finally, let's see the user level. We present only the users of the OP2 where every link is used by two users. Figure 41 shows Slice1, and we can see the users on two link. Because the two links have different capacity, the users do not fair each other in the slice, but they fair on the two links. We can see similar results on Slice2 (Figure 42). This slice has lower demand because of the share on the Slice level. We can show that NHQoS can operate at multiple levels and share resources fairly.

FIGURE 41: THROUGHPUT OF THE USERS ON SLICE1 OF OP2

FIGURE 42: THROUGHPUT OF THE USERS ON SLICE2 OF OP2

6.3.4 Limitations and further plans

In congested scenarios, the proposed method relies on timely and accurate in-network measurements to detect and adapt to changing traffic demands—functionality not typically supported by commodity switches. Additionally, implementing in-network DSCP tagging demands a nontraditional networking element, such as a programmable data plane. However, these advanced nodes are required only at the entry points of the network domain. As the rate allocation is centralized, synchronization across all entry points is necessary. It is feasible in current AANs but can pose challenges if the diameter of the network is high and has many entry points. Although we expect synchronization latency to be smaller than the offline allocation algorithm's execution time in most networks, larger networks may be split into smaller domains that each runs a local instance of the offline allocation algorithm to further reduce latency.

Furthermore, the offline throughput allocation process introduces some delay, slowing the system's response to sudden traffic spikes and delaying its convergence to an optimal state. Nevertheless, if the allocation granularity is limited to total user traffic rather than individual flows, this delay has a reduced overall impact.

The paper on this new method is currently under submission [28]. The code will be published as soon as the paper is accepted.

7 Components in the pervasive monitoring framework

The DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring framework is responsible for the activation, the observation at runtime, the collection of network and joint application/network metadata and, for service assurance mechanisms based on programmable data plane, the countermeasures to assure SLA figures. The upfront of this framework is represented by the MAS, receiving and processing aggregated telemetry data through its agent and data plane collectors.

In this section, we report the development and the evaluation of the pervasive monitoring framework components and modules. In particular, we report the telemetry agent at the MAS, the final development and evaluation of monitoring P4 network functions (i.e., extended UE-INT, in-band control NF, telemetry collectors), telemetry exposure at the RAN (i.e., Accelleran nRT RIC, the software performance monitoring for containerized network/app functions, and the cloud monitoring manager. Each component is described in terms of novelty beyond the state of the art, implementation description, interface for interconnecting to other components, performance evaluation and limitations.

7.1 MAS Telemetry agent

The distributed system comprises several interconnected software components. Among them is the MAS telemetry agent, which forms part of the distributed telemetry architecture. This agent includes a telemetry collector that periodically receives telemetry data from the P4 collector, as well as a per-flow telemetry processor. Together, these components are responsible for computing the necessary measurements and statistics that characterize the current Quality of Service (QoS) of the traffic flow based on the received In-band Network Telemetry (INT) data. An additional telemetry adaptor has been developed to support the collection of metrics generated by the RAN segment. This telemetry adaptor relies on an Apache Kafka bus exposed by the RIC where the telemetry is pushed on different topics that can be consumed depending on the use case.

7.1.1 Implementation

The final implementation has been described in D4.2. This paragraph summarizes the addition of a new telemetry adaptor to support RAN metrics.

The implementation of the MAS agents encompasses the development of several essential components, as illustrated in Figure 43. At the core of this architecture are telemetry adaptors, which are responsible for collecting measurements from external systems—such as RIC (RAN Intelligent Controller) platforms and P4 switches—and converting the collected data into a format compatible with the agent’s internal data structure. These adaptors ensure seamless integration between heterogeneous data sources and the MAS internal processing pipeline. A dedicated telemetry collector processes the incoming measurement data and systematically segregates it based on individual traffic flows. This organized data is then passed to the flow telemetry processor, which performs aggregation and analysis of the measurements. The processor is also tasked with generating periodic telemetry reports, which are distributed to other MAS agents as part of the system’s collaborative intelligence framework. An intelligent agent module is incorporated to host the core decision-making logic and autonomous functions of the MAS. This module enables real-time analysis and response capabilities, supporting the broader goals of distributed intelligence within the DESIRE6G architecture.

FIGURE 43: AGENT ARCHITECTURE

7.1.2 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The MAS telemetry is a key part of DESIRE6G’s distributed intelligence system that enables autonomous network operations with near-real-time response times. Unlike traditional network management that takes minutes or hours to make decisions, this system requires new control plane technologies

(advanced algorithms, machine learning, distributed coordination) and data plane capabilities (high-speed processing, low-latency communication, adaptive routing) to process real-time data and automatically respond to network changes before they affect service quality, supporting the demanding requirements of 6G networks.

7.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

The interfaces of the MAS telemetry agent are based on RESTful APIs. The first type is traffic telemetry, which includes the flow identifier and a list of metrics along with their corresponding measured values over a specified time. The second type is end-to-end telemetry, which also includes the flow identifier and a list of aggregated metrics—specifically delay, jitter, and load—measured over the same period and disaggregated by route. The final type comprises metrics collected by the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). These may include various indicators such as signal quality for a selected cell, uplink/downlink (UL/DL) throughput for a specific User Equipment (UE), and average downlink delay within the gNB-DU for a given Distributed Unit (DU), among others. Here is the description of the implemented endpoints for the telemetry agent:

- **Traffic Telemetry API**
 - o Endpoint: /traffic
 - o Returns traffic flow measurements containing:
 - Flow identifier: Unique identifier for the network flow
 - Metrics list: Bandwidth utilization, packet count, byte count, and throughput measurements

- **End-to-End Telemetry API**
 - o Endpoint: /collector
 - o Provides aggregated performance metrics across complete network paths with:
 - Flow identifier: Unique identifier for the network flow
 - Route-specific metrics: Delay and jitter

- **RIC Telemetry API**

- o Endpoint: /ric
- o Exposes metrics collected by the RAN Intelligent Controller including:
 - Flow identifier: Unique identifier for the network flow

Radio access network metrics such as signal strength, interference levels, cell capacity, and user equipment performance indicators

By correlating these metrics with the UE associated with the monitored service, it becomes possible to take corrective actions when end-to-end (E2E) delay requirements are not satisfied. The comprehensive set of metrics provided by the RIC (described in 7.5.2.2 and 7.5.2.3) and P4 Collector enables full visibility and control over the E2E service, allowing targeted interventions in the affected domain whenever performance requirements are violated.

7.1.4 Evaluation

A further evaluation will be provided in WP5 D5.3. The preliminary results reported in D4.2 include the evaluation of the time spent by the DRL-based algorithm and the delay added by the pub/sub message exchange in a dynamic flow routing scenario. They are summarized on the following table:

TABLE 8: MAS TELEMETRY AGENT EVALUATION

Component	Mean Time (ms)	Max Time (ms)	Description
DRL-based algorithm	20	-	Time required to evaluate the 115 eep reinforcement learning algorithm
Redis DB (pub/sub message delay)	1.5	-	Delay added to every message exchanged through the Redis database
Total decision-making time	26	29	Includes delays from both Redis DB and DRL-based algorithm

7.1.5 Limitations and further plans

Existing telemetry adaptors and processors are currently limited to P4 collector and RIC measurements. Expanding the system's capability requires developing additional adaptors and processors to integrate with various other telemetry data sources across the network infrastructure. The algorithms are based

on DRL techniques while other algorithms and techniques can be explored depending on the complexity of the targeted scenario.

7.2 Telemetry collector and in-network control

INT provides real-time and granular visibility into network behaviour by embedding metadata directly into packet headers. This mechanism enables efficient in-network measurements without relying on the control plane, allowing faster response and reduced overhead. While the rapid collection of metadata is essential, it alone is not sufficient to trigger immediate local-loop interventions during Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations. This becomes particularly critical for latency-sensitive applications, where exceeding an end-to-end latency threshold—often caused by network congestion—can severely impact performance.

To address this challenge, a novel approach called **in-network control (INC) of traffic flows** is introduced. This solution leverages an extended INT framework alongside a new **Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC)**, enabling in-network detection of network state changes through the collection of distributed metadata. Importantly, it also supports real-time decision-making directly at the data plane, paving the way for fast autonomous and adaptive traffic management within the data plane.

7.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Driven by the need for faster feedback loops, we introduce a novel approach focused on in-network control of traffic flows using extended INT and a novel Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC). Our solution enhances network responsiveness by enabling both collection of distributed metadata and decision-making directly within the data plane[75][76].

7.2.2 Implementation

To reduce the closed-loop delay, while enabling the network to react quickly to micro congestions, we introduce a new telemetry and routing scheme. The concept works by assigning labels to the packets crossing the INT domain.

Such labels have a global significance over the managed domain and serve in identifying routes and flows. We also introduce the Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC), shown in Figure 44(b). This advanced collector, besides receiving INT Reports and storing latency statistics, implements the logic of checking end-to-end SLA violation for a given number of packets belonging to a flow or a set of flows.

FIGURE 44: CLOSED-LOOP LATENCY ASSURANCE STEPS AND DELAYS: STANDARD INT (A), PROPOSED DPAC (B).

Then, it sends a novel INT control message, called In-Network Control (INC), to perform specific forwarding/priority actions in one or more involved nodes of the considered flow. All the closed-loop steps are fully embedded in the data plane space. In our implementation, the INC message is sent to the ingress node of the identified path to enforce the desired match/action rule on the considered flow. For example, in the case of f_2 congestion at node N_3 , the INC message is generated towards the INT source node (i.e., N_2) to steer some of the traffic -identified by its label- on a backup path, e.g., the N_1 - N_6 optical bypass or the N_2 - N_4 - N_6 alternative route. The INC extra header fields, all 2-bytes encoded, are the target node-id, the label identifying the flow and the backup port indication where to steer the flow. As shown in Figure 44(b), the closed-loop reaction time includes the INT processing (flowchart shown in Figure 45), the INT Reports, the processing at the DPAC and the backward INC message forwarding. The DPAC flowchart is shown in Figure 46 and includes the latency violation check computed from the Report, the backup port assignment and the INC message creation. Considering that the DPAC is entirely programmed in the data plane, the closed-loop delay is expected to be reduced, mainly

depending on the INT congestion contribution. Thus, recovery takes place when congestion is still occurring, impacting on burst of few milliseconds duration. Anyway, the DPAC benefits impacts longer congestions as well, reducing the recovery time and SLA violation duration.

FIGURE 45: PROCESSING OF NODES ALONG THE PATH.

FIGURE 46: DPAC PROCESSING

7.2.3 Usage and Interfaces

Telemetry data is embedded into the packet, exploiting INT headers, with the adoption of the In-Network Control to automatically reroute the traffic.

7.2.4 Evaluation

The DPAC solution has been evaluated experimentally on a packet-optical network testbed, composed of 5 P4 switches running the P4 NIKSS software switch [6], based on the eBPF backend technology, and

a pair of Ericsson SPO PM-QPSK coherent cards at 100Gb/s, acting as optical bypass link (see Figure 44). The DPAC collector P4 code is compiled and deployed into a commercially available Tofino P4 switch (programmable ASIC with 6.5Tb/s backplane throughput) equipped with 100Gb/s optical Ethernet interfaces. To compare DPAC results, a control plane distributed agent [30] and a custom SDN/P4 controller [31] have been included in the testbed.

FIGURE 47: THROUGHPUT VS LATENCY.

Figure 48 shows the resources occupancy of the DPAC pipelines deployed in the ASIC, with focus on the increase in memory (SRAM) as a percentage compared to a simple IP forwarding application and amounts to around 10% per extra configured backup path, this extra memory is used for deploying tables and stateful objects. Also, it shows the increase in Packet Header Vector (PHV) resource usage which varies from around 2% for a single backup path to 3% for three backup paths. In the Tofino architecture, a PHV is the data structure storing packet header fields and metadata, enabling packet processing and decision-making (e.g., forwarding, dropping, modifying) as each packet moves through the P4 pipeline.

To measure the scalability of the system as a function of the route length, Figure 49 reports the overhead in terms of total increase in bytes and as a percentage, assuming a packet length of 1500 bytes, this increase is linear, as the number of bytes inserted at each node along the path is the same, except for the ingress node which adds in addition to its latency data, a label and saves the ether-type field of the Ethernet header.

FIGURE 48: RESOURCE USAGE.

Figure 47 shows a performance comparison of the DPAC against the standard scenario employing the INT collector, the Control Agent and the SDN controller in terms of end-to-end latency, experienced by the traffic, and the traffic throughput. Results show a reaction time to SLA violations in the order of tens of microseconds, compared to a measured reaction time by the software controller in the order of tens of milliseconds.

FIGURE 49: INT OVERHEAD.

7.2.5 Limitations and further plan

This component has reached the top stage of the development, considering both software and Tofino targets. No further development is envisaged.

7.3 Heavy Hitter detection

Heavy hitters are high-volume traffic flows and heavy hitter detection (HHD) algorithms aim to identify these “heavy hitters” efficiently, often using limited memory and processing power at line rate. HHD is crucial for network management (e.g., preventing bottlenecks), security (e.g., detecting DDoS attacks), load balancing (optimizing network resource allocation) etc.

7.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Heavy hitters are network flows that generate a disproportionately large share of traffic [62]. Although they typically represent less than 10% of all flows, they carry most of the total traffic volume [62]. Detecting these flows is a critical task in network monitoring, supporting applications such as load balancing, anomaly detection, and quality of service assurance [64]. As a result, heavy hitter detection is a well-studied topic in the literature.

Existing heavy flow detection methods are commonly implemented on the control plane of a software define network [65]. Thereby, having the overhead and additional delay in decision making due to frequent communication between the control and data planes. In-network computing has been leveraged to diminish this overhead. The studies [66][67][68] are similar in implementing counting the packets per flow in the data plane to estimate flow size. For the analysis of the counted values, a machine learning approach has been utilized in [66], while a threshold-based decision has been suggested in [67]. Zhang et al. [66] present a heavy-flow detection scheme for programmable data planes that trains a decision tree offline on the controller and compiles it to switch resources for online inference, achieving up to 98% accuracy and 9.4 Gbps throughput on Barefoot Tofino hardware. Harrison et al. [68] propose network-wide heavy-flow detection system where PISA switches count packets per key and report threshold excesses to a coordinator that aggregates statistics, updates thresholds, and identifies heavy flows, achieving up to 70% bandwidth savings. Sivaraman et al. [67] propose a programmable switch algorithm that maintains flow counters in a fixed-size table, replacing the entry with the smallest count when full, to detect heavy flows with 95% accuracy using under 80 KB of memory.

In the context of DESIRE6G the HH detection approach moves complex flow monitoring logic from the network switches to the P4-programmable DPAC. Instead of burdening individual switches with maintaining per-flow state under strict hardware constraints, INT sink nodes forward lightweight packet metadata (flow identifiers and packet lengths) to the collector, where HHs are identified.

7.3.2 Implementation

Heavy hitter detection algorithms currently face several challenges. Existing software solutions for HHD struggle to keep up with the high packet processing rates of modern networks, while data plane-based approaches are constrained by the strict requirements of line-rate processing. In addition, memory limitations in programmable switches restrict the scale and accuracy of in-network detection, and frequent updates or complex logic can exceed hardware pipeline constraints. Network-wide detection introduces coordination overhead and communication costs between devices, while real-time detection increases computational complexity.

We propose a HHD scheme at the DPAC to alleviate processing burden on the individual network switches. Instead of requiring each switch to maintain complex flow state under strict hardware constraints, the related metadata is merely forwarded to the collector that performs more sophisticated heavy hitter detection. We adopt a sliding window approach for HH detection due to its high responsiveness and capability to capture short traffic bursts effectively [69]. Upon receiving a packet carrying a HH header (see Figure 50) - a 32-bit field storing the length of the packet - the accompanying FLOWINFO header is hashed to generate a flow identifier. These headers are embedded into cloned packets towards the DPAC at the INT sink. This flow identifier is then used to retrieve the current entry for the flow from a dedicated register that maintains sliding window state for each flow

```
1 header FLOWINFO {
2   bit<32> src_ip;
3   bit<32> dst_ip;
4   bit<16> src_port;
5   bit<16> dst_port;
6   bit<8>  protocol;
7 }
8
9 header HH {
0   bit<32> packet_length;
1 }
```

FIGURE 50: HEAVY HITTER HEADERS

Each sliding window entry stores (i) a timestamp marking the window's start time and (ii) a bandwidth counter recording the cumulative packet size (in bytes) for the corresponding flow. Upon packet arrival, the ingress global timestamp from switch metadata and the packet length from the HH telemetry header are used to update the entry. If the entry is uninitialized, it is created and initialized with these values. If active, the elapsed time since initialization is compared to a predefined interval; if the interval has not expired, the bandwidth counter is updated and checked against the HH threshold, defined as

the minimum byte volume required within a window for classification as a HH. Exceeding the threshold triggers the insertion of a HH header into the outgoing control packet, after which the entry is cleared. If the window expires without reaching the threshold, the entry is reset.

7.3.3 Usage and Interfaces

The proposed HHD functionality is designed to operate as part of the DESIRE6G pervasive monitoring framework. It is integrated to the INT pipeline at the INT sink node and the DPAC-based collector.

Data ingestion: Packets that have completed their INT path are cloned at the sink node. Each cloned packet is augmented with a FLOWINFO header (containing hashed flow identifiers) and a HH header (carrying the packet length). These packets are forwarded to the DPAC, which performs centralized sliding-window heavy hitter detection.

Detection output: When a flow is classified as a HH, the DPAC generates an in-network control packet containing the heavy hitter header and associated metadata (flow identifier, timestamp, byte count). This packet could be optionally sent to the telemetry server, where detection events are recorded, visualized, and, if necessary, trigger automated responses (e.g., rerouting, rate limiting). The output of the HH detector can feed into other DESIRE6G modules, such as the IML for adaptive load balancing.

Configuration interface: Operators can configure the HHD parameters via the control plane of the DPAC. Configurable parameters include the (i) sliding window interval (ii) HH byte threshold per window (iii) hashing parameters for flow ID generation (iv) INT sink nodes participating in metadata export.

7.3.4 Evaluation

Before performance evaluation, the HHD implementation was functionally validated to ensure correct operation of the sliding-window mechanism, threshold detection logic, and integration with the INT telemetry framework. The validation was carried out in the BMv2 and Mininet emulated environment, with a single INT-enabled BMv2 switch acting as the sink node and a BMv2 switch emulating the DPAC-based collector [70]. Traffic was generated using iPerf to create controlled flow patterns, including:

1. **Below-threshold flows** – short-lived or low-bandwidth flows designed to remain under the configured 10 Mb sliding-window threshold.
2. **Above-threshold flows** – high-volume flows exceeding the threshold within the sliding window.
3. **Mixed traffic scenarios** – concurrent low- and high-rate flows to test simultaneous detection.

The validation confirmed that below-threshold flows triggered no heavy hitter reports while above-threshold flows consistently generated correct notifications containing the expected flow identifiers and byte volumes. The sliding window reset correctly after expiration, clearing stale entries and enabling new flow detection. Integration with INT was verified: cloned packets carried the FLOWINFO and HH headers, which were correctly parsed by the collector, and output matched ground-truth measurements from packet captures. Figure 51 shows a Wireshark capture of traffic sent from the sink node to the DPAC. Each packet corresponds to a report in this capture and is a cloned packet from the sink that contains a combination of INT application headers (HHD along with DLINT and queue size information as described in [4]). Additional information on the headers and the functional validation of the approach is provided in [70] [71].

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
17	2015.592359	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	48	Ethernet II
18	2015.593930	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	33	Ethernet II
19	2015.599283	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	50	Ethernet II
20	2015.600409	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	50	Ethernet II
21	2015.602147	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	33	Ethernet II
22	2015.602466	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	33	Ethernet II
23	2015.608185	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	50	Ethernet II
24	2015.608966	08:00:00:00:02:04	08:00:00:00:02:05	0x0000	48	Ethernet II

- Framework Header ●
- Flow-info Header ●
- DLINT Header ●
- HH Header ●
- CC Header ●

▶ Frame 20: 50 bytes on wire (400 bits), 50 bytes captured (400 bits)
 ▶ Ethernet II, Src: 08:00:00:00:02:04 (08:00:00:00:02:04), Dst: 08:00:00:00:02:05
 ▶ Data (36 bytes)

```

0000  08 00 00 00 02 05 08 00  00 00 02 04 00 00 [0f 03]  .....
0010  [0a 00 01 01 0a 00 01 02  a5 bc 14 51 06] [00 02] [00  .....Q.....
0020  00 00 75] [00 01 00 00 00  00 02 00 00 00 00 04 00  ..u.....
0030  00 00] ..
  
```

FIGURE 51: A TELEMETRY REPORT FORWARDED FROM THE INT SINK TO THE DPAC

Processing performance measurements indicated an average per-packet processing delay at the collector for HHD at a roughly an 18% increase compared to DLINT [70]. The additional delay is due to maintaining per-flow state and performing threshold checks but remains within acceptable bounds for real-time operation, as DPAC is not in line with user traffic and detection remains at nsec level [71].

7.3.5 Limitations and further plans

This work was evaluated in a BMv2 and Mininet environment, which, while functionally accurate, does not fully capture the timing, memory, and pipeline constraints of production-grade programmable targets. The current implementation also relies on a single collector and uses statically configured thresholds and window sizes, which may limit scalability and adaptability under dynamic traffic

conditions. Furthermore, the use of hash-based flow identifiers introduces a potential risk of collisions in high-flow-density scenarios, and the reporting mechanism does not adapt to real-time network state. Future work will focus on porting the scheme to hardware for line-rate validation, developing a scalable multi-collector architecture, and introducing adaptive threshold and window mechanisms. Additional efforts will explore closed-loop response fully integrated with the IML.

7.4 P4 In-band Network Telemetry on UE

In DESIRE6G, the UE has been equipped with a software based P4 switch. This switch is responsible for the support of mobility and programmability, including the first mapping of the UE to a service and the provisioning of relevant monitoring information. Two main implementations have been proposed for this purpose: the first one relies on a L4 (i.e., UDP transport) implementation, while the second has been designed to work with the DESIRE6G header at layer 2.5.

Regarding monitoring information, the two implementations support the transmission of the following information:

- Ensuring forwarding of traffic through the network exploiting radio interface(s).
- Implementing the INT solution by adding additional metadata at the packet level of the data flow.
- Managing geo-localization and radio channel information through GPS receiver and radio modules.

The software P4 switch supports Ethernet-based interfaces (i.e., pure Ethernet, virtual Ethernet). Considering the radio interface towards the 6G RAN, where non-Ethernet are typically adopted the VXLAN overlay mechanism is used to overcome this limitation.

The packets of the flows traversing the switch, according to the service identifier, are received from an input interface and are processed, being augmented with the ad-hoc defined INT header. It includes, hop transmission information (based on input and output timestamp values and additional INT metadata (transmission, application or service specific) read from the local registers.

7.4.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The overall INT structure has been reconsidered, by moving the INT header from UDP (e.g., L4) to the L2.5 layer (after the DESIRE6G header). The In-Band Network Telemetry (INT) has been extended to support Heterogeneous metadata on UE node. The same pipelines are also adopted in other P4 switches of the chain, maintaining the same parsing strategy of the packets.

7.4.2 Implementation

7.4.2.1 L4 implementation

Extending the pervasive monitoring functionalities at the UE enables the operation even when network conditions change rapidly. A UE needs to be monitored periodically to ensure their functioning, detect relevant problems and apply network optimization.

Today, different types of network monitoring exist, including traffic probing and network equipment polling. Both approaches yield additional traffic that needs to travel over the network and are prone to performance issues.

In-Band Network Telemetry (INT) is an example of passive monitoring where monitoring information is directly appended to the data packets by each node along the path, instead of being sent in dedicated packets and without requiring intervention by the control plane.

The network state is obtained at the precise moment the real user traffic passes through, reflecting the instantaneous network performance and the exact treatment that an application packet undergoes. INT provides real-time insights, facilitating proactive issue detection and enabling the identification and addressing of potential problems before they escalate.

FIGURE 52: INT PACKET STRUCTURE

A dedicated In-band Telemetry (INT), leveraging the standard design of INT over UDP outlined is developed and implemented. Figure 52 shows the telemetry structure:

1. Shim header: A 4-byte header that indicates the presence of telemetry data. It contains information about the type of INT header following it and the total length of INT header and metadata stack encapsulated between it and UDP payload. The structure of this header is demonstrated in Figure 53.
2. INT header: An 8-byte header that follows the shim header and contains information about the stack of metadata that follows it, such as the length of metadata to be inserted at each node and the remaining number of nodes allowed to add their metadata to the packet. The fields of this header are also clarified in Figure 53.
3. Metadata stack: Following the INT header, it consists of a stack of metadata headers. Each header is inserted by an INT node along the monitored path and contains standard metadata, such as ingress timestamp, egress timestamp, and hop latency.

Our contribution lies in extending the standard in-band telemetry structure not only to monitor standard metadata but also to customize the monitoring operation by tracking new key parameters, which is crucial for optimizing end-to-end network performance, including the UE. These new parameters are the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) of radio link, the geolocation information (GPS longitude, latitude and altitude) and the CPU load. The designed INT can be activated for specific data flows and its structure is shown in Figure 52.

Every node has the flexibility to serve as a source node, transit node or destination node. Furthermore, a single node can perform multiple roles at the same time: it can act as both a source and transit node or as both a destination and transit node for different flows.

FIGURE 53: INT HEADER FORMAT

INT source node is the first node in the packet’s path of the INT domain. This node inserts a 12-byte structure (i.e., standard shim and INT header) after the UDP header. Subsequently, the source node acts as a transit node, appending 40 bytes of its metadata information into a metadata header known as ‘Switch Metadata Header’. The information in this header includes both the standard metadata and the new information specifically tailored for UAV network, as illustrated in Figure 53. The standard information encompasses: 1. Switch ID. 2. Ingress timestamp. 3. Egress timestamp. 4. Hop latency (the difference between egress and ingress timestamp). 5. Flow ID. The new information includes: 1. CPU load. 2. Longitude. 3. Latitude. 4. Altitude. 5. The RSSI of the incoming radio interface.

At the next INT transit node, 40 bytes of information are appended to a metadata header called ‘Second Switch Metadata Header’. All these metadata headers have the same structure as the Switch Metadata Header illustrated in. This process is repeated for each subsequent INT transit node along the monitored path. Eventually, at the sink node, the received packet is duplicated using the P4 clone function. The payload is removed from the cloned packet and the sink node sends it, along with its own metadata information, as a final report to the collector.

in parallel, the sink node removes all the INT information from the original packet and forwards it to the receiver. Figure 54 demonstrates the P4 pipeline architecture.

FIGURE 54: P4 INT PIPELINE ARCHITECTURE

The considered P4 implementation is based on the V1 architectural model specified in the reference P4 software switch, the Behavioral Model version 2 (BMv2).

The model includes several stages:

1. The parser: It is represented by a finite state machine, where the states are responsible for extracting data from the individual header struct into runtime variables. Transitions within the state machine occur conditionally, depending on the value of a parsed header field.
2. Ingress and egress control blocks: each block consists of several match-action tables that match the packet based on different header fields and determine the appropriate actions to take when a match is detected. It also defines a control function that decides the order in which the tables should be executed. The ingress stage is utilized to perform forwarding, while the egress pipeline is utilized to perform further operations after determining the output port for forwarding.
3. The deparser: Its role involves converting the modified headers back into a serialized format within the packet, preparing it for transmission to the subsequent switch in the network. State

transitions are determined by the examination of a specific header field, indicating the presence of the subsequent protocol.

The parser subsequently processes UDP, Shim, and INT headers. Ultimately, it extracts the header from the packet, characterized by a variable length with a predefined maximum size. This header represents a stack of metadata headers, including information appended by every transit node. In order to parse the appropriate variable length of this header at each node, the parsing process has been achieved based on the length field in the Shim header. This field encompasses the total length of Shim header, INT header and the stack of metadata headers (Sw mheader) in 4-byte words. By subtracting the length of the Shim header (1 word) and the length of the INT header (2 words) from the value of this field and converting the result from words to bits, the correct length for parsing this header is determined.

After parsing, packets proceed through the ingress pipeline, depicted in Figure 54, where three flow tables are executed: Forwarding, Activate Source and Activate sink. The Forwarding table determines the output port based on Layer 2 (L2) MAC addresses, essentially implementing switch behaviour. The Activate Source table initiates the INT process by invoking the associated action. This action involves inserting both Shim and INT headers into INT packets received at a designated port with a specific UDP port.

Additionally, it updates the length of IP and UDP headers to accommodate the new headers. Meanwhile, the Activate sink table is responsible for duplicating INT packets by executing the relevant action for packets destined for a particular interface with a specific UDP port.

In the egress pipeline, the control function directly triggers the addition of metadata through the 'adding metadata' action. This action retrieves INT metadata from various registers (CPU load, Antenna power register, Geo-latitude, Geo-longitude, and Geo-altitude registers), and writes them into the corresponding header fields. It also decreases the number of hops by 1 and assigns this modified value to the remaining hop field in the INT header, which determines the number of traversed nodes. Finally, it updates the lengths of the IP, UDP, and Shim headers to accommodate the new metadata information added by the node. The table 'Report Forwarding', adopted at the last node of the chain, is tasked with altering the destination of the duplicated INT packet (report) by modifying the MAC address of this packet.

7.4.2.2 L2.5 implementation

Implementation for the SDN transport domain

FIGURE 55: SDN INBAND TELEMETRY HEADER

FIGURE 56: SDN INBAND CONTROL HEADER

The L2.5 In-band Network Telemetry is implemented at the SDN transport domain, it uses the header shown in Figure 55. The SDN INT header goes directly after the Ethernet header and uses the label forwarding to determine the output port of the current packet. It goes beyond the traditional Match – Action forwarding model which normally maps a header field (such as label, or IP destination address) to an output port of the switch. The forwarding model used here maps the label to a register index (instead of an output port) then the output port value is read from that register. Because Match-Action entries in P4 are only changeable by control plane and not by the data plane, updating a Match-Action entry can take hundreds of milliseconds up to a few seconds. However, registers in P4 programmable switches are readable and writable at the line rate from the data plane, so no delay is introduced in this case, and it is possible to update the values almost immediately as a control packet is received. This forwarding mechanism is illustrated in Figure 57. The process starts from left to right in reference to Figure . A packet with the Desire6G Main header enters the SDN transport domain and is parsed by the

P4 parser of the ingress node, the field “Service ID” of the Desire6G Main header is used as a match field to Table 1, which then maps to an SDN label and inserts the SDN INT header show in Figure 55 into the packet and saves the EtherType field into the Original EtherType, and update the EtherType field of the packet to point to the SDN INT header, so later nodes can detect the existence of the INT and base their processing on it. The SDN label has a global significance within the SDN transport domain and is used by each node in the domain to determine a register index to read the output port from that register. Back to the figure, after the “Service ID” is mapped to an SDN label, a second table is applied, Table 2 which then maps the SDN label to a register index from which the relevant output port is read the packet is forwarded to that port. Later nodes within the SDN domain do not need to parse the Desire6G Main header and instead parse only the SDN INT header to read the SDN label. Thus, the processing of the subsequent nodes starts at Table 1. Hop Latency is also collected at each node by measure the difference between the Ingress and Egress time stamps of each packet at each node, which is then added to the SDN total hop latency field.

FIGURE 57: SDN PACKET FORWARDING BY READING OUTPUT PORT FROM A REGISTER ARRAY

The egress node of the SDN transport domain would then pop (remove) the SDN INT header and restore the EtherType field of the Ethernet header to point again to the Desire6G main header, the packet then exits the SDN transport domain unchanged. While the removed header is forwarded to a Data-Plane Active Collector (DPAC) (runs on a P4 switch) which reads the total SDN latency (this is done in the data plane at line speed) and the DPAC check for latency violations. If a violation is detected the SDN label is matched to a backward label and a backup port, and a packet is forwarded to the ingress node of the path that encountered the violation of the latency carrying instructions to change the output port (saved in the data plane register) to the backup one. This whole reconfiguration process happens in the data

plane at the line speed and avoids the processing delays encountered from carrying the telemetry data to the higher layers. This process is illustrated in Figure 58.

FIGURE 58: THE RECONFIGURATION PROCESS DONE BY THE SDN INGRESS NODE WHEN RECEIVING AN INC MESSAGE

The implementation over the Desire6G entire domain from UE to Central Site

Apart from the SDN transport domain the timestamps of certain nodes are collected as the packet traverses the Desire6G domain from the UE to the central site. The telemetry header with these timestamps is inserted after the DESIRE6G header (as opposed to the SDN transport domain where the telemetry header is inserted before the DESIRE6G header) as in the SDN INT, the “Service ID” field of the Desire6G main header is matched to determine if the flow needs to be monitored for Quality of Service, if so the DESIRE6G INT header (shown in Figure 59) is inserted and updated with the timestamps of determined P4 nodes in the domain.

FIGURE 59: DESIRE6G INT HEADER

The DESIRE6G INT header is then removed from the packet at the central site and is collected by the telemetry collector for the monitoring of the End-to-End service quality.

7.4.3 Usage and Interfaces

Activation of the proposed solution relies on P4Runtime, with the configuration of proper flow entries to activate INT generation for a specific flow. For the UE implementation, where no direct configuration API is available, some of the functionalities and parameters are pre-configured according to the node information.

7.4.4 Evaluation

Functional validation

A functional validation of the L4 implementation has been implemented in a 4 nodes testbed. An API in Linux has been launched on each node to collect information about the antenna power of wireless interfaces, CPU load, and geo-location information. It gathers geo-location information from a Global Positioning System (GPS) device using a Python script that utilizes the gpsd library. This library facilitates interaction with GPS devices through the gpsd service. Then, the API writes this information inside the appropriate register and updates these values every 1 second. Three flows of traffic with different destination UDP ports (i.e., 12345, 12344, 12343) have been generated in P4S4. The three flows are injected into the P4S container for processing. Here the P4S4 acts as a source node, selectively inserting shim and INT headers only into the flows destined for UDP ports 12345 and 12343, based on predefined flow entries, shown in Figure 60.

The switch adds its metadata to these two flows and forwards the three flows to P4S2. P4S2, in turn, appends its metadata to the incoming flows and forwards the three flows to P4S1, the sink node.

The figure shows that the length of the ingress packets is 44Bytes for the three flows. After the addition of the INT header, related to each node, 12 + 40 bytes are added (resulting length of 96Bytes).

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	0.000000000	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12345 Len=2
2	1.047799469	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12344 Len=2
3	2.103186017	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12343 Len=2

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	0.000000000	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	96	54321 → 12345 Len=54
2	1.051752900	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	44	54321 → 12344 Len=2
3	2.111200663	10.10.10.102	10.10.10.103	UDP	96	54321 → 12343 Len=54

FIGURE 60: TRAFFIC CAPTURE IN THE EXPERIMENT, WITH INGRESS TRAFFIC (NO INT) IN THE TOP AND AUGMENTED TRAFFIC IN THE BOTTOM

In the implementation, the maximum path length is assumed equal to 6, with a maximum INT size of 252 bytes in the worst case (at the sink node).

End-to-end latency

The purpose of this set of experiments is to check the ability of the P4S container to process FINT information with a limited additional latency compared to the latency introduced with standard forwarding, with variable topology of P4S nodes with different path depths and variable traffic. Moreover, we investigate the ability of the P4S container to manage and process FINT information for any switch role (source, transit and sink). The impact of data plane programmability in terms of accumulated latency was evaluated. The ICMP traffic has been used for the generation of packets at variable rates. The latency is evaluated as a function of the traffic bitrate and path length, ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 4 nodes. In these experiments, the Round Trip Time (RTT) latency measured by Ping includes all the P4-UE system, with a wireless interface and nodes connected with wired links.

Ping packets are generated externally to the P4S container and are routed inside the P4S container which processes the packet.

In the set of measurements without INT, each switch was configured only in static forwarding mode, allowing pings to be routed to the next hop in a bidirectional fashion. In the set of measurements with INT, the P4S has been populated with flow rules to correctly manage the INT. Then, a first INT stack was

configured up to the sink node. The sink node eliminates all INT headers and forwards the ping request packet to the external radio interface of the last node. The interface responds with a ping reply in the backward direction. In this case, the local node acts as the source node for a new INT stack backwards to the source. The experienced RTT results are shown in Table 9 when varying the rate of the packet per second (p/s) and the number of the switches.

TABLE 9: RTT MEASUREMENTS

Rate (p/s)	RTT without INT (msec)			RTT with INT by (msec)		
	2 switches	3 switches	4 switches	2 switches	3 switches	4 switches
1	4.896	6.953	14.243	5.627	8.980	13.276
10	5.164	6.461	13.045	5.712	8.980	12.991
100	4.272	5.687	10.895	5.103	8.980	11.217
1000	4.039	6.595	9.470	5.830	8.980	10.037

The table shows that the additional contribution due to INT processing is always less than 0.5 ms per node in a single direction. The non-linear latency values concerning data plane bitrate are attributed to the behaviour of the BMv2 container which is well known in the literature [32][32][32]. Specifically, the switch demonstrates superior performance within an aggregate bitrate range of 150 to 800 Mbit/s, exhibiting increased latency at lower bitrate. However, it is clearly noticed that the latency is always less than 5ms per node, with or without INT.

7.5 RAN Telemetry Exposure

In 5G and beyond, telemetry enables dynamic network adjustments based on real-time data analysis. For example, data collected from Distributed Units (DUs), Radio Units (RUs), and Central Units (CUs) help optimize resource usage, balance loads, and improve energy efficiency across the network. The integration of AI and Machine Learning (ML) further enhances telemetry's role, as AI algorithms use

telemetry data to automate network management, enabling near-instant adjustments to optimize performance and energy use.

Looking ahead to 6G, the role of RAN telemetry will expand significantly. Emerging technologies such as Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and advanced spectrum management strategies will all depend on robust telemetry systems to function efficiently. Dynamic spectrum re-farming, for example, will rely heavily on real-time telemetry data to make decisions regarding spectrum allocation and interference management. Without accurate and timely telemetry data, these innovations would be challenging to implement effectively.

Additionally, Open RAN (O-RAN) architectures play a critical role in advancing telemetry systems. O-RAN introduces the RAN Intelligent Controllers (RIC), both in Near-RT and Non-RT forms, which use telemetry data to drive intelligent network decisions. These RICs ingest data from various sources in the RAN, process it using AI/ML models and make real-time decisions that optimize network performance. Telemetry serves as the backbone of this decision-making process, ensuring that the network remains responsive and adaptive to changing conditions, including fluctuations in traffic, mobility patterns, and resource availability.

Furthermore, 6G networks are expected to integrate more diverse data sources, such as environmental sensors and positioning systems, which will feed additional telemetry data into the system. This expanded scope of telemetry will enable networks to not only optimize performance but also address broader goals such as reducing electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure and improving user experience in urban and rural environments.

7.5.1 Novelty Beyond the State-of-the-Art

The Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture represents a significant evolution in how telemetry is collected, processed, and used for network optimization. Traditional RAN systems typically rely on vendor-specific solutions that are tightly coupled with proprietary hardware, limiting flexibility and innovation. O-RAN breaks away from this paradigm by introducing open, standardized interfaces (such as E2, O1, and A1), which facilitate the integration of third-party applications (xApps and rApps) for telemetry collection and control.

In O-RAN systems, the RAN Intelligent Controllers (RIC) – both in their near-real-time (Near-RT) and nonreal-time (Non-RT) forms – play a crucial role in leveraging telemetry data to optimize network performance. The Near-RT RIC enables real-time adjustments by collecting telemetry data from network elements such as DUs and RUs. This data is used to drive optimizations in areas like resource scheduling, energy efficiency, and user mobility. The Non-RT RIC, on the other hand, is responsible for longer-term network planning and policy management, often using machine learning (ML) models trained on historical telemetry data to make informed decisions.

A key innovation in this project lies in extending telemetry collection to include non-O-RAN-compliant elements. Many networks still contain legacy systems or proprietary devices that do not fully adhere to O-RAN standards. Traditional telemetry frameworks are often limited in their ability to integrate data from these non-compliant components. This project introduces a flexible telemetry architecture that bridges the gap between O-RAN and non-O-RAN systems, allowing data from proprietary sensors, legacy infrastructure, or even custom-built radios to be collected and processed alongside standardized O-RAN components O-RAN Alliance.

Another novel feature is the system's ability to handle more diverse data sources. As 6G technologies evolve, the network will need to process telemetry from new types of devices and systems, such as environmental sensors, user equipment with advanced sensing capabilities, and infrastructure providing Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS). These devices introduce new data streams that traditional RAN telemetry systems were not designed to handle. The extended telemetry framework is capable of ingesting and processing this wider variety of data, enabling more sophisticated network optimizations, such as dynamic spectrum re-farming, real-time interference management, and energy-efficient network configurations.

Furthermore, advancements in programmable telemetry, such as the RANSight platform, are revolutionizing the way telemetry data is collected and exposed within the RAN. Programmable telemetry allows for highly customizable data collection pipelines, where network operators can specify the exact metrics they want to collect and how they want to process them. This flexibility enables more granular control over network operations and allows for real-time adjustments to be made based on precise, localized data. These advancements in programmable telemetry have far-reaching implications,

especially for AI-driven network management, which relies on vast amounts of accurate and timely data to function effectively.

Lastly, recent updates to the O-RAN specifications have introduced enhanced support for telemetry collection and management. The latest revisions to the O1 and E2 interfaces have refined how telemetry data is transmitted between network components and the RICs, improving both the speed and accuracy of data transmission. These updates also include expanded support for new use cases, such as network slicing and autonomous vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communications. By building on these developments, this project ensures that the telemetry system is future-proof, capable of supporting the rapidly evolving demands of next-generation networks O-RAN Alliance.

DESIRE6G architecture supports programmable data plane implementation where in network functions like CU-UP are realised as P4 programmable data plane components which run in CPUs, Smart NIC cards or Tofino switches. This introduces the scope for P4 INT (in band network telemetry) which can expose telemetry to all routers and switches in the packet data network. This allows for run-time optimisation of network paths taken by the packets including QoS. RAN telemetry collected via E2 interface is exposed to near RT RIC. The near RT RIC publishes this telemetry data to Kafka data bus as JSON messages. The desire 6G INT framework reads data from Kafka bus and exposes this data to MAS agents in near-RT RIC as well as non-RT RIC. The MAS agents perform runtime optimisation of user plane by interacting with SDN controller in non-RT RIC based on this telemetry data.

7.5.2 Implementation

Section 7.4.2 of D4.2, the previous version of this Deliverable, introduced and described the Accelleran Telemetry Collector and provided a high-level overview of its Architecture. That deliverable also described the standardised and proprietary input and output interfaces which, respectively, are the key providers of O-RAN telemetry and the mechanisms to execute RAN control actions.

Of these interfaces, the E2 interface could be considered as the key telemetry and action interface. In the O-RAN architecture, it connects the Near-Real-Time RIC (Near-RT RIC) to RAN O-CU and O-DU nodes and is responsible for both telemetry collection and control actions. It supports the collection of real-

time network data and enables RIC applications (xApps) to make decisions based on live telemetry, such as traffic load, signal quality, or resource usage.

E2 Service Models (E2SMs) define the structure and behaviour of telemetry and control exchanged over the E2 interface. For telemetry, E2SMs like E2SM-KPM (Key Performance Measurements) and E2SM-RC (RAN Control) specify how performance metrics, such as throughput, signal quality, and resource usage, are reported to the Near-RT RIC. These telemetry data streams enable xApps running on the Near-RT RIC to monitor RAN conditions in near real-time. For actions, E2SMs define how the RIC can issue control commands to the RAN nodes—such as load balancing, handover decisions, or radio parameter adjustments—based on analytics or learned policies.

7.5.2.1 The Telemetry to Action Workflow

The following sequence describes, in a high-level way, the general telemetry to action workflow.

- **Telemetry collection:** The RAN node sends real-time performance data (e.g., user load, interference, throughput) to the Near-RT RIC via E2SM-KPM or other telemetry service models.
- **Decision-making:** xApps running on the RIC analyse this data and determine whether action is needed e.g., to reduce congestion, improve QoS.
- **Action triggering:** The RIC sends an E2 control message containing the defined E2SM action e.g., initiate handover, adjust transmit power.
- **Execution:** The RAN node receives and applies the command and may optionally report back status or acknowledgment.

7.5.2.2 E2 O-DU Telemetry

The E2 O-DU telemetry available to the DESIRE6G project is summarised in Table 10 below.

TABLE 10: E2 INTERFACE O-DU TELEMETRY AVAILABLE IN DESIRE6G

Counter Family	KPI Name	KPI	Description

Radio resource utilization	DL Total PRB Usage	RRU.PrbTotDI	This measurement provides the total usage (in percentage) of physical resource blocks (PRBs) on the downlink for any purpose.
	UL Total PRB Usage	RRU.PrbTotUI	This measurement provides the total usage (in percentage) of physical resource blocks (PRBs) on the uplink for any purpose.
	DL total available PRB	RRU.PrbAvailDI	This measurement provides the total number of physical resource blocks (PRBs) in average available downlink.
	UL total available PRB	RRU.PrbAvailUI	This measurement provides the total number of physical resource blocks (PRBs) available uplink.
UE throughput	Average DL UE throughput in gNB	DRB.UETHpDI	This measurement provides the average UE throughput in downlink. This measurement is intended for data bursts that are large enough to require transmissions to be split across multiple slots.
	Average UL UE throughput in gNB	DRB.UETHpUI	This measurement provides the average UE throughput in uplink. This measurement is intended for data bursts that are large enough to require transmissions to be split across multiple slots.
CQI related measurements	Wideband CQI distribution	CARR.WBCQI ist.BinX.BinY.BinZ	This measurement provides the distribution of Wideband CQI (Channel Quality Indicator) reported by UEs in the cell.

Packet Drop Rate	DL RLC SDU Packet Drop Rate in gNB-DU	DRB.RlcPacket DropRateDL	This measurement provides the fraction of RLC SDU packets which are dropped on the downlink, due to high traffic load, traffic management etc in the gNB-DU.
Packet delay	Average delay DL in gNB-DU	DRB.RlcSduDelayDL	This measurement provides the average (arithmetic mean) RLC SDU delay on the downlink within the gNB-DU, for initial transmission of all RLC packets.
Data Volume	DL Transmitted Data Volume	DRB.RlcSduTransmittedVolumeDL_Filter	This measurement provides the transmitted data volume in the downlink in a measurement time.
	UL Transmitted Data Volume	DRB.RlcSduTransmittedVolumeUL_Filter	This measurement provides the transmitted data volume in the uplink in a certain period.
Packet Success	UL Packet Success Rate	DRB.PacketSuccessRateULgNB-Uu	UL Packet success rate for the DRB for a UE during measurement interval
Signal Quality	RSRP	RSRP	Average RSRP of the UE during measurement interval
	RSRQ	RSRQ	Average RSRQ of the UE during measurement interval
RLC Tx Rx Common Metrics	DU Id	du_id	DU id of the UE to which these measurement stats belong
	UE Id	ue_id	UE id of the UE to which these measurement stats belong

	DRB Id	drb_id	DRB id of the UE to which these measurement stats belong
RLC Tx Metrics	Number of SDUs	num_sdus	Number of SDUs transmitted during a measurement interval
	Number of SDU bytes	num_sdu_bytes	Number of SDU bytes transmitted during a measurement interval
	Number of dropped SDUs (due to full queue)	num_dropped_sdus	Number of dropped SDUs due to Queue full error during a measurement interval
	Number of discarded SDUs (instructed from higher layer)	num_discarded_sdus	Number of SDU discards during a measurement interval
	Total SDU latency	sum_sdu_latency_us	Total SDU latency in microseconds
	Number of transmitted PDUs without segmentation	num_pdus_no_segmentation	Number of transmitted PDUs without segmentation during the measurement interval
	Number of transmitted PDU bytes without segmentation	num_pdu_bytes_no_segmentation	Number of transmitted PDU bytes without segmentation during the measurement interval
	RLC Mode	mode	DL RLC mode for the DRB

	Number of allocations that are too small to TX PDU	num_small_allocs	Number of allocations that are too small for a TX PDU
	Number of transmitted PDUs with segmentation	num_pdus_with_segmentation	Number of downlink PDU segments transmitted to a UE during measurement interval
	Number of transmitted PDU bytes with segmentation	num_pdu_bytes_with_segmentation	Number of downlink RLC PDU bytes transmitted to a UE during a measurement interval
RLC TM Mode Tx Metrics	Number of RETX'ed PDUs	num_retx_pdu_s	Number of downlink RLC PDUs retransmitted to a UE during a measurement interval
RLC UM Mode Tx Metrics	Number of RETX'ed PDU bytes	num_retx_pdu_bytes	Number of downlink RLC PDU bytes retransmitted to a UE during a measurement interval
	Number of transmitted PDUs with segmentation	num_pdus_with_segmentation	Number of downlink RLC PDU segments sent for a UE during measurement interval
RLC AM Mode Tx Metrics	Number of transmitted PDU bytes with segmentation	num_pdu_bytes_with_segmentation	Number of downlink RLC PDU bytes sent for a UE during measurement interval

	Number of control PDUs	num_ctrl_pdu	Number of downlink control PDUs sent for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of control PDU bytes	num_ctrl_pdu_bytes	Number of DL RLC control PDU bytes sent for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of SDUs	num_sdus	Number of UL RLC SDUs received for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of SDU bytes	num_sdu_bytes	Number of UL RLC PDU bytes received for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of PDUs	num_pdus	Number of UL RLC PDUs received for a UE during measurement interval
RLC Rx Metrics	Number of PDU bytes	num_pdu_bytes	Number of UL RLC PDU bytes received for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of dropped PDUs (reassembly timeout expiry or out of rx window)	num_lost_pdus	Number of UL RLC PDUs lost during measurement interval
	Number of malformed PDUs	num_malformed_pdus	Number of UL RLC malformed PDUs received during measurement interval
	RLC Mode	mode	UL RLC mode for a UE
	Number of SDU segments RX'ed	num_sdu_segments	Number of UL RLC SDUs received for a UE during measurement interval

	Number of SDU segments Bytes	num_sdu_segment_bytes	Number of UL RLC bytes received for a UE during measurement interval
	Number of SDU segments RX'ed	num_sdu_segments	Number of SDU segments received at RLC
RLC UM Mode Rx Metrics	Number of SDU segments bytes	num_sdu_segment_bytes	Num of SDU bytes received at RLC
	Number of control PDUs	num_ctrl_pdus	Number of control PDUs received at RLC
RLC AM Mode Rx Metrics	Number of control PDU bytes	num_ctrl_pdu_bytes	Number of control PDU bytes received by RLC
	PCI	pci	PCI of the cell to which the UE is connected
	Number of PRBs	nof_prbs	Number of PRBs scheduled for the UE
	RNTI	rnti	RNTI of the UE
Scheduler Metrics	Channel Quality Indicator	cqi	Channel quality indication(CQI) of the UE
	Rank Indicator	ri	Rank indicator of the UE
	Downlink MCS	dl_mcs	Downlink MCS of the UE
	Downlink PRB Used	dl_prbs_used	Number of DL PRBs used by the UE
	Downlink Data Rate	dl_brate_kbps	Downlink data rate of the UE
	Downlink Data HARQ Acks	dl_nof_ok	Downlink HARQ ACKs received for the UE

Downlink Data HARQ Nacks	dl_nof_nok	Downlink HARQ NACKs received for the UE
Average PUSCH SNR	pusch_snr_db	Average PUSCH SINR detected for the UE
Average PUSCH RSRP	pusch_rsrp_db	Average PUSCH RSRP for UE during measurement interval
Average PUCCH SNR	pucch_snr_db	Average PUCCH SINR detected for the UE
Uplink MCS	ul_mcs	Uplink MCS detected for the UE
Uplink PRB Used	ul_prbs_used	Uplink PRBs used by the UE
Uplink Data Rate	ul_brake_kbps	Uplink data rate of the UE
Uplink Data HARQ Acks	ul_nof_ok	Uplink HARQ ACKs sent for the UE
Uplink Data HARQ Nacks	ul_nof_nok	Uplink HARQ NACKs sent for the UE
Uplink Buffer Status Report	bsr	Uplink buffer status report for the UE
Downlink buffer Status	dl_bs	Downlink Buffer status for the UE
Last Timing Advance	last_ta	Timing advance computed for the UE
Last PHR	last_phr	Power Headroom reported by the UE

7.5.2.3 E2 O-CU Telemetry

The E2 O-CU telemetry available to the DESIRE6G project is summarised in Table 11 below.

TABLE 11: E2 INTERFACE O-CU TELEMETRY AVAILABLE IN DESIRE6G

Counter Family	KPI Name	KPI	Description
RRC connection number	Mean number of RRC Connections	RRC.ConnMean	This measurement provides the mean number of users in RRC connected mode for each NR cell during each granularity period.
	Max number of RRC Connections	RRC.ConnMax	This measurement provides the maximum number of users in RRC connected mode for each NR cell during each granularity period.
PDU Session Management	Number of PDU Sessions requested to setup	SM.PDUSessionSetupReq	This measurement provides the number of PDU Sessions by the gNB.
	Number of PDU Sessions failed to setup	SM.PDUSessionSetupFail	This measurement provides the number of PDU Sessions failed to setup by the gNB. This measurement is split into subcounters per failure cause.
Mobility Management - Inter gNB HO	Number of requested legacy handover preparations	MM.HoPrepInterReq	This measurement provides the number of legacy handover preparations requested by the source gNB.
	Number of successful legacy handover preparations	MM.HoPrepInterSucc	This measurement provides the number of successful legacy handover preparations received by the source NR cell CU.
Intra gNB HO	Number of requested legacy	MM.HoExeIntraReq	This measurement provides the number of outgoing intra gNB legacy

	handover executions		handover executions requested by the source NRCellCU.
	Number of successful legacy handover executions	MM.HoExeIntraSucc	This measurement provides the number of successful intra gNB legacy handover executions received by the source NRCellCU.
DRB related measurements	Number of DRBs attempted to setup	DRB.EstabAtt	This measurement provides the number of DRBs attempted to setup to support all requested QoS flows in the PDU sessions to be setup by the INITIAL CONTEXT SETUP REQUESTs, PDU SESSION RESOURCE SETUP REQUESTs and PDU SESSION RESOURCE MODIFY REQUEST message received by the gNB from AMF.
	Number of DRBs successfully setup	DRB.EstabSucc	This measurement provides the number of DRBs successfully setup to support all requested QoS flows in the PDU sessions to be setup by the INITIAL CONTEXT SETUP REQUESTs, PDU SESSION RESOURCE SETUP REQUESTs and PDU SESSION RESOURCE MODIFY REQUEST message received by the gNB from AMF.
	Number of released active DRBs	DRB.RelActNbr	This measurement provides the number of abnormally released DRBs that were active at the time of release.

RRC connection establishment related measurements	Attempted RRC connection establishments	RRC.ConnEstabAtt	This measurement provides the number of RRC connection establishment attempts for each establishment cause.
	Successful RRC connection establishments	RRC.ConnEstabSucc	This measurement provides the number of successful RRC establishments for each establishment cause.
Packet Loss Rate	UL PDCP SDU Loss Rate	DRB.PacketLossRateUI	This measurement provides the fraction of PDCP SDU packets which are not successfully received at gNB-CU-UP.
	UL F1-U Packet Loss Rate	DRB.F1UpacketLossRateUI	This measurement provides the fraction of PDCP SDU packets which are not successfully received at gNB-CU-UP.
Packet Drop Rate	DL PDCP SDU Drop rate in gNB-CU-UP	DRB.PdcpPacketDropRateDL	This measurement provides the fraction of PDCP SDU packets which are dropped on the downlink, due to high traffic load, traffic management etc in the gNB-CU-UP.
Packet delay	Average delay DL in CU-UP	DRB.PdcpSduDelayDLFilter	This measurement provides the average (arithmetic mean) PDCP SDU delay on the downlink within the gNB-CU-UP, for all PDCP packets.
	Distribution of delay DL in CU-UP	DRB.PdcpSduDelayDIDistribution.Filter	This measurement provides the distribution of PDCP SDU delay on the downlink within the gNB-CU-UP, for all PDCP packets.
GTP Throughput	UL GTP Throughput	UL_GTP_THP	Measure of UL GTP data received during the reporting period in the

			observed cell. Data for all UEs (all PDU sessions) in a cell is aggregated
	DL GTP Throughput	DL_GTP_THP	Measure of DL GTP data received during the reporting period in the observed cell. Data for all UEs (all PDU sessions) in a cell is aggregated

7.5.2.4 E2 Actions

E2SMs define how the RIC (xApps), based on analytics or learned policies, can issue control commands to the RAN nodes—such as load balancing, handover decisions, or radio parameter adjustments.

The principle E2SM for E2 actions in DESIRE6G is E2SM-RC (RAN Control). E2SM-RC enables radio configuration control such as, Cell configuration, UE handover commands for connected UEs and RRM (Radio Resource Management) parameter tuning. It also supports RIC-controlled policies, with the ability to dynamically adjust radio settings in response to changing network conditions.

7.5.3 Scalability and Future Enhancements

The Accelleran Telemetry Collector Architecture is built with scalability in mind, designed to accommodate the increasing complexity and data volume of 6G networks. As technologies like Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) and Joint Communication and Sensing (JCS) become more integrated into the network, the system will need to handle an even greater diversity of data sources.

To support these advancements, the architecture is modular, allowing for the easy addition of new protocols and interfaces as they become necessary. The system's ability to scale horizontally by adding new processing nodes and vertically by increasing its processing power ensures that it can grow with the demands of next-generation networks O-RAN Alliance.

Future iterations of the system will focus on improving the integration of AI and ML into the decision-making process, enabling the network to optimize itself autonomously based on the telemetry data it

collects. This will further reduce operational overhead and improve network efficiency, particularly in dense, urban deployments where real-time data processing is critical.

7.6 Self-contained software monitoring

Self-contained monitoring consists of monitoring the performance of the software by itself, through modifications which enable this monitoring. The research activity results in a feasibility study, based on a testbed which enables to measure and validate the solution. This feasibility study is positioned over three core values of accuracy (i.e., reflecting measures accuracy), convergence (i.e., reflecting the time required for a measure) and penalty (i.e., reflecting how the measurement impact performance). Our research has cleared up misconceptions and biased measures before reaching valuable conclusions and elaborated techniques exposed below. We had corrected erroneous implementations and reconsidered how the technique could be used. We had produced a massive quantity of measurements made over a set of standard algorithms and the emblematic L2fwd network function.

7.6.1 Novelty beyond the state of the art

The state of the art is made of various performance monitoring tools installed on the platform and extracting metrics. The key novelty is to obviate to the installation of such tools. Self-contained monitoring is worked out in any execution environment without restriction as it is a function of the software itself, not of the environment. A second benefit is the lower performance penalty incurred by the traditional performance monitoring. A third benefit is to enable the performance monitoring of continuous lifespan workloads (e.g., L2Fwd network function) for which there are no solution today. Self-contained monitoring works at finite-lifespan code block level to extract performance ratio.

7.6.2 Usage and Interfaces

7.6.2.1 Usage

Two core usages resulted from our work:

Execution environment status

The core usage of self-monitoring is to bring insight on the execution environment state. This insight is in fact focused on the workload execution environment, a sub-part of the platform execution environment. We can check the stress level of the CPU by inserting an ad hoc specific reference block.

Speed of execution of the workload

With a knowledge of the code structure, it is possible to insert probes at selected locations, marking the walk through these locations. Probing the code at different locations enables to assess the call frequency of each of these locations. From these call frequencies located at the right code block, it is possible to extrapolate the speed of execution of the software.

7.6.2.2 Interfaces

The solution does not expose interfaces per-se, usable for external tools.

7.6.3 Evaluation

The general objective of the self-contained software monitoring is captured below. Prior execution, the original binary file is patched with trampolines inserted into the software control flow graph. A reference is produced to capture a normal execution speed. During the execution, the trampolines produce timestamps when they are traversed by the control flow. A comparison is then produced to assess the performance deviations to the reference.

As shown in Figure 61, before execution, the original binary file is patched with trampolines inserted into the software control flow graph. A reference is produced to capture a normal execution speed. During the execution, the trampolines produce timestamps when they are traversed by the control flow. A comparison is then produced to assess the performance deviations to the reference.

FIGURE 61: PRINCIPLE OF SELF-CONTAINED SOFTWARE MONITORING

As shown in Figure 62, our implementation general schema is given below. A shared memory is used to write (ie, by trampolines) and read timestamps (by the reader process). The reader produces a CSV file which is used in post processing to extract performance metrics.

FIGURE 62: GENERAL REPRESENTATION OF THE SELF-MONITORING TESTBED

The L2Fwd specific testbed is represented below in Figure 63. This test setup uses two virtual machines: VM 1 runs the TREX traffic generator, sending up to 1 Gbps of traffic to VM 2, which runs the l2fwd application to forward packets back. We measure all incoming and outgoing traffic from l2fwd internal counters.

FIGURE 63: L2FWD SELF-MONITORING SPECIFIC TESTBED

ET and CF metrics

We had defined two core metrics used for our research, defined as the Execution Time (ET) and the Call Frequency (CF). We initially considered to set trampolines of the original code blocks to extract both metrics. ET is the measure of the time to execute the code block, CF its call frequency (i.e., number of calls per unit of time). The two metrics are reflecting two different sides of the code block as CF reflects what is located outside de block (i.e., calling it) and ET what is inside the block.

Need for reference block

Our initial approach was to monitor each code blocks, delivered by the static analysis tool. This approach was unappropriated in the directions of excessive overhead caused by the monitoring and of biased measures caused by the control flow graph imprecision aka CFG undecidability. As a matter of fact, the linker can create unpredictable jumps inside a code block after its entry point hence after our trampoline which will not be traversed. Identically, a jump from the code block before it is terminated is also possible, so that our trampoline located just before its exit will not be traversed. To solve this issue, we insert our own code block here represented in blue colour with the other original blocks. The reference code does not produce operations and is forcibly executed from its entry point to exit, as being unknown by the rest of the code. To solve this issue, we insert our own code block here represented in blue colour with the other original blocks as shown in Figure 64. The reference code does not produce operations and is forcibly executed from its entry point to exit, as being unknown by the rest of the code. This method has greatly improved our method, in all directions and notably accuracy and penalty limitation. As shown in the Figure 64, The reference code block captures both Execution Time and Call Frequency.

FIGURE 64. DUAL METRIC REFERENCE BLOCK PLACEMENT AND USABILITY

Stress level assessment on finite lifespan workloads

For finite-duration workloads, by fixing the operands, we observed a strong correlation between stress level and call frequency. To exploit this relationship, we can use two approaches: linear interpolation and modelling as shown in Figure 65.

FIGURE 65. LINEAR AND QUADRATIC INTERPOLATIONS OF CALL FREQUENCY VERSUS STRESS LEVEL

L2FWD experiments. Using CF and ET to assess traffic volume (ingress and egress)

We have reversed L2Fwd and insert our reference block in the main packet processing loop, with the objective of showing the correlations between CF, ET and the traffic volume, simulating various CPU stress conditions with an adjustable quantity of consuming workers.

FIGURE 66. LF2WD. IMPACT OF ET AND CF CF IN STRESSED CONDITIONS

As shown in Figure 66, ET and CF are inversely proportional. This signifies the code block is a good selection as its expansion of execution time is aligned with the extension of the rest of the code expansion of

execution time (i.e., reflected by CF, a measure of how frequently the code block is called by the rest of the code). The mismatch between CF and ET when considered at the function or code block level is explained as function are integrating the code blocks with very different level of occurrences so that some highly varying blocks may relatively less occur in function. We have then considered how CF and ET could reflect the egress volume, setting the dual-metric reference code block in the packet main processing loop. As reflected in Figure 67, we found that CF (on the right side) delivered a good match. Conversely, ET (on the left side) is poorly correlated as the execution time can very much vary according to time locality.

FIGURE 67. USABILITY OF CF AND ET FOR EGRESS ASSESSMENT

CF set in main packet processing loop, a measure of traffic volume

We several iterations, we had defined a scheme to assess the traffic volume in non-saturated conditions.

We first realized that in a **saturation regime**, there any rationale to see the performance drop, apart the probable elevation of temperature and subsequent IPC drop. However, there is a possible activation of IPC boost by the processor. In other words, a flood attack on the network function would in fact not degrade the performance of the network function, which will process the ingress packets at its own pace which is fixed by the execution environment. if the traffic takes one or several orders of magnitude, the NF's performance ratio will not change, showing no correlation between the speed of execution of the NF and the traffic volume. **In a non-saturated mode**, and more precisely in situation where packets are processed as soon as they reach the NF (i.e., w/o bufferization of the packets), we had assessed if we can collect a variation of the NF performance. At first, there are no reason for any loss of the CPU speed and the network function will keep executing at this own nominal speed. Therefore, positioning CF on the packet processing branch directly reflects the speed of arrival of the ingress packets. Each time a packet arrives, a call to the

NF packet processing branch is produced. This reflects that CF is CFG and data-dependent and can be used to collect L2Fwd operational metrics (e.g., traffic volume throughput). As soon as the traffic volume augments beyond what the NF can process, a FIFO buffer will start growing. NF will be unchanged whatever the traffic volume as stated above in saturated regime.

Identifying processor stress conditions

We first measured ET for a reference block located in all entries of all blocks of the Primes Calculator. Figure 68 shows how CPU frequency scaling can accelerate execution, leading to a drop-in execution time until it stabilizes around 580 TSCs.

FIGURE 68. ET VARIATION OVER TIME

We had then stressed the processor and could reveal interruption, reflected as vertical empty tunnels where no execution is processed. Our reference code block was sporadically put on hold by the dispatcher, breaking the correlation between ET and the egress traffic. This is shown in Figure 68.

When this happens, the execution of the block is paused and resumed later, which artificially inflates its measured execution time. This added delay does not reflect the actual processing time of the block itself but rather the time it spent waiting due to a context switch or CPU scheduling event.

In Figure 69 (left side), we see that when no NOPs are added to the reference block (i.e., left side) there are no observed interruptions captured in the reference block. In contrast, Figure 69 right side shows that adding 2 million NOPs, providing a sufficiently large number of instructions in the reference block, makes it possible to observe a correlation with packets sent as it is affected by the same number of interruptions.

FIGURE 69. CORRELATED BLOCK ET AND PACKETS WITH NO AND HIGH NUMBER OF NOPS

Usability of CF and ET metrics

Call Frequency CF, with original control flow graph blocks or being an added CF reference code block.

- Pros: Good collector of global program performance as CF represents the speed of what is executed outside the reference block.
- Cons: CF may be CFG-dependent, and data driven (case of conditional jumps). Typically, a CF reference block could decrease if there is data-driven test made upstream that reduces the frequency of flow execution in the branch that contains the CF reference block.
- Typical use:
 - Accurate software monitoring based on these CF markers located at the right places (ie, routines of interest).
 - This accuracy does not come for free. CF correct positions must be cared with a deep understanding of the code (or a static analysis on the executable)
 - CFs can be used to assess the software global performance with predefined datasets. These performance-related datasets can be defined to induce repeated CFG flows, hence enable calibration and measurements.
- **Execution Time ET** of a given code block, (ideally on an injected ET reference block).
 - Pros:
 - ET reference blocks being added post-compilation are unknown to the compiler and linker, hence cannot be jumped to after their entry point or left before their last instruction. They are solving the problem of CFG undecidability we had faced at the initial stage of our research.

- ET reference blocks execution can be defined to be cache independent; hence their execution speed does not depend on the status of the cache.

Cons:

ET reference blocks must be long enough to capture interruptions by the dispatcher, therefore induce penalty.

○ Typical use:

- Revealer of resource sharing by on-demand probes (to avoid excessive induced penalty) located at locations of the CFG which ensures that they can be traversed within a reasonable delay.
- Do not bring insight on cache usage as they are cache-agnostic.

7.6.4 Limitations and further plans

The limitations or challenges of self-contained monitoring are several:

7.6.4.1 Requirements for pre-deployment code analysis and baseline definition

The solution requires a hybrid analysis (ie, static code analysis and dynamic analysis by tracing tool) and more generally a good understanding of the software structure and functions to position adequately the reference blocks. Typically, for using CF as a marker of the software throughput as we did for L2Fwd, we had gone to a reverse engineering to identify the packet main processing loop. The solution modifies the binary, another severe workflow hurdle, significantly affecting the user acceptability and solution scalability. Last, the definition of the baseline, serving as a reference for both ET and CF requires to define arbitrarily the normal execution through an averaging over a sufficiently long time.

7.6.4.2 Limitations

Multi causal opacity

Software performance depends on past and present processed data (i.e., past data influences cache hit rates) and execution environment status (e.g., its load level at a given time, its IDC variation by boost or throttling). We do not have a strategy to discern the cause, without directly modifying

these endogenous or exogenous conditions (e.g., cache prefetching, inhibiting Intel's *TurboBoost* or equivalent, setting CPU reserve for a process). This opacity decreases the trustworthiness of the measurement or derivative conclusions. For instance, CF, when adequately placed, is a good metric to assess ingress traffic in normal conditions. If the processor gets stressed and sets the network function in idle mode, CF will decrease while the ingress traffic has not changed.

Overhead

In a general perspective, our work has always opposed overhead and accuracy. As an emblematic example, capturing system interruption on our reference code block comes only with sufficient long code blocks, hence impacting the performance severely. Additionally, patching multiple blocks has clearly improved the solution's accuracy and convergence time, but it has also increased the associated penalty.

7.6.4.3 Future plan

Towards simplified DevSecOps for higher acceptability.

All pre-deployment tasks as cited above shall be either simplified with automation or simply suppressed. On that direction, we consider leveraging ad-hoc monitoring agents able to grasp at least the execution environment status, then tentatively grasp the data processing logic of the monitored workload. It is worth noting that this would create a deviation to our original concept of self-contained performance monitoring, as the workload will no longer monitor itself.

In a general perspective, capturing the execution environment status will lead a workload-agnostic common agent, as opposed to capturing the workload data processing stream which will lead to the design of workload-specific agents. However, we may also consider the relevance, feasibility and limits of sifting the calls and jumps made by a workload agnostic agent, accessing to the workload dynamic stack.

Last and ideally, for containerized workloads, we consider a sidecar-mounted agent, without making any change on the monitored workload. This configuration is 1:1 matching with D-MUTRA remote attestation solution so that the same sidecar would be extended to performance monitoring.

Penalty limitation

The agent shall be only launched on-demand, restricting and fixing the impact on performance. We truly believe that with the blockchain overlay set up for D-MUTRA, one separate smart contract can trigger on-demand performance monitoring, follow user-intent or orchestrate automated security policy. On-demand performance monitoring is the best choice to limit the performance overhead to the lowest, being time-limited.

Removing opacity

Getting our own agent, arbitrarily programmed, broadens the possibilities compared to what can be done by modifying the workload. We may be able to discern the root cause of software performance variation (ie, endogenous, exogeneous) with a programmed discriminating algorithm.

An area of progression is to set up CF before the exit of a code block of function instead of its entry point. By doing so, we remove the ambiguity of a possible interruption inside the reference code block.

Towards code optimisation

The solution may be used for network function design optimization. By setting up several CF reference blocks at developer defined location, the solution could identify potential bottleneck set along the processing path. We are considering developing this idea in the last period of DESIRE-6G.

7.7 Cloud monitoring manager

The need of monitoring cloud resources has driven us to develop a new monitoring module for such purpose. The monitoring manager is responsible of two main tasks:

- Perform the infrastructure monitoring of a cloud cluster
- Perform the resource occupation evaluation of a specific pod running in the cluster.

In particular, the module relies on Kubernetes cluster, running on a DESIRE6G site, where multiple nodes are included. Kubernetes APIs are exploited in order to collect relevant metrics.

The module exposes REST API for the activation of monitoring thread on demand, while the data is pushed in the local (i.e., within the site) Kafka cluster.

7.7.1 Novelty beyond the state of the art

The module represents an innovation with respect to the literature, enabling the possibility of collecting in real time cloud metrics, meeting the requirements of the demonstrators.

7.7.2 Implementation

The monitoring manager is composed by the main module running a flask application, implementing the REST API. Figure 70 shows the view of the flask REST plus module running in the module. A k8s environment has been considered for the deployment of pods pertaining to a specific : DESIRE6G service with a service_name. The pods, belonging to the service, are deployed in a specific namespace. Three APIs are implemented:

- **MonitoringManger/getJobs** exposes a GET method to list the active monitoring jobs;
- **MonitoringManger/startJob** exposes a PUT method for the activation of a new monitoring job. It requires three input parameters: (i) service_name, (ii) namespace, (iii) pod name. The API returns the assigned job_id.
- **MonitoringManger/stopJobs** exposes a DELETE method to delete a monitoring job, requiring as input parameter the job_id.

FIGURE 70: MONITORING MANAGER REST VIEW

The main thread of the module, started automatically, is in charge of collecting cluster resource availability. In particular, this thread collects the output of the `kubectl top nodes`, obtaining the aggregated total and available CPU (in millicore) and total and available RAM.

The output is pushed in the Kafka cluster under the topic “infrastructure” following the format reported in Figure

```
{
  "totCPU (mCore)": {
    "0": 64000
  },
  "totmem": {
    "0": 388000
  },
  "available mCore": {
    "0": 62464
  },
  "available Mem": {
    "0": 350679
  }
}
```

FIGURE 71: OUTPUT OF INFRASTRUCTURE CLOUD MONITORING

By exploiting the `MonitoringManger/startJob` the system spawns threads for the monitoring of pods.

Running the command `kubectl top pod` the system collects the metric for a specific pod, pushing the data in the topic `serviceName_namepsce_podName` in a csv-like format, including timestamp, cpu value (millicore) e RAM.

```
1750889720461.19;2.0;31.0;
```

FIGURE 72: POD DATA MONITORING

7.7.3 Usage and Interfaces

The module relies in Kubernetes APIs and exposes a REST-based API for starting, stopping and listing monitoring jobs.

7.7.4 Evaluation

The module has been functionally validated collecting data for both infrastructure and pods, connecting it with a local Kafka cluster. The infrastructure metrics were periodically provided by the main thread of the system, being then consumed by a Kafka consumer subscribed to the infrastructure topic. Moreover, different parallel jobs were enabled to monitor the performance of different pods, running in the same namespace and in different namespaces. The monitoring jobs were created and deleted, testing all the functionalities of the system.

7.7.5 Limitations and further plans

This is the first implementation of the module that has been designed for the collection of cloud entities (i.e., infrastructure and pod) metrics.

8 Application and network function acceleration and offloading

In this section we describe the final update on the components for acceleration or offloading of network functions as well as for application acceleration.

With respect to D4.2, for network function acceleration and offloading, we present updates on i) FlexUP, a framework to decompose and offload CU-UP processing across multiple heterogeneous programmable data plane devices, ii) the framework for the offloading of security functions on Bluefield, and iii) the SDN controller of PREOF, which enables deterministic networking. We also present two entirely new components which are iv) the framework for the offloading of the UPF on a Bluefield device and v) P4RROT, which provides Python abstractions to facilitate P4 programmability.

For application acceleration we present updates of vi) the SOL server, to accelerate neural network execution and enable power savings, and vii) the vAccel framework for seamless hardware acceleration across heterogeneous environments.

8.1 Accelerated CU-UP on SmartNIC

As 5G networks aim to meet demanding requirements—such as ultra-low latency, massive device connectivity, and multi-gigabit throughput [32][33][34][35] The Radio Access Network (RAN) often emerges as a key performance bottleneck [36][37][38]. The adoption of disaggregated and virtualized architectures, particularly through O-RAN, has introduced flexibility and scalability by decoupling hardware from software and promoting open interfaces. However, this shift also brings new challenges. General-purpose processors (GPPs), commonly used to virtualize RAN components, often fall short in meeting the strict latency and throughput demands of modern applications, especially in the user plane. These limitations are most pronounced in the Centralized Unit User Plane (CU-UP), which is responsible for compute-heavy tasks such as encryption, packet reordering, and tunnelling. While much of the research and optimization to date has focused on accelerating the Radio Unit (RU) and Distributed Unit (DU), the CU-UP remains relatively underexplored—still bound by the constraints of traditional CPU-based processing.

8.1.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

Recent studies [39] have begun to investigate the Centralized Unit (CU), proposing the offloading of certain functions to programmable switches. However, the study is preliminary and exhibit gaps in both design and implementation. During the project we further investigated the use of SmartNICs as an alternative [4]. Both approaches introduce a fast path/slow path abstraction: the fast path handles offloaded functions, while the slow path remains on the traditional CPU. On one hand, [40][41] explore offloading CU-UP functionalities to programmable switches but implements only a limited set of features—mainly PDCP sequencing and GTP-U. This restricts the number of flows that can be processed via the fast path and relies on an external classifier for path selection, which may further hinder scalability. On the other hand, [4] investigates the use of SmartNICs (i.e., Netronome Agilio) for offloading. Although this approach offloads a broader range of functionalities, it still depends on the slow path for critical functions such as packet reordering and deduplication.

Extending upon the study for offloading the CU-UP to a SmartNIC, we introduce [42][72] a modular and hierarchical strategy for CU-UP offloading. FlexUP combines the strengths of the aforementioned approaches by offloading CU-UP functionalities to programmable switches and SmartNICs in a coordinated, layered manner. It defines three processing paths—fast, medium, and slow—corresponding to execution on the switch, SmartNIC, and CPU, respectively (see Figure 73). By organizing offloading across these three tiers, FlexUP accelerates RAN performance, ensuring that traffic flows are processed only by the necessary components, often avoiding the traditional CPU altogether. Compared to the aforementioned approaches, FlexUP supports a broader set of functionalities on both the fast and medium paths, allowing a greater portion of traffic to benefit from hardware acceleration. Moreover, FlexUP includes its own intelligent agent for traffic classification and management. This agent makes dynamic decisions not only based on the available processing capabilities but also considering the specific requirements of each application and the current workload across the infrastructure.

FIGURE 73: FLEXUP OVERVIEW

8.1.2 Implementation

The FlexUP design is guided by two key principles: performance and modularity. It is designed to be adaptable across different deployment scenarios and scalable, enabling the addition of new HW nodes to both the fast and medium paths as needed. For example, if a deployment demands extra processing capacity on the medium path (e.g., due to high encryption loads), FlexUP allows additional nodes to be integrated seamlessly, without disrupting the overall architecture or operation. To maximize performance, FlexUP offloads as many functionalities as possible to the fast and medium paths, thereby reducing latency, improving overall throughput, and alleviating the CPU workload.

To fulfil these design goals, FlexUP must address several key challenges:

1. **Context-aware agents:** Both the fast and medium paths must implement lightweight agents capable of monitoring and interpreting the current traffic context, enabling dynamic and informed decisions about flow handling and offloading. This implies that the fast path must autonomously determine whether it can handle a given flow, and, if not, delegate it to a slower path. Additionally, it must maintain per-flow state information to support advanced functions such as packet reordering and deduplication. Similarly, the medium path, even implementing all functionalities, must also decide when to offload flows to the CPU, based on criteria such as its own current load, flow-specific performance requirements (e.g., prioritizing latency-sensitive flows), and overall system conditions.
2. **Resource constraints:** Despite being extremely efficient in packet processing, programmable switches and SmartNICs are very limited in terms of resources and supported operations. Programmable switches, while offering predictable high-performance execution, are restricted by a limited number of pipeline stages, a constrained instruction set, and the inability to perform complex

tasks such as encryption. In contrast, SmartNICs provide greater implementation flexibility, often including embedded CPU cores and hardware accelerators, but their limited resources can lead to significant performance degradation depending on the complexity of the assigned tasks. Implementing FlexUP's hierarchical scheme requires carefully navigating these constraints—leveraging the strengths of both architectures while coordinating their roles to optimize overall packet processing performance.

3. **Integration in heterogeneous infrastructures:** Integrating FlexUP with existing RAN components, software stacks like srsRAN and OAI (open source) implementations, demands harmonization of interfaces and protocols across heterogeneous hardware. Variations in timing, data formats, and abstraction levels between fast-path (Tofino), medium-path (SmartNIC), and slow-path (GPP) components can introduce integration complexity and operational overhead. Ensuring compatibility without sacrificing performance requires careful design of control and data plane interfaces, potentially necessitating customized adaptation layers.

FIGURE 74: FLEXUP ARCHITECTURE

Figure 74 presents the FlexUP architecture. Our architecture was designed to be implemented on programmable switches like Tofino, and SmartNICs with embedded CPU cores like Bluefield and Intel IPU.

Fast Path: In the fast path, we used Tofino as a programmable switch target. Therefore, our implementation is based on P4 and the Tofino native architecture (TNA). Since Tofino does not support encryption and compression/decompression, the only CU-UP features that can be implemented are Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) sequencing and reordering, SDAP QoS mapping, and GTP-U encapsulation. According to the 3GPP definition, the remaining features are optional and not required for all flows and applications.

The switch interfaces with F1 to the DU and N3 to the UPF, receiving and forwarding traffic accordingly. Upon receiving a packet, the switch determines whether it is destined for the CU-CP or CU-UP, as well as the ingress interface. For CU-UP packets, the switch invokes the FlexUP agent. The agent checks whether it already has a processing rule for the flow, i.e., if the FlexUP controller has made an offloading decision. If no decision exists, the packet is forwarded to the traditional CU-UP running on the CPU, and a notification is sent to the FlexUP controller. This message includes key flow information, such as QFI, sequence number, and GTP-U TEID. If a decision has already been made, the switch either processes the packet locally or forwards it to the appropriate offloading target, as instructed by the controller. All this processing is implemented using match-action tables and registers, which store flow state information.

Medium Path: In the medium path we used an NVIDIA BlueField-2, leveraging DPDK and DOCA Flow to construct a hardware-assisted, low-latency user plane pipeline. This design supports key CU-UP functions, including GTP-U encapsulation and decapsulation, SDAP QoS mapping, and PDCP sequence number handling. These operations are offloaded to hardware, allowing efficient packet processing directly in the NIC's data path. However, more computationally intensive functions, such as PDCP reordering and compression, must be performed in software on the BlueField-2 embedded ARM cores. Furthermore, due to the lack of cryptographic hardware acceleration in the BlueField-2 version used in our experiments, operations such as PDCP ciphering cannot be offloaded through the crypto and are instead executed in software. This limitation can significantly impact throughput and overall system performance, especially under high traffic loads. The FlexUP agent runs on the SmartNIC and interfaces with the FlexUP framework to coordinate processing decisions. For each flow, the agent determines whether it should be handled locally on the SmartNIC or forwarded to the host CPU.

FlexUP Controller. The FlexUP Controller, analogous to a control plane, is a centralized Python-based component responsible for making flow placement decisions across the CPU, SmartNIC, and programmable switch. It uses runtime information, such as flow requirements and resource availability, to assign each flow to the most suitable target. The controller communicates with the data plane through a lightweight control API, enabling efficient and low-latency reconfiguration. Detailed description of the MIP flow placement problem is provided in [72].

8.1.3 Usage and Interfaces

The high-level FlexUP workflow for offloading a CU-UP flow is depicted in Figure 75. While the figure presents an example with one switch and two SmartNICs, FlexUP is inherently target- and topology-independent. Therefore, the same workflow applies regardless of the specific hardware configuration or deployment scenario.

FIGURE 75: FLEXUP WORKFLOW.

In Step (1), the user plane traffic flow is initially processed by the traditional CPU-based CU-UP software implementation. Once the FlexUP agent detects its presence, in Step (2), reports this information to the FlexUP controller. The controller continuously monitors both the FlexUP agent and the software-based CU-UP instance to make informed offloading (flow placement) decisions. In Step (3), the FlexUP controller runs the flow placement decision model, considering the new (active) flow and deciding where to process it. Based on the output, in Step (4), the FlexUP controller installs the required configurations (for example, table entries) on the FlexUP agent. These configurations enable the agent to determine whether each flow should be offloaded in the underlying topology or handled by the traditional CU-UP. From Step (5), onward, the flow is processed directly in the data plane, effectively offloaded to the selected programmable switches or SmartNICs. In Step (6), the FlexUP agent continues to periodically report status updates to the controller, allowing the controller to monitor active flows and track the current state of the network.

This workflow enables fully transparent and adaptive offloading of CU-UP processing. By continuously monitoring flows, selecting the most suitable processing targets, and dynamically installing the required configurations, FlexUP seamlessly redirects flows from the traditional software-based CU-UP to programmable data-plane devices such as switches and SmartNICs. This process allows the infrastructure to automatically balance load, reduce latency, and improve energy efficiency, all while

remaining target- and topology-independent and without requiring any manual intervention or causing service disruption. From the network perspective, CU-UP continues to appear as a single unified component, while in reality, FlexUP offloads traffic in a distributed way across multiple heterogeneous devices. The FlexUP design ensures that existing interfaces, signalling procedures, and management operations remain intact, enabling seamlessly performance improvements (e.g., reduced latency or energy consumption) without disrupting the logical view of the RAN or requiring changes to higher-level network functions and standard interfaces.

8.1.4 Evaluation

The FlexUP evaluation was conducted on a testbed comprising two servers, a NVIDIA BlueField-2 SmartNIC, and an EdgeCore Wedge 100-32X Tofino switch. One server hosted a simplified srsRAN CU-UP, while another CU-UP instance was offloaded to the SmartNIC. The Tofino switch ran a minimal CU-UP implementation in P4. A secondary server with TRex traffic generator that emits synthetic packets emulating traffic from the DU.

The evaluation aimed to assess FlexUP's dynamic flow allocation decision layer, focusing on (i) *response and action time*, measuring how quickly FlexUP can detect new flows (e.g., URLLC) and allocate them to the optimal target to meet sub-ms deadlines and (ii) *allocation benefits*, quantifying latency, CPU utilization, and energy savings from offloading CU-UP processing to SmartNICs and switches.

FIGURE 76: HOST CPU POWER CONSUMPTION

FIGURE 77: FLOW ALLOCATION LATENCY

Figure 76 shows the host CPU power consumption (W) versus packet rate (pps) for URLLC, eMBB, and a 50:50 mixed traffic profile. Results show that URLLC traffic consumes the least CPU power, eMBB the most, with mixed traffic profiles in between, as larger eMBB packets trigger heavier processing for CPU-intensive functions such as encryption and compression, which scale with packet size, whereas the smaller URLLC packets require fewer CPU cycles per packet.

Figure 77 presents the time required for FlexUP to make and apply offloading decisions. Specifically, we emulated URLLC flows and measured the total time taken by the FlexUP controller to detect a new flow, decide upon flow placement (CPU, SmartNIC, or switch), and enforce the decision via the FlexUP agent. In the worst-case scenario, FlexUP completed the decision process in up to 29.30 ms. Additionally, we compare the CU-UP processing latency across the three devices, where the switch achieves the fastest response—up to 99.49% faster than the CPU, further reinforcing the benefits of intelligent offloading to hardware accelerators.

Overall, FlexUP demonstrates that it can achieve rapid decision times for URLLC flows, reduced CPU load and energy consumption through intelligent offloading, validating its potential for energy-efficient, low-latency RAN user-plane processing.

8.1.5 Limitations and future plans

Despite the promising capabilities of FlexUP, the current architecture presents some limitations. The fast path, implemented on programmable switches, does not support computationally intensive functions such as encryption, compression, or decompression. As a result, its applicability is constrained to scenarios where such functionalities are not required, which can limit its deployment in more security-sensitive or bandwidth-optimized contexts. Additionally, while the medium path running on SmartNICs like the BlueField-3 provides greater flexibility, its reliance on embedded ARM cores with limited processing resources can significantly impact overall performance, especially under high load or when executing complex CU-UP functions. Consequently, the slow path (CPU-based) must still be maintained to guarantee full functionality.

8.2 Offloading of security functions to Bluefield NICs

In future 6G infrastructures, real-time processing of user traffic will be essential. The User Plane Function (UPF), a critical component for handling user data, can be deployed on P4-programmable switches to enable telemetry through INT Reports on GTP streams. These real-time features can then be offloaded to accelerated functions—either for AI-based inference or in-network AI directly implemented using the internal CPU or GPU of a SmartNIC like the NVIDIA Bluefield-2 DPU.

SmartNICs such as the Bluefield-2 represent a significant evolution in networking hardware. By offloading resource-heavy security tasks like firewalls, intrusion detection, and DDoS mitigation from general-purpose CPUs, these DPUs reduce latency, increase throughput, and boost overall scalability. This is particularly important as growing network traffic threatens to overwhelm traditional CPU-based systems.

In the context of DDoS attacks, for example, immediate access to telemetry is a key feature for identifying and addressing abnormal traffic behavior. Bluefield DPUs enable real-time telemetry analysis and anomaly detection at line-speed, minimizing response delays and limiting damage. Offloading such security functions to Bluefield not only accelerates processing but also ensures more effective, hardware-level protection at the network edge.

8.2.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The integration of security functions directly into the data plane—through P4 programmability and SmartNIC acceleration—introduces several key innovations:

- **Real-Time Analysis:** By leveraging real-time telemetry, the system can detect and mitigate DDoS attacks more effectively than traditional approaches, addressing threats at both packet and flow levels.
- **Deep Learning Integration:** A CNN-based anomaly detection model is deployed to identify DDoS patterns with high precision, achieving 98.6% accuracy and an F1-score of 98%.
- **Advanced Telemetry Architecture:** A two-stage telemetry collection mechanism combines scalable packet processing with Fastcapa-based data compression and preprocessing, supporting traffic rates up to 100 Gbps.
- **Programmable Data Plane:** P4-based User Plane Functions (UPFs) enable flexible packet processing and in-network telemetry collection, bringing deep programmability to the data plane for enhanced visibility and control.

8.2.2 Implementation

In the implementation of this security use case for the 5G User Plane Function (UPF), referred to as 5G DDoS Attack Detection (5G-DAD), the system architecture is illustrated in Figure 78.

FIGURE 78: SECURITY OFFLOADING ARCHITECTURE

The experimental setup models a realistic Data Network (Data Net) composed of both benign and malicious traffic sources. Malicious nodes are configured to generate DDoS attacks targeting gNodeB

hosts, simulating volumetric attacks on the access edge of a 5G infrastructure. The programmable UPF, implemented using a P4-based data plane, is designed to export In-band Network Telemetry (INT) Reports related to GTP (GPRS Tunneling Protocol) traffic. These telemetry reports are transmitted to a Fastcapa-enabled Telemetry Collector running over DPDK, which ensures high-speed and low-latency packet processing even at high traffic volumes.

At the collector stage, essential features—such as flow duration, packet size distribution, and inter-arrival times—are extracted in real-time and streamed to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based detection engine. This AI model has been specifically trained for DDoS detection and operates continuously to flag anomalies with high accuracy.

In addition to real-time inference, the system includes a data acquisition pipeline for model training and refinement. Features and corresponding classifications are published to dedicated Kafka topics, while all processed and labeled samples are persistently stored in an InfluxDB time-series database. This setup enables continuous model improvement, replay-based testing, and historical analysis of attack scenarios.

The initial deployment focuses on onboarding the Fastcapa telemetry component onto the NVIDIA Bluefield-2 DPU, taking advantage of its programmable hardware and data plane offload capabilities. Future iterations aim to extend offloading to the AI detection stage, potentially utilizing the Bluefield-2's embedded GPU or CPU cores to run inference directly on the SmartNIC. This evolution would enable fully in-network detection, drastically reducing end-to-end latency and improving scalability by removing the need to forward data to external hosts for processing.

8.2.3 Usage and interfaces

The framework centers around a P4-based User Plane Function (UPF) that harnesses data plane programmability to enable advanced telemetry and traffic management. At its core, P4-programmed switches capture and process telemetry data, providing flexible and efficient network monitoring capabilities. These switches work in tandem with SmartNIC Data Processing Units (DPUs), which offload demanding computational tasks from the CPU. This offloading enhances overall system performance and facilitates real-time processing of high-bandwidth traffic flows.

Telemetry collection is performed through a two-stage process. Initially, a P4 telemetry collector captures and compresses data directly within the network. This is followed by a second stage where the DPDK-based Fastcapa framework preprocesses the telemetry packets, allowing for scalable, wire-speed packet processing. The processed telemetry data is then stored in an InfluxDB database, where it supports both training and inference operations using a CNN-based detection model.

The CNN analyzes various telemetry features—such as packet flow rates, inter-arrival times, and header information—to accurately detect DDoS attacks. Complementing the detection capabilities, the framework includes visualization tools that allow network operators to monitor performance metrics and identify anomalies in real time.

For testing and validation, the entire system was deployed within Docker containers, simulating realistic network conditions. The experimental environment consisted of malicious nodes generating DDoS traffic alongside normal traffic sources. P4 switches handled UPF-based GTP traffic management across interfaces N3, N6, and N9, while simultaneously generating telemetry data that was forwarded to the SmartNIC for processing.

8.2.4 Evaluation

Results show that, for 100 Gbps traffic with 1512B length, more than 8 million telemetry packets are generated per second by each P4 switch. The telemetry processing system takes 120 ns to process each packet. With a DPDK-based telemetry worker system, we use up to 5 CPU cores to process telemetry packets within a single pipeline designed to handle 100 Gbps. The Fastcapa server provides five types of DPDK workers on each CPU core to handle tasks such as pulling packets, ACL control, flow handling, Kafka topics handling, TCP connection maintenance, and CSV file generation. Results also show that the CNN is able to detect DDoS packets with 98.6% accuracy (see the CNN performance metrics in Figure 79).

FIGURE 79: PERFORMANCE METRICS OF THE CNN MODEL FOR DDoS ATTACK DETECTION

One limitation of the framework lies in its current focus on detecting and mitigating DDoS attacks. While effective for this type of threat, it does not yet address other significant security concerns, such as advanced persistent threats (APTs) or zero-day exploits, which are also critical in the 5G and 6G contexts. Another limitation is its reliance on specialized hardware, such as DPUs, which, while enhancing performance, may limit deployment in environments without such resources. Additionally, the dataset used for training and evaluation was collected in a controlled testbed environment. While this guarantees consistent results, it may not fully capture the variability and complexity of real-world traffic patterns, potentially impacting the generalization of the model. All the details of the implementation and results are reported in the published paper [20].

8.2.5 Limitations and further plans

While the framework demonstrates strong performance in detecting and mitigating DDoS attacks, it presents some limitations that must be addressed in future developments. Its current design is specialized for DDoS detection and does not yet accommodate broader security challenges such as advanced persistent threats (APTs) or zero-day exploits—both of which are highly relevant in emerging 5G and 6G environments. Another constraint stems from the framework’s reliance on specialized hardware, particularly DPUs. Although these components significantly boost performance through offloading and real-time processing, they may limit the framework’s applicability in scenarios where such hardware is unavailable or impractical to deploy. Moreover, the dataset used to train and evaluate the AI detection model was generated within a controlled testbed environment. While this ensures

reproducibility and stability, it may not reflect the full spectrum of variability found in real-world traffic, potentially affecting the model's ability to generalize to more complex or unpredictable conditions.

To overcome these limitations, future work will focus on integrating more sophisticated offloading techniques for AI-driven inference, broadening support for diverse and dynamic traffic patterns, and improving detection coverage to encompass a wider array of security threats. Additionally, research will continue into optimizing telemetry collection and preprocessing pipelines, aiming to reduce latency and improve scalability for real-time, high-throughput environments

8.3 Offloading of UPF to Bluefield NICs

The evolution of mobile networks towards 6G has introduced stringent requirements for high throughput, low latency, and scalable flow management. Traditional software-based User Plane Functions (UPFs) in 5G networks struggle to meet these demands due to performance bottlenecks in packet processing, GTP tunnel handling, and Quality of Service (QoS) enforcement. To address these challenges, offloading network functions to specialized hardware like NVIDIA's BlueField Data Processing Units (DPUs) has emerged as a promising solution. This module implements the offloading of network functions to BlueField NICs, focusing on its novelty, implementation, usage, evaluation, and future directions.

8.3.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The proposed 6GUPF architecture leverages the hardware acceleration capabilities of BlueField-3 DPUs and the DOCA Flow API to overcome limitations in existing UPF solutions. Unlike traditional software-based UPFs, which suffer from high CPU utilization and latency, the DPU-based approach offloads computationally intensive tasks such as GTP encapsulation/decapsulation and flow-based QoS enforcement to the hardware. This significantly reduces latency and improves throughput.

A key novelty of this work lies in its integration of Stateful Flow Table (SFT) offload capabilities, enabling support for over 500K User Equipment (UE) IDs and 4 million concurrent flows. This surpasses the scalability of existing solutions like HiP4-UPF [21], which is constrained by SRAM and TCAM limitations in Tofino-based P4 switches. Additionally, the DOCA Flow API provides programmable packet

processing directly in the data path, ensuring flexibility without sacrificing performance. The architecture also introduces flow-based acceleration features such as receive-side symmetric scaling (RSS) for efficient core utilization and non-blocking state management, further enhancing performance in multi-core environments.

8.3.2 Implementation

The implementation of the 6GUPF architecture involves a Dell R760 server equipped with an NVIDIA BlueField-3 DPU, featuring two QSFP network ports for interfacing with base stations and data centers. The DOCA SDK is installed on the DPU to program the pipelines for packet processing. The ingress pipeline consists of five primary tables:

1. GTP Default Forward Table: it routes GTP-U packets for processing.
2. IP Default Forward Table: it manages forwarding of standard IP packets.
3. GTP Encap Table: it handles GTP-U header encapsulation for outgoing IP packets.
4. GTP Decap Table: it removes GTP-U headers from incoming packets.
5. L2 Forward Table: it modifies source MAC addresses post-encapsulation/decapsulation.

Dynamic rules are added to the pipeline during runtime, allowing packets matching specific headers to bypass the host server entirely. The DOCA Flow API ensures efficient packet classification, QoS assignment, and forwarding, with telemetry data providing insights into pipeline performance.

8.3.3 Usage and interfaces

The 6GUPF architecture interfaces with the N3 (gNodeB) and N6 (data network) interfaces, enabling seamless integration into existing 5G/6G networks. The DOCA QoS Engine plays a critical role in parsing and processing IP flows, performing classification, policy enforcement, load balancing, and scheduling. Each uplink/downlink IP flow is encapsulated into GTP-U Protocol Data Units (PDUs) and associated with a QoS Flow Identifier (QFI), which maps to Data Radio Bearers (DRBs) at the gNodeB. This ensures end-to-end QoS enforcement with minimal CPU intervention.

The system supports three priority levels for QoS:

- High Priority: For latency-sensitive applications (e.g., autonomous driving, medical robotics).
- Medium Priority: For high-throughput but less latency-sensitive applications (e.g., video streaming).
- Low Priority: For applications tolerant to latency and throughput variations (e.g., IoT backhaul).

8.3.4 Evaluation

The performance of the DPU-based 6GUPF was evaluated using traffic generators (VIAVI and TRex) to emulate realistic 6G network conditions. Key metrics included throughput, latency, CPU utilization, and packet drop rates. The obtained results are shown in Figure 80: and are summarized in the following, highlighting the benefits with respect to existing deployments:

1. Throughput: The DPU achieved near-line-rate performance of 200 Gbps for 1500-byte MTUs, outperforming NIC-based implementations (89 Gbps) and DPDK-based UPFs (34.61 Gbps). For smaller MTUs (128 bytes), the DPU maintained 30 Gbps, significantly higher than the 6 Gbps achieved by software UPFs.
2. Latency: At 80 Gbps traffic load, the DPU reduced latency to 0.3 ms, compared to 0.9 ms for NIC-based systems.
3. CPU Utilization: Offloading tasks to the DPU reduced CPU usage to 22% at 80 Gbps, compared to 50% for NIC-based implementations.
4. Packet Drop Rate: The DPU-based system exhibited a drop rate of only 0.29% under high load, while NIC-based systems suffered a 10% drop rate.

These results demonstrate the superiority of the DPU-based approach in meeting the demands of 6G networks.

FIGURE 80: 6GUPF IN BF3: PERFORMANCE RESULTS

8.3.5 Limitations and further plans

Despite its advantages, the current implementation has limitations:

- Dependency on BlueField DPUs: The architecture is tightly coupled with NVIDIA’s hardware, limiting portability to other platforms.
- Complexity of DOCA Programming: Developing and optimizing DOCA pipelines requires specialized expertise.

- Scalability Testing: While the system supports 500K UEs, further testing is needed for ultra-large-scale deployments (e.g., millions of IoT devices).
- Future work will focus on:
 - Edge Deployment: Extending the architecture to edge-based UPFs for localized processing.
 - Support for Emerging 6G Use Cases: Enhancing the system for applications like holographic communications and tactile internet.
 - Integration with AI/ML: Leveraging machine learning for dynamic QoS adaptation and anomaly detection.

8.4 Accelerated Neural Network Execution

DESIRE6G architecture leverages SOL Neural Network compiler to transparently accelerate neural networks workloads, as described in D4.1 [1]. The compiler is integrated in the architecture as the SOL server, which is described in D4.2 [4].

In this section, we report advancements of both the compiler and the server.

8.4.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

As described in D4.2 [4], SOL emerges in the neural network optimization area for its versatility, being able to support both inference and training and a variety of hardware platforms, such as NVIDIA GPUs, x86 processors, and NEC Sx-Aurora Tsubasa Vector Engine.

8.4.2 Implementation

8.4.2.1 SOL compiler

The SOL compiler has received significant updates aimed at improving its functionality, compatibility, and performance. Advanced gather and scatter operations, such as *torch.scatter*, *torch.index_select*, and related PyTorch functions, are now supported, along with a broader range of PyTorch loss functions. Compatibility with major libraries has been increased, with *Torchvision* now at 83%, TIMM at 93%, *KerasApplications* at 100%, and Transformers at 52%. On the performance front, the compiler has been

upgraded to utilize the CUDNN v9 API, which introduces post-operation layer fusion for greater efficiency, and now incorporates the CUBLASLT API for better auto-tuning capabilities. Additionally, the SOL compiler now supports n-th order gradients through *torch.autograd.backward* and features an improved determinism system, enabling users to loosen accuracy requirements and use faster PRNG algorithms when desired.

8.4.2.2 SOL server

We extended the SOL server functionalities, by adding support for full lifecycle management of the ML models deployed. In D4.2 [4], we reported an initial version of the server with two endpoints⁵: *deploy-model*, which triggers the optimization of the neural network with SOL and its deployment as an object file; *get-model* for retrieving the deployed model, containing the object file and its dependencies, after the compiling process is completed.

In the latest version, we added support for GPU targets, as the previous version was supporting CPU targets only and extended the deployment endpoint to specify the target hardware as a parameter. Furthermore, we added four new endpoints to retrieve the models list, delete and update already deployed models and re-deploy a model. Table 12 shows the full list of the server endpoints with their parameters and a description.

TABLE 12: SOL SERVER ENDPOINTS

Endpoint	Operation	Parameters	Description
deploy-model	POST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> model file username modelName device batch size height width 	<p>It receives a neural network model and triggers its optimization, for a CPU or GPU device, with SOL's deploy function. All the parameters are mandatory.</p> <p>It returns a uuid unique identifier to retrieve the model when the deployment process is over</p>

⁵ In D4.2 [], the two endpoints were called /upload and /check-status but we report here the new names.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • channels 	
get-model	GET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uuid 	It returns a deployed neural network model in the form of an object file that can be called via a C or Python function. It also returns also the dependencies needed to use the object file
list-models	GET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uuid • username • device 	It returns the list of the models in the server and their metadata that matches the specified parameters. If no parameters are specified, it returns the list of all the models available in the server
delete-model	DELETE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uuid 	It deletes a specific model in the server
update-model	PATCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uuid • username • modelname • device • batch size • height • width • channels 	It updates one or more metadata of a model in the server. The uuid parameter is mandatory
redeploy-model	PUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • model file • uuid 	It triggers the redeployment of a specific model in the server. All the parameters are mandatory

8.4.3 Usage and Interfaces

The usage and interfaces of the SOL server have been described in D4.2 [4] and there are no sensible variations to report.

8.4.4 Evaluation

We evaluated the capabilities of SOL by optimizing and testing several computer vision models from the popular Torchvision library⁶. We performed the optimization for two target devices, a NVIDIA L40 GPU⁷ and an AMD EPYC 7702p CPU⁸. In our evaluation we considered three metrics – latency, throughput and power consumption – and compared the results with a PyTorch baseline of the same model.

The results presented in the following sub-sections are measured during inference. In the power consumption sub-section, we also report results measured during training.

8.4.4.1 Latency

Figure 81 shows the results of latency in the GPU. SOL, in green, is consistently faster than the PyTorch baseline in all the 60 models tested. The same trend can be observed in the CPU tests, shown in Figure 82, with SOL having a smaller advantage in comparison to the baseline. Table 12 summarizes some statistics on the latency registered in GPU and CPU. In average, the SOL version of a neural network is more than 6 times and almost 2 times faster than the baseline in GPU and CPU respectively.

⁶ <https://docs.pytorch.org/vision/0.9/models>

⁷ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/data-center/l40/>

⁸ <https://www.amd.com/de/products/processors/server/epyc/7002-series.html>

FIGURE 81: GPU LATENCY - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH BASELINE IN RED

FIGURE 82: CPU LATENCY PER INFERENCE: SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED.

TABLE 13: LATENCY STATISTICS

Device	Framework	Mean [msec]	Gain	Std	Min [msec]	Max [msec]
GPU	PyTorch	8.67	-	5.63	0.84	28.84

	SOL	1.38	6.28x	1.43	0.21	9.65
CPU	PyTorch	53.76	-	42.66	9.19	151.34
	SOL	27.59	1.95x	23.71	4.59	109.09

8.4.4.2 Throughput

Also the throughput, measured in number of inferences per second, is consistently higher than the baseline both in GPU and CPU, shown in Figure 83 and Figure 84, respectively. As shown in Table 14 in average SOL throughput is 9 times higher in the GPU and almost 2 times higher in the CPU.

FIGURE 83: GPU THROUGHPUT - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED

FIGURE 84: GPU THROUGHPUT - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED

TABLE 14: THROUGHPUT STATISTICS

Device	Framework	Mean [inf/s]	Gain	Std	Min [inf/s]	Max [inf/s]
GPU	PyTorch	180.42	-	167.51	34.67	1185.62
	SOL	1698.61	9.43x	1483.86	103.56	4577.78
CPU	PyTorch	34.77	-	29.06	1.86	13.33
	SOL	66.78	1.92x	51.62	1.88	22.84

8.4.4.3 Power consumption

The power consumption measurements have been performed on the GPU only, as we leveraged the nvidia-smi⁹ tool to read the power consumption of the NVIDIA L40. We could not perform the measurements on the CPU as we did not have a similar tool available. In GPU Power consumption during

⁹ <https://developer.nvidia.com/system-management-interface>

inference - SOL in green, PyTorch in red. In Figure 85 and Figure 86 we can see how also in this case SOL is performing better than the baseline, consuming less power. In average, the PyTorch baseline consumes 2.8 and 2.1 more energy than the SOL version, as shown in Table 15.

FIGURE 85: GPU POWER CONSUMPTION DURING INFERENCE - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED.

FIGURE 86: GPU POWER CONSUMPTION DURING TRAINING - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED.

TABLE 15: POWER CONSUMPTION RESULTS

ML phase	Framework	Mean [J]	Gain	Std	Min [J]	Max [J]
Inference	PyTorch	0.73	-	0.45	0.17	1.87
	SOL	0.26	2.81x	0.12	0.17	0.61
Training	PyTorch	2.90	-	1.44	0.43	7.18
	SOL	1.39	2.08x	0.74	0.44	2.81

8.4.5 Limitations and further plans

Our evaluation shows how the SOL compiler can boost the neural network execution performance in the two dimensions of latency and throughput. Besides, we showed how a faster execution (or training) translates into power saving. The SOL server is a strategic component of the DESIRE6G architecture to enhance neural network execution, leading to better performances, compared to a PyTorch baseline, in all three dimensions explored, and especially for GPU targets. We observe that the performance gains for CPU targets are not as good as the GPU ones. We plan to further improve the SOL compiler in this direction.

8.5 Remote hardware accelerators in applications with vAccel

The vAccel framework has evolved into a fully modular, production-ready solution for seamless hardware acceleration across heterogeneous environments—ranging from edge devices (e.g., Raspberry Pi, Jetson) to cloud nodes with GPUs and SmartNICs. In contrast to traditional acceleration libraries that expose low-level device-specific APIs, vAccel abstracts functionality at the application level, enabling developers to use simple, high-level primitives (e.g., `classify_image`, `depth_estimate`) while transparently targeting the appropriate accelerator via a dynamic plugin system.

Through continued development in DESIRE6G, the framework now features:

- A native Python interface, unlocking integration with ML workloads and rapid prototyping.
- Tighter integration with NEC’s SOL runtime, offering near-zero overhead hardware dispatch.

- Demonstrated support for complex PyTorch models, such as monocular depth estimation, packaged and deployed over vAccel with remote acceleration capabilities.

8.5.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The architecture of vAccel has matured significantly and is now structured to support:

- **Layered Abstraction via Dispatch Engine:** The core library serves as a dispatch handler for all vAccel API calls, dynamically resolving them to the appropriate backend plugin. This enables the same application code to target different hardware simply by changing the plugin configuration—no recompilation or modification needed.
- **Modular Plugin System:** Plugins encapsulate hardware-specific implementations of abstract operations. These can be local (e.g., running on an attached accelerator) or remote (via a vAccel agent). For example, one plugin might offload inference to a local GPU, while another uses a remote TPU cluster or DPU-enabled node.
- **Unified High-Level API:** Instead of exposing device-centric calls (e.g., CUDA kernels), vAccel exposes application-oriented functions like `classify_image`, `matrix_multiply`, `depth_estimate`, or even `model.predict`. This makes it easy to plug acceleration into applications without requiring ML engineers or developers to specialize in hardware APIs.
- **Remote Execution via Transparent Transport Layer:** Remote plugins use RPC-like communication to forward requests to remote vAccel agents, which act as microservices running the actual model or computation on a hardware accelerator. This model preserves abstraction while enabling low-end devices to benefit from high-performance inference backends.

8.5.2 Implementation

The current implementation includes several production-grade components:

- **vAccel Core (C Library):** Acts as the central dispatch handler and plugin loader. It is lightweight, fast, and designed for embedded use as well as high-performance servers.

- **Python Interface:** A new native Python binding allows Python applications (including PyTorch-based pipelines) to invoke vAccel operations directly. This unlocks broader compatibility with ML research tools and enables end-to-end model deployment through simple Python scripts.
- **SOL Runtime Integration:** vAccel now embeds more tightly with NEC's SOL runtime. Inference operations can be offloaded through SOL-managed runtimes, benefitting from shared memory, zero-copy transport, and tightly coupled lifecycle management.
- **Demo Application – Monocular Depth Estimation (Demo 2):** A PyTorch-based model for monocular depth estimation has been integrated into the vAccel pipeline as a proof-of-concept. The model is executed remotely via a vAccel agent, with the front-end invoking it through the Python API. This demonstrates how complex ML models can be offloaded from constrained clients to accelerated backends transparently.

8.5.3 Usage and Interfaces

Developers can choose between a C interface for embedded applications or the Python API for AI/ML use cases. The APIs expose high-level function calls that abstract over device-specific logic.

Applications can be bound to specific hardware targets by selecting a plugin via configuration—no code changes required. For instance, a single Python application can run on Jetson, x86+GPU, or a SmartNIC cluster depending on the loaded plugin.

Through vAccel's plugin system, applications can execute operations on remote devices (via RPC calls), enabling constrained edge devices to transparently offload ML inference.

Tutorials and quick-start guides are available, with simple examples for running local and remote operations. The Python API¹⁰ significantly lowers the barrier for AI workloads.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel-python>

8.5.4 Evaluation

To validate the efficiency of the vAccel framework, we conducted an evaluation using the YOLOv8s object detection model running on a Raspberry Pi 5. Four execution modes were compared:

- Stock (Torch, CPU) – baseline PyTorch execution on the Pi5 CPU.
- vAccel-Local (CPU) – inference via vAccel using the CPU backend on the Pi5.
- vAccel-Jetson (Remote GPU) – inference transparently offloaded through vAccel to a Jetson Orin GPU.
- vAccel-BF (Remote GPU) – inference transparently offloaded through vAccel to an x86 server equipped with a discrete GPU (“bf” configuration).

FIGURE 87: VACCCEL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION FOR YOLOV8S

The results are summarized in average throughput across 50 inference frames and demonstrate the following:

- Stock PyTorch (CPU): ~1.25 FPS
- vAccel-Local (CPU): ~1.21 FPS, showing negligible overhead compared to the baseline.

- vAccel-Jetson (Remote GPU): ~5.70 FPS, representing a ~4.5x speedup over the CPU baseline.
- vAccel-BF (Remote GPU): ~6.96 FPS, achieving the highest throughput with a ~5.6x improvement over CPU execution.

The evaluation results (Figure 87) demonstrate that vAccel introduces negligible runtime overhead when operating locally on the CPU, as the vAccel-local configuration performs almost identically to native PyTorch execution. More importantly, the framework enables transparent acceleration on remote GPU backends without requiring any code modifications. Both the Jetson Orin and the x86 GPU node achieved significant performance gains, with the latter delivering the highest throughput overall. This confirms that vAccel effectively scales workloads across different hardware tiers, from lightweight embedded accelerators to high-performance compute nodes. In practice, this means that constrained devices such as the Raspberry Pi 5 can benefit from remote execution, seamlessly accessing high-performance inference backends while maintaining the same simple, unified programming interface.

8.5.5 Limitations and further plans

While vAccel now supports Python and complex inference tasks, future work will focus on:

- Expanding plugin coverage for more ML frameworks (e.g., ONNX Runtime, TensorRT).
- Extending transport mechanisms (e.g., QUIC, WebRTC) for wider deployment scenarios.
- Introducing plugin capabilities for model lifecycle management (loading, caching, versioning).
- Enhancing multi-model support and parallel execution on shared hardware.

vAccel remains an **open-source project**, developed and maintained by NUBIS under the **Apache-2.0 license**:

- GitHub: <https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel>
- Documentation: <https://docs.vaccel.org>

8.6 In-network computing with P4RROT

P4RROT is a Python-based library developed at Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE) that automates the generation of P4 programs for application-layer offloading. Instead of wrestling with P4’s low-level parsing, header-length adjustments and checksum recalculations, developers describe payload-centric logic in Python using intuitive constructs such as `FlowProcessor`—which defines inputs, outputs, local and shared state—and `FlowSelector`, which steers matching packets into the appropriate processor. Under the hood, P4RROT builds an abstract syntax tree of composable `Command` objects (e.g., assignments, comparisons, conditional branches, send-back operations) and injects the resulting code into target-specific P4 templates. This approach not only generates human-readable P4 for BMv2 switches and Netronome SmartNICs, but also supports pre-generation simulation of the data-plane behaviour and simple “hints” to choose, for instance, table-based versus if-else implementations. By elevating application-layer transformations to a high-level API, P4RROT hides boilerplate complexity and accelerates the path from algorithm to deployed P4 program.

8.6.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

P4 has proven useful for implementing application-layer tasks, but even simple functionalities can quickly result in complex software projects. This is due to the limitations of the underlying devices and the fact that P4 was not designed to support this kind of computations. On the other hand, different targets have their own limitations and constraints that need to be considered during the development of data plane programs. These constraints and the immaturity of P4 compilers usually make the code very complex at the end. Automatic code generation can greatly simplify implementing application-layer tasks if we narrow down the scope of target features. By application-layer tasks, we mean functionalities concerned about the payload rather than protocols of traditional networking layers. P4RROT is a code generator (in form of a library) for P4 to support and speed up the offloading process of application layer tasks, and implements the target-dependent optimizations behind the scenes. In the past, different code generators have been introduced for various use cases to reduce the software development complexity. Lucid is a programming language providing an event-driven abstraction for implementing control functionalities for the Intel Tofino switch. Sonata offers a scalable and flexible

query language to collect information about the network traffic. Poise is able to define context-aware security policies. Marple offers real-time performance monitoring using its Python-like query language. These examples among many others CITE all emit P4 code for selected use cases and mostly focusing on a single P4 target. In contrast, P4RROT aims to have a general-purpose code generator to support the offloading of various application layer tasks to P4 data planes. It currently supports three different targets including BMv2, Netronome Agilio SmartNIC and Intel Tofino ASIC (TNA).

8.6.2 Implementation

FIGURE 88: HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE OF P4RROT

Figure 88 illustrates the architecture of the P4RROT code generator. It takes two inputs: a P4 template describing the usual parts of a pipeline, and the application-specific logic using P4RROT’s API. After running the code generator, we get a P4 code that can be further compiled to the desired target using the vendor-provided compiler. Though in DESIRE6G, we mostly reuse P4RROT as an alternative data plane library, we also extended it with the support of Intel Tofino ASIC

8.6.3 Usage and Interfaces

P4RROT is a library-driven P4 code generator designed to simplify the creation of “offloading” applications—packet-processing logic that runs directly on a programmable switch. It has been written in Python and provides a Python API. Its core components are:

- **FlowProcessor:** A declarative, fluent API for defining application-layer computations. You specify input/output headers (e.g., a byte for a guess and two bytes for a response),

local and shared state (like the secret number), and then chain high-level commands (including If/Then/Else, Switch, and atomic blocks) to express your algorithm.

Internally, these are mapped to P4 constructs, and the library can even perform semantic checks or simulate your logic.

- **FlowSelector:** A way to pick which packets your offloaded logic applies to. You declare one or more selectors (e.g., IPv4/UDP with a given port or custom look-ahead fields) arranged as a chain of parser states. Matching packets enter your FlowProcessor; others fall through or go to a default state. The generator neatly injects `#define` pragmas to manage empty chains or optional selectors.
- **Templates:** Static P4 skeletons that handle baseline parsing and forwarding. Your generated code is spliced in via `#include` pragmas. Templates must expose certain metadata variables (to track added/removed bytes, manage atomicity, etc.) and can be customized with extra macros to suit more complex scenarios.

```

fp = FlowProcessor(
    istruct = [('guess', uint8_t)],
    locals = [('l', bool_t), ('good', bool_t), ('solution', uint8_t)],
    ostruct = [('r1', uint8_t), ('r2', uint8_t)],
    state = [ SharedVariable('shared_solution', uint8_t) ]
)

fp\
.add(Comment('init variables'))\
.add(ReadFromShared('solution', 'shared_solution'))\
.add(AssignConst('good', True))\
.add(AssignConst('r1', ord(':')))\
.add(AssignConst('r2', ord(' ')))\
.add(Comment('check whether solution<guess'))\
.add(LessThan('l', 'solution', 'guess'))\
.add(If('l'))\
    .add(AssignConst('r1', ord('x')))\
    .add(AssignConst('r2', ord('<')))\
    .add(AssignConst('good', False))\
.EndIf()\
.add(Comment('check whether solution>guess'))\
.add(GreaterThan('l', 'solution', 'guess'))\
.add(If('l'))\
    .add(AssignConst('r1', ord('x')))\
    .add(AssignConst('r2', ord('>')))\
    .add(AssignConst('good', False))\
.EndIf()\
.add(Comment('generate a new number if required'))\
.add(If('good')) \
    .add(AssignRandomValue('solution', 0, 255))\
    .add(WriteToShared('shared_solution', 'solution'))\
.EndIf()\
.add(Comment('send back the result'))\
.add(SendBack())

fs = FlowSelector(
    'IPV4_UDP',
    [(UdpDstPort, 5555)],
    fp
)

solution = Solution()
solution.add_flow_processor(fp)
solution.add_flow_selector(fs)
solution.get_generated_code().dump('test.p4app')

```

Defining inputs and outputs and other variables for the FlowProcessor

Populating processing steps

Channeling the proper packets to the FlowProcessor with the FlowSelector

Composing the parts of the solution.

FIGURE 89: EXAMPLE ON HOW P4RROT CAN IMPLEMENT A SIMPLE NUMBER GUESSING GAME

Figure 89 shows an example P4RROT program that offloads a simple “guess-the-number” game: the client’s guess arrives in a packet, the switch compares it to a stored secret, updates shared

state if needed, and replies with “low,” “high,” or “win”—all composed in a few dozen lines of high-level code that the generator turns into full P4.

8.6.4 Evaluation

The evaluation case study revolves around a service supporting real-time data streams, as they for example appear in the context of high-frequency trading where interested parties monitor market events (e.g. buy and sell orders, executed transactions). We consider the ITCH application layer protocol provided by NASDAQ. ITCH messages are sent to the customer using MoldUDP as a transport layer, which is similar to the original UDP protocol but with a special payload structure. After the standard UDP header, there are three additional fields: session (identifying the stream), sequence number (the ID of the first message), and message count (the number of messages included in the MoldUDP packet). Finally, we find the message blocks consisting of two parts: the length of the ITCH message and the ITCH message itself.

Clients can detect packet loss by observing the MoldUDP sequence numbers. In case of a loss, they can request the missing messages from a different retransmission server. Our task is to request retransmission automatically, thus saving time. A retransmission request has the same structure as every MoldUDP packet with a slightly different meaning: session, sequence number (the ID of the first requested message), and message count (number of consecutive messages requested).

We compared the reaction time of the data plane offloaded and the original software MoldUDP implementations. Our test MoldUDP server sent out a packet in every second where each packet triggered a retransmission request. Figure 90 depicts the observed response times on a 2x25G Netronome smartNIC between two servers. We used tcpdump to capture the relevant packets and iperf to generate background traffic. The offloaded solution requests retransmission faster 50-70ms, compared to the 70-550ms response times of the non-offloaded software implementation. Moreover, the response time of the offloaded implementation was less affected even by the 10 Gbps background traffic. We also repeated this experiment with an Intel Tofino ASIC. The P4rrot program was basically the same. The observed response times are depicted in Figure 90 for various background traffic intensities. The response time is in the sub-millisecond range (1-2usec) in the base case. If the egress

port is overloaded the latency increases because of the queueing effect, this can be solved by introducing a dedicated high-priority queue for the latency sensitive MoldUDP traffic. In that case, the observed latency distribution is the same as in the base case.

FIGURE 90. THE OBSERVED RESPONSE TIMES ON A 2X25G NETRONOME SMARTNIC

We also repeated the same measurement when the same P4RROT program is deployed on a Tofino ASIC. In the first scenario without background traffic, the response times in a similar setting were always below 0.04 ms. In case of 5Gbps background traffic, the response times diverge: over 90% of offloaded responses have remained below 0.05 ms and largest observed response time was also below 0.1 ms. Note that the observed increase in the response time was caused by the queueing effect of the background flows. However, we can further reduce the response times if the latency critical application traffic is isolated from the background traffic by, e.g., placing the packets to a high priority queue while the background packets to a lower priority one.

8.6.5 Limitations and further plans

P4RROT currently supports three different targets: bmv2 software switch, Netronome Agilio smartNIC and Intel Tofino ASIC. The supported features also differ as the bmv2 target is the most flexible and the Tofino ASIC is the most restrictive target. Adding a new target support to P4RROT is possible but requires the implementation of different code generator primitives for the new target that may be

challenging the requires deep knowledge of the target device. The source code of P4RROT including the Tofino porting done in DESIRE6G is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/Team-P4RROT/P4RROT>

8.7 Teraflow SDN controller for PREOF

In previous deliverables, we described PREOF, a feature of Deterministic Networking (DetNet) that enhances network reliability through four main functions: (1) Sequencing information, (2) Replication, (3) Elimination, and (4) Ordering. As outlined in Deliverable D4.2, Section 8.5, PREOF was developed using network programmability technologies—specifically, P4 (on Tofino switches) for the implementation of the first three functions, and DPDK (on servers) for the Ordering function.

In that implementation, the control of the Tofino switches was carried out through Python scripts executed locally on each switch. As a step forward in the development, we aimed to externalize this control by employing a Software Defined Networking (SDN) controller capable of contributing to the TeraFlow technology stack.

This deliverable focuses on the detailed explanation of this advancement.

8.7.1 Novelty beyond the state-of-the-art

The integration of a SDN controller into Tofino-based switches (Intel, 2025) for controlling a DetNet network represents important novelty in terms of being able to dynamically configure, program and control the hardware switches to perform PREOF.

Tofino switches are P4-capable, which means that their data plane can be programmed internal or externally using the P4 language, thus enabling a wide range of possible behaviours for the switches. DetNet requires that the switches composing the network behave differently depending on the type of function they should enforce (for instance, they might need to forward packets, but also, they should be able to eliminate or replicate them). Although the programmability of the data plane can be achieved internally in the switch by loading, configuring, compiling and running P4 programs in the switch, using a SDN controller enables the advantages of SDN networks in the DetNet, allowing for a dynamic remote

control of the switches, and allowing the integration for controlling, management and orchestration platforms.

Moreover, using the Teraflow SDN controller (which is the ETSI standard for SDN controllers) is interesting because of its modular high-performance capable design, P4 compatibility and general SDN features. The integration of this controller with Tofino switches is a challenge that has not yet been properly solved, as there are compatibility issues based on the different Southbound APIs deployed that need to be specifically addressed.

Enabling the integration between Teraflow SDN and Tofino switches will be not only novel and interesting from the project point of view, but beneficial for the technologies used, adding extra functionality to the controller and the switches, and paving the way for further research in fields such as telemetry or network automation.

8.7.2 Implementation

The implementation of this integration has focused on programmatic control over the Tofino Switches through the Teraflow SDN controller. In Figure 91 it is shown how this component determines the communications between the controller and the switches, and how it is integrated in the DetNet network that is part of the demonstration scenario.

FIGURE 91: TERAFLW SDN CONTROLLER CONTROLLING EDGECORE P4-ENABLED SWITCHES IN THE DETNET ENVIRONMENT

Given the complexity of directly integrating the controller with production Tofino hardware (as pointed out in the previous section), we have adopted a phase-based strategy.

Phase 1 - Simulator-based development

In a first phase we have developed and validated a complete toolchain using a Tofino software simulator. The goal was to establish end-to-end interaction with the switch data plane via gRPC. The core components include custom python scripts that load P4 programs into the Tofino simulator, retrieve and inspect table definitions and current entries, and add runtime match-action entries to switch tables. The components also include support for multiple P4 behaviours such as packet duplication, port forwarding and packet filtering.

The virtual environment used for the simulation is based on open-p4studio, and it aims to ease the development laboratory tests over P4 switches based on TNA (Tofino Network Architecture) without compromising the hardware scenario.

Phase 2 - Toward real hardware replication

After validating the full pipeline in simulation (including P4 compilation, runtime configuration, and packet test verification), the second implementation phase consists of replicating the real hardware-based scenario within the software simulator.

This involves configuring the simulated environment to match the actual switch topology and behaviour, enabling pre-validation of use cases before physical deployment. This step is critical to ensure that the solution will be portable and functional on Telefónica's actual infrastructure.

Phase 3 - Remote hardware controlling

This latest phase completes the implementation of the remote-control module for the Tofino switches. The Teraflow SDN controller includes, in its latest release (May 2025), support for P4 switching control via the P4Runtime communication interface. However, not all Tofino-based switches support this interface natively, using a different API called BFRT. To avoid this issue, it is sometimes possible to modify the control software in the Tofino switches using the code developed by the Stratum project. This solution is not valid for every hardware Tofino switch in the market, and unfortunately, the specific Edgecore CSP-7550 switches used by Telefónica for the demo are not compatible with that software.

Having these issues in mind, the phase 3 has been developed following different work lines:

- Developing a new Teraflow SDN controller module, which would be able to communicate with Tofino native switches using the BFRT API. We have analysed the Teraflow SDN controller architecture, identifying the components to develop, based on the recent supported P4runtime.
- Developing a translator between P4runtime and BRFT, based on similar feature from Stratum. This translation software runs in the Tofino switch and listens to p4runtime requests from the controller, translating them into the BFRT API used in the switch.

In parallel, aiming to develop a contribution to the Teraflow SDN project we have worked on combining open-p4studio and Stratum, developing an open-source complete tool that will allow the simulation of Tofino-based switches controlled from Teraflow via P4runtime.

8.7.3 Usage and Interfaces

The main interfaces to interact with this component are based on the APIs deployed by the controller and the communications between the controller and the switches (both simulated and actual hardware switches). Additionally, the current control of the switches is performed by CLI-style script-based interfaces developed in Python.

- Northbound interfaces: The Teraflow SDN controller deploys a REST-based API to communicate with other components, offering information from the controlled network.
- Southbound interfaces: gRPC APIs are used to remotely communicate the controller and switches, interacting with the P4 pipeline. The specific API implementations used by the different components are based on P4runtime and BRFT.
- CLI scripts: A set of Python scripts have been developed and allow us to use and control the different features of the switches remotely (load compiled P4 programs, verifying program status, listing current tables in the switch, inserting match entries in the switch tables or running different traffic-based tests).

8.7.4 Evaluation

For the evaluation of this component, we have initially used a controlled simulated environment that replicates the expected behaviour of the hardware Tofino switches. Once we reach certain milestones in the development plan, we plan to test the features on the actual hardware environment.

The functional evaluation of each implemented feature is performed by determining the correct behaviour of each part of the component (for instance, the successful load and execution of P4 programs, the correct gRPC-based configuration and modification of table entries or the end-to-end verification of the functionality using packet-based tests).

Additionally, we use observability and debugging tools to inspect the table state and to debug the code and determine if the expected behaviour is met.

The simulation environment approach has allowed us to mirror the actual testing environment and running comprehensive, reproducible tests in a sandbox environment, before deploying changes on the physical counterpart. This approach can also be seen as a risk mitigation layer, ensuring compatibility and reducing development friction when transitioning to real hardware devices.

For the final evaluation results, given the nature of this component and its integration with the PREOF scenario, we intend to detail the technical evaluation results along with demo 2, and they will be presented in the deliverables related to the demo (D5.3).

8.7.5 Limitations and further plans

The main limitation of the developed component relies on the incompatibility between the different southbound APIs used by the controller and the hardware switches for the P4-based control. This issue may limit the integration of the Teraflow SDN controller and the features that can be used with this specific scenario. In any case, our implementation from phase 3, aims to allow for the remote control of the switches in the main behaviours required by the PREOF scenario, enabling the correct function of the Deterministic Network. On the other hand, we aim to contribute to the Teraflow SDN controller with code that will enable the control of Tofino-based switches in simulation scenarios.

9 Conclusion

In this deliverable we presented the final report on the components of the unified programmable data plane. In this document we summarized the efforts made in WP4, detailing the work done during months 24 to 32 of the project and referencing the work documented in the previous deliverables where applicable, to avoid unnecessary repetitions.

The components described in this document are the result of the DESIRE6G architecture design presented in deliverable D2.2, enabling the DESIRE6G architecture to meet its goals of programmability, efficiency, and performance. They highlight the innovations in site-specific resource management, cloud-native data plane optimization for unique latency and performance needs, programmable traffic management, pervasive monitoring and the integration of application and hardware accelerators.

We first presented how the unified programmable data plane components meet the programmable data plane and pervasive monitoring requirements of DESIRE6G architecture and how they fit into the overall service requirements picture. We then highlighted how some of the project KPIs are fulfilled by the components developed in WP4. We finally provided the final updates on the components reported in D4.1 and D4.2, and presented some new components for performance isolation for deep slicing, pervasive monitoring and network function offloading, capturing the novelty beyond the state-of-the-art, implementation and deployment aspect, usage and interfaces, limitations and potential improvement ideas related to these modules beyond the DESIRE6G project timeframe.

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